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Masterarbeit

Annotation-based Modeling of Non-functional Requirements and Analysis Results in Domain-driven Design

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Abstract

Runtime quality analysis such as resilience and load testing assists software engineers in identifying deviations of quality requirements in business-critical applications. Thus, different stakeholders need to reason about the business' domain from a common point of view to refine the model to their needs. Domain-driven-Design empowers stakeholders to elaborate domain models in a concise manner using a Ubiquitous Language for communication. Modeling languages such as UML and MARTE are often too technical for this purpose. In contrast, Domain Storytelling naturally fits into this methodology by using pictographic storytelling and the Ubiquitous Language to collaboratively shape the domain in Domain Stories. However, three fundamental problems arise. (P1) Domain Storytelling does not offer to enrich domain models by quality properties like performance or reliability. (P2) Next, there is no solution available that transforms the annotated model into runtime quality analysis tests. (P3) In association with P1, there has not been a solution to report the analysis results on the domain level in the context of a Domain Stories.

In the scope of this work, we have created an annotation-based modeling concept that extends Domain Storytelling by performance and reliability properties and report the analysis results to domain experts. Our modeling approach relates to annotation-based concepts from UML and MARTE as well as ATAM for finding a uniform template to describe different runtime quality analysis tests. We implemented this modeling concept into an existing Domain Story Modeler to create a prototype as a solution for P1 and P3. For this purpose, we have conducted four interviews with domain experts from two distinct business domains (taxing and insurance) to elicit requirements and find issues with current approaches towards solving P1, P2, and P3. We have gathered evidence that current solutions are similar to waterfall models in terms of communication and that domain experts lack the ability to efficiently express their needs on a domain level to software engineers. We summarized our findings and prepared twelve user stories which build up our prototype. After implementation, we have used one sample Domain Story from literature and field data from expert interviews to demonstrate that the transformation of the annotated domain models work using ChaosToolkit for resilience testing and JMeter for load testing.

In the end, we evaluated our prototype in a qualitative study to figure out if our prototype is a solution to P1 and P3. Based on our findings, we concluded that our modeling concept greatly assists domain experts in their processes to enrich domain models with quality properties that are critical to their domain and make the analysis results available in an understandable manner. We have demonstrated that our modeling concept is capable of solving P2 in the future, thus, effectively allowing domain experts and software engineers to make their processes more efficient.

Kurzfassung

Laufzeitqualitätsanalysen, wie zum Beispiel Resilienz- und Lasttests unterstützen Entwickler bei der Ermittlung von Abweichungen von Qualitätsanforderungen in geschäftskritischen Anwendungen. Daher müssen Fachexperten sowie Entwickler in der Lage sein, gemeinsam die Vision eines Domänenmodells voranzutreiben, welches die gewünschten Qualitätseigenschaften aufweist. Domain-driven Design ermöglicht es den Beteiligten, Domänenmodelle auf prägnante Weise unter Verwendung einer Ubiquitous Language für die Kommunikation zu erstellen. Modellierungssprachen wie UML und MARTE sind für diesen Zweck oft zu technisch. Im Gegensatz dazu fügt sich Domain Storytelling auf natürliche Weise in die Methodik von Domain-driven Design ein, indem es eine piktografische Modellierung sowie die Ubiquitous Language verwendet, um die Domäne in Domain Stories zu gestalten. Es ergeben sich jedoch drei grundlegende Probleme. (P1) Im Moment bietet Domain Storytelling nicht die Möglichkeit, Domänenmodelle mit Qualitätseigenschaften wie Performance oder Reliability anzureichern. (P2) Weiterhin gibt es keine Lösung, die das annotierte Modell in Qualitätstests zur Laufzeit umwandelt. (P3) In Verbindung mit P1 gab es bisher keine Lösung, um die Analyseergebnisse auf der Domänenebene im Kontext von Domain Stories darzustellen.

Im Rahmen dieser Arbeit, haben wir ein Annotations-basiertes Modellierungskonzept entwickelt, das Domain Storytelling um Performance- und Reliabilityeigenschaften erweitert und die Analyseergebnisse an Domänenexperten liefert. Unser Modellierungsansatz bezieht sich dabei auf annotationsbasierte Konzepte aus UML und MARTE sowie ATAM, um eine einheitliche Vorlage zur Beschreibung verschiedener Laufzeitqualitätsanalysen zu finden. Wir haben dieses Modellierungskonzept in einen bestehenden Domain Story Modeler implementiert, um einen Prototypen als Lösung für P1 und P3 zu erstellen. Zu diesem Zweck haben wir vier Interviews mit Domänenexperten aus zwei verschiedenen Geschäftsbereichen (Lohnabrechnungen und Versicherungen) geführt, um Anforderungen zu ermitteln und Probleme mit aktuellen Lösungsansätzen für P1, P2 und P3 zu finden. Wir haben Beweise dafür gesammelt, dass aktuelle Lösungen in Bezug auf die Kommunikation zwischen den Interessensgruppen, Wasserfallmodellen ähneln und dass Fachexperten nicht in der Lage sind, ihre Bedürfnisse auf Fachgebietsebene gegenüber Softwareingenieuren effizient auszudrücken. Wir haben unsere Ergebnisse zusammengefasst und zwölf User Stories erstellt, die unseren Prototyp bilden. Nach der Implementierung haben wir eine Beispiel-Domain-Story aus der Literatur und Felddaten aus Experteninterviews verwendet, um zu demonstrieren, dass die Transformation der annotierten Domänenmodelle mit Hilfe von ChaosToolkit für Resilienztests und JMeter für Lasttests funktioniert.

Schließlich haben wir unseren Prototyp in einer qualitativen Studie evaluiert, um herauszufinden, ob unser Prototyp eine Lösung für P1 und P3 darstellt. Auf der Grundlage unserer Ergebnisse kamen wir zu dem Schluss, dass unser Modellierungskonzept Domänenexperten bei ihren Prozessen zur Anreicherung von Domänenmodellen mit Qualitätseigenschaften, die für ihre Domäne entscheidend sind, erheblich unterstützt und die Analyseergebnisse auf verständliche Weise zur Verfügung stellt. Wir haben gezeigt, dass unser Modellierungskonzept in der Lage ist, P2 in der Zukunft zu lösen und somit Domänenexperten und Softwareingenieuren zu ermöglichen, ihre Prozesse effizienter zu gestalten.

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Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface.	20
APM	Application Performance Monitoring.	1
ATAM	Architecture Trade-off and Analysis Method.	xiii
BPMN	Business Process Model Notation.	10
CLI	Command Line Interface.	20
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets.	73
CSV	Comma-separated Values.	51
DDD	Domain-driven Design.	1
DSL	Domain-specific Language.	25
DST	Domain Storytelling.	2
EBNF	Extended Backus-Naur Form.	51
FMEA	Failure Modes and Effects Analysis.	20
FTA	Fault Tree Analysis.	20
GUI	Graphical User Interface.	20
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language.	15
HTTP	Hypertext Transport Protocol.	7
IDE	Integrated Development Environment.	72
JSON	Javascript Object Notation.	21
MARTE	Modeling and Analysis of Real-Time and Embedded systems.	2
MDA	Model-driven Architecture.	25
MDSD	Model-driven Software Development.	25
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration.	92
NPM	Node Package Manager.	14
OOP	Object-oriented Programming.	13
QA	Quality Assurance.	18
REST	Representational State Transfer.	20

RQA Runtime Quality Analysis. 26
SLA Service Level Agreement. 32
SLO Service Level Objective. 54
SOAP Simple Object Access Protocol. 20
SUT System Under Test. 18
UI User Interface. ix
UML Unified Modeling Language. ix
VM Virtual Machine. 88
VMI Virtual Machine Image. 88
YAML Yet Another Markup Language. 21

1 Introduction

Business-critical applications must handle millions of user requests to provide a good customer experience and stay competitive. The ongoing digitization of user services leads to high expectations about the application's quality properties like performance and reliability. Domain experts are familiar with the problem domain and have profound knowledge of the user's expectations and needs. Domain experts closely collaborate with technical experts (software engineers) to elaborate quality requirements a software application must fulfill to meet the user's expectations. However, the users' expectations grow constantly as other competitors enter the market with faster and better products. Therefore, organizations must refine their quality requirements and improve their applications to stay competitive. Otherwise, a decreasing software quality endangers the organization's revenue stream and customer development [HHMO17]. Many studies have identified that performance-related issues result in high revenue losses. For instance, Amazon forfeits approximately 1% of revenue when the latency deviates by only 100 ms [Lid08]. To improve an application's performance, software engineers aim to design distributed applications that share the work to allow a higher throughput and faster responses. Another positive result of distributed systems is that they are less prone to failure. For instance, an application that runs on a single node will become unavailable if that one node fails. A distributed application can redirect incoming requests to another node if one or more nodes fail. Distributed application patterns such as microservices promise many advantages about better resilience and higher performance. However studies have shown that they require extensive effort and expertise to achieve a high degree of quality [BFWZ19]. These factors suggest that organizations must observe their applications throughout the entire software life cycle and ensure to meet their desired quality requirements. Accordingly, there is a growing need for monitoring quality characteristics and verifying application behavior during runtime. Application Performance Monitoring (APM) is a means to assist developers and stakeholders in continuously monitoring a system's runtime behavior and identifying deviations in quality characteristics [HHMO17]. To further strengthen their knowledge about the system's behavior, businesses combine APM with load testing and resilience testing strategies [FHW+22].

However, creating a monitoring solution or technical tests from business metrics requires matured knowledge of the business domain and understanding of how they translate to technical metrics such as response times or error rates. Although domain experts know the problem space, they lack the skill and knowledge to voice their concerns in a technical context. In contrast, technical experts (software engineers) have matured knowledge of the solution space and the application's technical characteristics. However, technical experts do not know how the application's software quality influences the business goals. Thus, there is a large gap between domain and technical experts that promotes miscommunication and overly extensive communication between the parties. Figure 1.1 emphasizes the communication among the stakeholders. As domain experts try to communicate a business-related problem, technical experts cannot get all information to create a technical solution to the problem. Domain-driven Design (DDD) closes this gap by empowering domain experts and technical experts to explore the domain and create concise domain models from a common point

Figure 1.1: Extensive information exchange between stakeholders to communicate concerns

of view using the Ubiquitous Language. To this day, technical experts use modeling languages such as UML and Modeling and Analysis of Real-Time and Embedded systems (MARTE) to communicate different viewpoints of a software application to other stakeholders. However, these modeling approaches often require learning and understanding complex notations. Moreover, they include many technical details that are not relevant to understanding the domain model nor do domain experts know the technical information in a domain context [Eva04]. In contrast, Domain Storytelling (DST) naturally fits into the DDD methodology by using pictographic storytelling and Ubiquitous Language to shape the domain collaboratively.

At this point, three fundamental issues arise. (P1) Although DST enables stakeholders to explore and create concise domain models, it does not provide any means to enrich the model with quality properties in a way UML or MARTE do. At the moment, domain experts have to use annotations in the form of sticky notes that contain the information in natural language. This requires that domain experts are capable of phrasing their concerns precisely. However, at the very least, domain experts give informal and incomplete information about what they expect from the application's quality properties. (P2) Even if a domain model includes quality properties, there is no solution available to transform the annotated model into runtime quality analysis tests such as resilience and load tests. This would require more specific details like the type of workload, or experiment setting that domain experts typically can not provide. Therefore, technical experts would have to consult domain experts for more information to create a runtime quality analysis test. (P3) Lastly, the results from runtime quality analysis tests are often visualized in complex dashboards that show technical data for the most time. However, domain experts have difficulties in making decisions from data-driven analysis results without concise explanation on how the data relates to their business goals. Therefore, there is no option to report the results from runtime quality analysis tests to the domain model in the context of a Domain Story.

In the context of this work, we have created an annotation-based modeling concept that enables domain experts to describe performance and reliability-related properties on their domain model in the context of Domain Storytelling (DST). Our approach relates to the annotation-based concepts of UML and MARTE but without using a technical notation. We intended to keep the fundamental concept of DST or Domain Stories. In fact we provide additional modeling interfaces that describe performance and reliability-related properties in natural language. As a precondition of this work,

we decided to use the Domain Story Modeler by the WPS organization ¹ as a basis for a first prototype towards solving P1 and P3. It is easier to extend an existing tool as it already implements important features for modeling Domain Stories, e.g., enforce connectivity rules and ensure the completeness of a story. In the beginning, we have conducted expert interviews to achieve two goals. First, we wanted to find out how domain experts currently solve the problem stated in P1, P2, and P3. Second, we were interested in the domain expert's requirements for a first prototype that solves P1 and P3. Therefore, we have prepared a question catalogue in a semi-structured manner. We have selected the domain experts as interview participants from two distinct business domains and companies (taxing and insurance). In total, we have conducted four one-on-one interviews with two domain experts from each domain. We have identified that domain experts face similar issues as illustrated in Figure 1.1, which require multiple iterations to elicit enough information for creating runtime quality analysis tests. We found evidence that their current processes have much in common with traditional waterfall processes that slow down communication and impede domain expert's ability expressing their concerns about quality properties. Afterwards, we summarized our findings and elaborated twelve user stories for a first prototype for our modeling concept. In addition, to the user stories, we have used the expert's feedback to create our modeling concept that describes how we store performance and reliability-related properties into a unified data model using the ATAM scenario description.

As a part of our concept P2, we have conceptually demonstrated how to transform the annotated domain model into a resilience and load tests by assuming the usage of tactical design patterns from DDD and the existence of an appropriate Domain Story. For this purpose, we have used one Domain Story from the work of Hofer and Schwentner [HS21] to demonstrate that the transformation of the annotated domain model works using ChaosToolkit for resilience testing and JMeter for load testing. In the end, we have conducted a qualitative evaluation with four domain experts from the insurance and taxing domain. During the evaluation they had to solve four different tasks using established Domain Stories by Hofer and Schwentner [HS21]. We intended to figure out whether our modeling concept successfully solves P1 and P3 and improve the domain expert's current processes. For a better evaluation, we have phrased five research questions and created a questionnaire that assisted us in analyzing our observations. In the end, we have gathered evidence that our concept works by reducing the effort of eliciting information for creating runtime quality analysis tests. Moreover, given the expert's feedback we conclude that we have successfully solved P1 and P3, although, there exist still points for improvement with regard to user experience and usability. In addition, we have prepared further user stories that may be implemented in the future to extend our concept. Lastly, we have thoroughly discussed our findings and made a final statement.

This work has been conducted as a part of the research project dqualizer². Dqualizer aims to close the gap between domain experts and technical experts (e.g., software engineers) by generating load and resilience tests from a business perspective and producing understandable runtime-critical insights into a system's quality characteristics. Dqualizer utilizes domain knowledge elicited with practices that fit into the DDD methodology, i.e., DST and Event Storming [Bra13]. Two industry partners from different business domains participate in dqualizer and provide valuable material to this work. In parallel to this work, the industry partners participate in a series of workshops conducted by researchers of dqualizer. We have used the results of these workshops to further

¹<https://www.wps.de/>

²<https://dqualizer.github.io/>

develop our concept and refine our prototype. Further, we have selected employees from these industry partners for conducting our interviews and expert evaluation to support our claims with field data. In the context of dqualizer, the results of this thesis build the first unit of work by providing a modeling concept that extends DST. Therefore, this work solves problems P1, and P2. Further, our work demonstrates a possible solution for P2.

Summary of Method and Findings

In the following we will summarize the research method and findings of this work.

Method

- We have prepared semi-structured interviews as a part of our requirements elicitation process. In total, we have conducted four one-on-one interviews with two experts from the insurance domain and two experts from the taxing domain. Each interview took approximately 45 minutes to one hour.
- From the findings, we have determined a set of product requirements for the development of a prototype. Further, we have found evidence on the domain expert's current solutions to P1, P2, and P3 that assisted us in understanding their issues. The product requirements were transformed into twelve user stories which we split into smaller, implementable tasks during the prototype development.
- We have created our modeling concept using integral parts of other modeling languages for annotating domain models. Further, we use the scenario description from ATAM as an orientation to create a uniform data model to describe runtime quality analysis tests.
- We have conceptually demonstrated that the transformation of an annotated domain model using our modeling concept works. For this purpose, we have used one Domain Story from Hofer and Schwentner [HS21] demonstrating the transformation. Further, we have assumed that dqualizer implements the necessary interfaces and services to allow a concise transformation using determined mapping rules based on tactical design patterns from DDD. Further, we assumed that dqualizer uses ChaosToolkit and JMeter for resilience and load testing.
- We evaluated our prototype by conducting four one-on-one expert interviews. In these interviews, the experts used our prototype to solve four tasks dedicated to our concept. Prior, we have phrased five research questions in our evaluation plan that helped us to analyze the findings of the interviews as well as to decide whether our concept solves P1 and P3. Afterward, the experts filled out a questionnaire that provided us with detailed information about the expert's impressions of our prototype and concept.

Findings

- Based on our findings, we have identified twelve user stories as a result of our elicitation interviews. Furthermore, we have identified points of improvement in two business domains where our modeling concept provides a valuable improvement.
- We have created an annotation-based modeling concept for modeling non-functional requirements on the domain level which we have successfully implemented in a prototype using an existing domain story modeler provided by the WPS organization.
- We have shown that our modeling concept works on a conceptual level with regard to the equalizer ecosystem by demonstrating an end-to-end workflow.
- During the evaluation, the experts have stated that our prototype improves their processes by allowing domain experts to add quality properties to domain models without extensive assistance of technical experts. Furthermore, they have stated that our concept is easy to understand even without profound technical expertise. Furthermore, we observed that the experts were able to provide a lot of information on the domain level if there is documentation available that assists them in the process.
- In assistance of our prototype, we have demonstrated that we have found a solution to the initially phrased problem P1. Further, we have introduced a potential solution to problem P2 by demonstrating a conceptual transformation of an annotated domain model into technical tests.
- As a part of our elicitation and evaluation, we have gathered more user stories and feedback for further extending the prototype and improving its usability and user experience.
- We have concluded that the domain story modeler by WPS is probably not suitable for further iterations as it contains a lot of technical limitations.

We have gathered supplementary materials related to our elicitation process, prototype development, and expert evaluation and provided them under the following link: [10.5281/zenodo.7319806](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7319806)

Thesis Structure

This thesis is structured as follows.

Chapter 2 – Foundations and Related Work: This chapter introduces concepts and terminologies with regard to Domain-driven Design, resilience and load testing. Also we introduce the Domain Story Modeler for the development of our prototype. Lastly, we will elaborate existing scientific works related to modeling quality requirements in Domain-driven Design.

Chapter 3 – User Requirements Elicitation: This chapter explains our interview design including the participant selection process, question catalogue and how we structured the interviews. In the end, we summarize and discuss our findings from the interviews.

Chapter 4 – Annotation-based Concept to Extend Domain Storytelling: In this chapter, we elaborate our main contribution, i.e., the modeling concept for annotating domain models in the scope of Domain Stories to create runtime quality analysis tests.

Chapter 5 – Prototype Development: This chapter explains the integration of our modeling concept in to the Domain Story Modeler based on the requirements we elicited in Chapter 3.

Chapter 6 – Evaluation: In this chapter, we evaluate our prototype in the context of a qualitative expert study by using established domain models from literature and dedicated tasks that the experts had to solve in assistance of our prototype.

Chapter 7 – Conclusion Lastly, we conclude our work by summarizing the content of this work and discuss the advantages and disadvantages as well as the threats to validity. In the end, we discuss future work packages that extend this work.

2 Foundations and Related Work

This chapter explains the fundamental concepts and terminology necessary to understand the content of this work. In addition, we introduce the Domain Story Modeler and its architecture. Lastly, we discuss our research methodology to identify relevant and related scientific works. Thus, this chapter is structured as follows. Section 2.1 explains foundational concepts related to Domain-driven Design, software quality, and runtime quality analysis. Section 2.2 discusses the related works.

2.1 Foundations

This section explains the fundamental concepts and terminology related to DDD, software quality, quality scenarios, and runtime quality analysis. This section is structured as follows. Section 2.1.1 thoroughly explains essential concepts and practices of Domain-driven Design. Section 2.1.2 introduces the Domain Story Modeler that is the basis for the prototype of our modeling concept. Section 2.1.3 briefly discusses software quality models and requirements. Section 2.1.4 describes quality attribute scenarios. Section 2.1.5 explains the fundamentals of runtime quality analysis and core principles of Application Performance Monitoring.

2.1.1 Domain-driven Design

Models and diagrams are a fundamental medium in the communication between stakeholders for many years. The UML has improved the quality of these models by providing a coherent set of elements and relationships to describe structure, behavior, and distribution of software. According to Kazman et al. [KKB+98], (software), architecture diagrams aim to improve the communication between stakeholders by creating and maintaining distinct models of the software that reflect a particular view.

A *view* focuses on one representation of the software system that shows a specific set of elements and the relationship among them [KKB+98].

Common examples of views are component or class diagrams that focus on the structural properties of a software application. These model types include many technical characteristics or follow a complex notation such as UML. Figure 2.1 illustrates a deployment diagram showing two services, namely *Cargo* and *Voyage* that run on distinct web servers and a database connected to the *Cargo* service. Both services communicate by Hypertext Transport Protocol (HTTP). Software engineers have become accustomed to UML models for communication over the years as it is a widely accepted notation. As software engineers and domain experts tend to describe the software application from different perspectives, UML and the like primarily assist software engineers but make it difficult for

Figure 2.1: UML deployment diagram for booking *Cargos* onto a *Voyage* of a ship [Eva04]

Figure 2.2: Distilled domain model of *Cargo* and *Voyage* [Eva04]

domain experts to express their concerns from a business perspective. Moreover, domain experts have a limited understanding of technical concepts and terminology, which makes it even more difficult to reason about the same model.

Vernon [Ver17] further emphasizes that software engineers inevitably think of what the software does rather than thinking of the business rules that the software should follow. In contrast, domain experts are not interested in technical details when considering business goals. Domain-driven Design (DDD) is a methodology that aims to solve this issue by removing technical details from models and focuses on the problem domain.

A *domain* refers to the highest level of a business and broadly describes what a company does [Ver17]. The domain is one of the most important objects of interest in DDD.

Figure 2.2 shows a simplified example of a distilled model for the *Cargo-Voyage* example. The model removes technical details and only shows the objects and their relationship. Evans [Eva04] defines a *domain model* as follows.

A *domain model* is a model that comprises concepts, terms, and relationships that reflect insights of the domain [Eva04].

Further, Evans [Eva04] highlights that at its core DDD is about creating *knowledge-rich* models that reflect the behavior of domain objects and the enforced business rules of the observed domain. However, DDD does not eliminate the perspective view of stakeholders but creates a common understanding of the problem domain using a concise domain model and a unambiguous language.

Figure 2.3: Ubiquitous Language for the *Cargo* domain model

At last, stakeholders must communicate the terms, concepts, and relationships reflected in the domain model. However, the difference in their perception of the domain model creates a gap between domain and technical experts. Therefore, it is necessary to create and use a common language that both parties understand.

The *Ubiquitous Language* describes a collection of terms and their semantics for a particular domain. The goal is to use this language by everyone in the project to decrease the linguistic separation between stakeholders by allowing unambiguous communication [Ver17].

Figure 2.3 shows a simplified example of a Ubiquitous Language for the *Cargo* domain model. The Ubiquitous Language must at least describe the domain objects and how they relate to each other. For simplicity reasons, we only illustrate a possible description for Voyage and Cargo example. However, the Ubiquitous Language is not limited by any means. As well as the domain model, the Ubiquitous Language only includes information most important to the model.

In the beginning, the Ubiquitous Language may look scarce as the domain model lacks information to make it expressive. Consistent usage of the Ubiquitous Language surfaces weaknesses in the domain model. However this requires that stakeholders extend the language by the observed concepts and business rules that were not present in the model from the beginning [Ver17]. Over time, the domain model changes as new findings emerge due to the increasing understanding of the model. Thus, the stakeholders must extend the Ubiquitous Language with information continuously. Otherwise, the terminology becomes obsolete leading to communication problems.

Collaborative Modeling

Evans [Eva04] argues that, to make the Ubiquitous Language and DDD work, it is necessary that stakeholders work collaboratively towards a mutual domain model that is maintained throughout the life cycle of the system. In general, there are many options for creating a domain model. For

Figure 2.4: Arthouse cinema example by Hofer and Schwentner [HS21]

instance, the example shown by Evans [Eva04] in Figure 2.2 uses a basic notation of lines and boxes that everyone can understand. However, this kind of notation makes it difficult to read and understand the model. Moreover, it does not allow extensive expressions in the relationship between individual objects. Therefore, many practitioners such as Plöd [Plö19b] and [Ver17] suggest to use Domain Storytelling (DST) to create, update, and maintain domain models.

DST is a collaborative modeling technique that emphasizes on transforming domain knowledge into software by telling and visualizing stories about the problem domain [HS21]. Domain experts tell their stories to other stakeholders with different background within the scope of a workshop where a moderator guides the storytelling, asks questions, and challenges the participants to identify plot holes [HS21]. Evans [Eva04] explains that DST should not use formal model languages such as Business Process Model Notation (BPMN) or UML, to tell domain stories as they distract participants from their core activity, i.e., understanding the domain model. Therefore, stakeholders lose their focus on domain objects and events. Instead they try to understand the notation of a formal modeling language.

Hofer and Schwentner [HS21] suggest using a simple pictographic language for DST to avoid complex notations or interactions inherent to a formal modelling language. This allows a simple demonstration of people, their activities, and business processes [HS21]. DST knows three elements for modeling a story, i.e., *actors*, *work objects*, and *activities* [Plö19a]. *Actors* are the protagonists of a story and can be persons, groups, or software systems. Actors always play an active role in a domain story and have a label that describe their role in a domain story. In their story, actors create, use, or exchange objects such as documents, things, digital objects and the like. These are the *work objects*. *Actors* and *work objects* are connected by arrows called *activities*.

Hofer and Schwentner [HS21] remark that *activities* are always verbs in the domain language, whereas *actors* and *work objects* are nouns. Figure 2.4 shows a domain story based on the *metropolis arthouse cinema* domain by Hofer and Schwentner [HS21]. In this example, the customer and the cashier are *actors*. The elements ticket, movie, theater, and room are *work objects*. The arrows labeled with *shows*, *returns*, *opens*, and *checks* are the *activities*. Thus, we can read the domain story as follows.

The customer shows the movie ticket to the cashier. Then the cashier checks the movie on the ticket. Afterward, the cashier checks the room on the ticket. Then, if everything seems correct, the cashier returns the ticket to the customer and opens the theater. In general, the modeling of a domain story depends on the stakeholder's interpretation and understanding of the domain which may lead to a different domain model than the one we have shown in Figure 2.4.

Another collaborative modeling technique is *Event Storming* [Bra13]. During Event Storming workshops, the participants *brainstorm* events that occur in the observed domain. They arrange the events on a timeline to create a time-dependent series of events [HS21]. Brandolini [Bra13] proposed Event Storming in the context of DDD. Although there are similarities between Event Storming and DST, they differ in their process. During Event Storming, participants focus on domain events that occur in the domain and draft the domain's *big picture* whereas, in DST, the participants work out a particular scenario focusing on the *small picture* [HS21]. Despite their similarities in many situations, it makes sense to use Event Storming over DST. For instance, Hofer and Schwentner [HS21] explains that they use Event Storming when there is no structured vision of the domain. In such cases, it is helpful to *brainstorm* the big picture instead of working out scenarios that consist of small interactions.

Strategic Design Patterns

Strategic design is a collection of design decisions and patterns that stakeholders apply to large parts of the system to focus on the big picture [Eva04]. Plöd [Plö19a] encourages to think of strategic design as a top-down approach to reduce the complexity of a domain by breaking it down into smaller subdomains. A key principle of the strategic design in DDD is the notion of *subdomains* and *bounded contexts*.

A *subdomain* is a domain that lives within another domain, having its own domain model and thus its own *Ubiquitous Language* [Ver17].

Evans [Eva04] clarifies that a domain, contains at least but more often multiple distinct domain models. It is common for stakeholders that their initial domain exploration results in one big domain model, referenced as *big ball of mud* [Eva04], [Ver17]. Subdomains assist stakeholders in disentangling the *big ball of mud* and create multiple smaller domains, the subdomains. At this point, the notion of subdomains and bounded contexts are often used interchangeably because they are closely related to each other.

A *bounded context* isolates one domain model within a firmly defined scope where a particular set of rules and terminology applies [Eva04].

In contrast, Vernon [Ver17] explains *bounded contexts* as semantic, contextual borders that separate components and (domain) models from other parts of the software where each model has only one meaning and one purpose. Another noteworthy mention by Plöd [Plö19a] states that each *bounded context* comes with its *Ubiquitous Language* since a ubiquitous language is bound to one particular domain model. The distinction between a subdomain and a bounded becomes obvious in Figure 2.6. It shows the decomposition from a top-level domain called *Insurance* that is decomposed into two smaller subdomains called *Sales* and *Customers*. As Evans [Eva04] explains, a subdomain resides in the problem space to reduce the size of the domain. In the last step, a subdomain is decomposed into one or more bounded contexts. According to its definition, the bounded context isolates one

Figure 2.5: Example of two bounded contexts

Figure 2.6: Splitting a domain into subdomains and bounded contexts

domain model with all its rules and terminology. Thus, a bounded context resides in the solution space. A subdomain consists of at least one bounded context. However, a subdomain may also have multiple bounded contexts in one subdomain. Although, Evans [Eva04] and Vernon [Ver17] motivate that a bounded context and a subdomain should be connected by a 1 : 1 relationship. That means, one bounded context belongs to one subdomain.

However, it is not always possible to separate two bounded contexts from each other. Figure 2.5 shows an example of two bounded contexts where each context holds its domain model. If there is no clear separation between two domain models, two bounded contexts will connect using *Context Maps*. A *Context Map* describes a structured approach to transition from one bounded context to another. Prominent examples include *Shared Kernel*, and *Separate Ways* [Ver17]. However, as context mapping is not an integral part of our work, we do not discuss it in detail.

Tactical Design Patterns

The tactical design is a bottom-up analysis that concentrates on patterns that describe the implementation of domain models [Plö19a]. For this purpose, it is not relevant if the domain model was created using DST as in Figure 2.4 or as a line and boxes diagram as in Figure 2.2. However, it is relevant that the domain model is well-defined and agreed to by everyone. Though it is best practice to use DST. Hofer and Schwentner [HS21] explain tactical patterns from the point of view of a domain story for implementing a domain model. We only consider the concepts of *entities* and *value objects* as other tactical design patterns are not relevant to our work. Vernon [Ver17] explains *entities* and *value objects* as follows.

An *Entity* is an individual thing that has an unambiguous identity and changes its content through life cycles.

Value objects are objects holding a value but do not have an identity. Additionally, *value objects* describe entities in more detail by quantifying them.

Entities and value objects are the two fundamental building blocks of the tactical design. Moreover, they are essential for building *aggregates* that are the core objects of a bounded context. However, we do not discuss the aggregate pattern since it is not relevant to this work. For now, it is enough to know that multiple entities or a combination of entities and value objects constitute to build aggregates. The aggregate is the object that changes over time in response to domain events.

Implementing a domain model requires to identify the entities and value objects. In DDD, it is best practice to use domain stories creating a domain model. Therefore, it is important to know how actors, activities, and work objects are related to the tactical design patterns entity and value object. As a rule of thumb, Hofer and Schwentner [HS21] explain that work objects are potential candidates for entities and value objects. At times, actors may also be implemented as entities. Deciding whether a work object is an entity or a value object mostly depends on personal preference and design choices. In contrast, activities are suitable to become operations to define the behavior of an entity.

Listing 2.1 shows an abbreviated implementation of the domain story in Figure 2.4 using Java. We observe that the entities relate to the concept of classes in Object-oriented Programming (OOP) languages which are templates for objects that have behavior and properties. The value objects become the class variables as shown in the *Ticket* class having *room* as its variable. The activity *show* in the domain story relates to a method that describes a behavior of the *Ticket*'s class object.

However, Vernon [Ver17] and Evans [Eva04] emphasize that the exact implementation of the domain model may differ significantly as there are many options to define entities and value objects. Further, it is often personal preference how to implement these tactical design patterns and also depends on the context.

Listing 2.1 Implementing the domain story in Figure 2.4

```
/*Actor or work object can be candidates for Entities */
public class Ticket {

    private String room;

    /* Activities can be candidats for methods */
    public boolean show(){ ... };

}

/* Actor or work object can be candidates for Entities */
public class Movie {

    /* Work objects can be candidates for value objects */
    private String room;

}
```

2.1.2 Domain Story Modeler by WPS

We have decided to use the Domain Story Modeler by the WPS¹ organization as a basis for our prototype. The main advantage of using an already existing tool is that we can focus entirely on implementing our approach rather than creating an entire tool from scratch. The following sections point out the main features of the tool and how it has been built.

Features

The Domain Story Modeler was licensed under GPLv3.0² and bpmn.io licence³ as it uses the bpmn-js Node Package Manager (NPM) library. The tool implements the following three core features.

- create and visualize domain stories
- export domain stories using a domain story file format (.dst)
- import domain stories from .dst files

Figure 2.7 shows a snippet of an existing domain story that we imported into the Domain Story Modeler. The imported domain story has been attached in Appendix B.2. The panel on the left shows a set of icons separated into two categories, i.e., actors and work objects. The icons can be moved onto the canvas to model domain stories. In the top right corner, the user may export or

¹<https://www.wps.de/>

²<https://www.gnu.org/licenses/>

³<https://bpmn.io/license/>

Beispiel 4 - Ticketverkauf Happy Path (digital)

Annahmen: Happy Path; Kinobesucher hat kein Abo

Figure 2.7: Snippet from a domain story that has been imported into the Domain Story Modeler

import domain stories from a dst file. Upon clicking on an element on the canvas, e.g., as shown on the *Preis* element, a context menu shows up additional configuration elements, e.g., changing the color, removing elements from the domain story, or adding elements.

Other features of the Domain Story Modeler include customization of icons and a replay feature that tells the domain story backward. However, these features are not necessary or relevant to our approach. Therefore, we do not consider them nor explain them in any detail.

Architecture and Implementation

The Domain Story Modeler is a web-based application built with Javascript without using any frameworks. However, the modeler uses several libraries to implement the concise modeling of domain story elements. The core NPM library is *bpmn.js* that implements BPMN. As it allows the customizability of modeling elements, the Domain Story Modeler extends and customizes the core features of *bpmn.js* to render and compute domain stories according to the rules of the Domain Storytelling practice.

As the application runs with basic Javascript, there are no framework related patterns. The application imports an index file that includes the Hypertext Markup Language (HTML) elements and the Javascript files that implement the business logic. The business logic separates in different features. Figure 2.8 shows the building blocks of the Domain Story Modeler. Note that each block in Figure 2.8 references a package in the Domain Story Modeler application. To extend the *bpmn.js* components, the developers followed OOP to overwrite behavior of BPMN elements.

As the application requires a few dependencies, the command *npm install* must be executed to install the dependencies. Otherwise the application will not work. Then, the Domain Story Modeler can be executed locally by running *npm run dev* in the application's directory.

Figure 2.8: Folder structure of the Domain Story Modeler application

In the scope of this work, we will extend the Domain Story Modeler application by our modeling concept. However, we will not make fundamental changes to existing features of the Domain Story Modeler. Moreover, we will add additional features that allow to model and create expressive technical tests and specifications. Furthermore, we will provide an interface to forward the modeled elements to dqualizer's backend components.

2.1.3 Software Quality

This section explains selected topics from software quality and elaborates non-functional requirements according to a software quality model. Throughout the years, quality models have been used as a reference for evaluating the qualitative properties of software applications. A quality model is a set of quality characteristics and the relationships between them to assess and describe the quality characteristics of a product [BNJ01]. ISO/IEC 25010 is a well-known and frequently cited quality standard [ISO]. Figure 2.9 shows a breakdown of software product quality as defined by ISO/IEC 25010.

ISO/IEC 25010 defines characteristics as stakeholder needs which cover different concerns regards software product quality [ISO]. However, quality characteristics may be prioritized by different criteria depending on the stakeholder's concerns and how they view the product as a whole from a business perspective. The fundamental business needs and stakeholder concerns drive the focus on quality characteristics. For instance, domain experts and managers typically focus on observable characteristics such as reliability and security, as these are also observable by the end users. Vice versa, technical stakeholders, aim to improve the compatibility and maintainability of a software product as they typically need to work with the product on a technological level.

In the context of this work, the observed quality requirements majorly focus on the runtime behavior of an observed system. Thus, this work primarily deals with the characteristics and sub characteristics of performance and reliability as highlighted in Figure 2.9.

Figure 2.9: Breakdown of ISO 25010 [ISO]

Figure 2.10: Visualization of a scenario according to Kazman et al. [KKB+98]

2.1.4 Quality Scenarios

According to Glinz [Gli00], a scenario is an ordered sequence of steps where two or more actors participate in these steps. An example for scenarios are use case diagrams as described in the UML notation, where one or more actors communicate with a system through a set of ordered interactions. In contrast, Kazman et al. [KKB+98] describe a scenario in more detail by stating that a (quality attribute) scenario constitutes of a sequence of interactions that include a *stimulus*, the *source of the stimulus*, an *artifact*, the *environment*, the system's *response*, and a *response measure*. Although, Kazman et al. [KKB+98] clearly use the term scenario in the context of quality attributes, the general meaning of scenarios remains the same. Another similar description has been given by Hofer and Schwentner [HS21] who define a scenario as stories about people and their activities in a fixed context by using a sequence of activities and events.

Although each of these definitions have their purpose and semantically reference the same concept, we go by the definition of Kazman et al. [KKB+98] since our work concerns about quality attributes as well. Figure 2.10 shows a scenario description according to Kazman et al. [KKB+98].

Scenarios start with a *source* from which the *stimulus* originates. The *source* may be an end user, a system, or a subsystem. The *stimulus* can be anything such as HTTP requests, crashes, or a server that does not respond. The *artifact* is the object that will be affected by *stimulus*. In case of an

HTTP request, the *artifact* may be the receiving service provider. The *environment* describes the circumstances in which the *artifact* operates. For example, the *environment* describes that the system works under normal conditions and does not report any errors. The condition of the system can be further described by using workloads if necessary, i.e., a normal condition means the system receives 4000 requests per minute. The *response* is the actual measured response by the system, e.g., measured response or recovery times. Lastly, the *response measure* describes a hypothesis which we assume to hold in the context of the scenario.

The scenario described in Figure 2.10 is fundamental for the ATAM [KKB+98, p. 429] to identify trade-offs in a system's architecture. ATAM assesses a given architecture by considering trade-offs according to selected quality attributes and identifies potential risks in making architectural choices [KKB+98]. In their works, Kesim et al. [KHFH20] and Frank et al. [FHW+22] have used this scenario template in other contexts for describing resilience and load test scenarios. Both works have demonstrated that the scenario template by Kazman et al. [KKB+98] is suitable to describe an arbitrary scenario in a common language that is understandable by domain experts and software engineers. Furthermore, it creates a uniform template for different types of scenarios by using the template's keywords, *stimulus*, *artifact*, *environment*, and *response measure*.

2.1.5 Application Performance Management

Software quality directly influences a business's performance in the market. Moreover, quality issues, e.g., decreasing performance, may lead to revenue losses and negative customer turnover rates [HHMO17]. Different studies involving large companies such as Amazon and Google gathered evidence that these companies lose high amounts of money if they do not meet their quality goals [Lin], [Lid08].

Businesses use performance management to observe an application's runtime behavior and track pre-defined metrics on different levels to engage when a metric drops below a certain threshold. More precisely, Application Performance Monitoring (APM) is a means to assist developers and stakeholders in continuously monitoring a system's runtime behavior and identifying deviations in quality characteristics [HHMO17].

APM involves different activities that may be executed concurrently and influence each other, namely (1) data collection, (2) data storage and processing, (3) data presentation, and (4) data interpretation and use [HHMO17]. Data collection focuses on collecting data from different sources and answering three questions. *Where* to get the data, *what* data is important for the problem, and *how* will the data be collected. After data collection, it is important to know how to store the data and where to store it. Next, the data must be presented in a meaningful way. However, managers and developers may require different scopes and level of detail for the observed data. For instance, managers or domain experts may be interested in a business point of view, unlike developers who are more interested in traces, server health, and similar technical metrics. Lastly, the data can be used for interpretation and to initiate other actions. For example, detecting a violation of thresholds may send out a message to the system's operators to inform them about an anomaly.

Figure 2.11 illustrates APM on an example workflow for monitoring a System Under Test (SUT). Quality Assurance (QA) declares and specifies a monitoring configuration file which includes information about *what* kind of data to monitor, *how long* to observe it, and *where* to get the data

Figure 2.11: Example monitoring of a system

from, i.e., which services provide the data of interest. A monitoring suite, e.g., Prometheus⁴ uses the configuration to run the monitoring on the SUT. Then, the observed monitoring data is aggregated by the monitoring suite and provided on a dashboard, e.g., Grafana⁵.

2.1.6 Load Testing

According to Beizer [Bei84], *load testing* is a process to gain information on a system's capability to fulfill its functional and non-functional properties under specific conditions to uncover functional or non-functional related problems. It emerged as an addition to functional testing approaches to ensure that systems meet their quality requirements by observing their behavior in a given environment. In general, load testing requires three steps, i.e., (1) load design, (2) execution, and (3) analysis. Load design is about deciding what kind of workload intensity the SUT experiences during the execution. *Workload intensity* defines the rate of requests the SUT receives during execution [JH15]. Another interpretation is to consider the workload intensity as the number of concurrent users that access the SUT. Jiang [JH15] differentiates between realistic load and fault-inducing load. Realistic load design leverages existing operational data, e.g., user profiles that access the SUT in a specific period, to generate a load that is similar to the observed data. The fault-inducing load may also consist of a realistic load but includes configurations that cause functional or non-functional related problems during the load execution.

The latter is often chosen for conducting so-called stress tests. During a stress test, the workload intensity is set to a rate higher than the observed operational profile (if available), thus, it is possible to observe how the SUT responds under more extreme conditions [ZED11]. The objective, in this case, is to uncover problems that only occur when the SUT has to perform under heavy environmental conditions or when the observer has little to no trust in non-functional properties of the SUT, such as scalability or robustness. If the workload profile also includes a fault load, the stress test becomes a resilience test (see Section 2.1.7).

⁴<https://prometheus.io/>

⁵<https://grafana.com/>

There exist many different load testing tools such as Gatling [Gat11], JMeter [The19a], or k6 [Gra] that achieve similar goals with varying levels of detail. As the specification and test plans of these tools vary significantly, we use the test plan of JMeter as a reference for this work as we already have a profound experience with JMeter. Furthermore, a thorough evaluation of all the available tools would be out of the scope of this work.

We use the official Apache JMeter documentation The Apache Software Foundation [The19b] as a reference for the following explanations of JMeter. JMeter is a Java-based testing tool created by the Apache foundation that allows the simulation of user workload as a means to load and performance test software applications. Vieira et al. [VWAM12] describe workloads as events that an application is exposed to, e.g., database queries or Application Programming Interface (API) calls. JMeter allows the creation of sophisticated load test plans through a Graphical User Interface (GUI) as well as a Command Line Interface (CLI).

A minimal test plan configuration comprises a *thread group* and one or more *samplers*. The *thread group* describes the number of concurrent requests (or users) that access the application during the test run. The *sampler* defines an actual request. For instance, JMeter offers an HTTP request sampler that allows the declaration of an HTTP request for Representational State Transfer (REST) web interfaces or other protocols such as Simple Object Access Protocol (SOAP). The thread group requires to define a *ramp up* period measured in seconds. JMeter uses this time interval as a measure to reach the maximum number of concurrent requests defined in the *thread group*. For example, if the *thread group* contains a total number of concurrent requests of 10, and the *ramp up* period is set to 100 seconds, then JMeter takes 100 seconds to get all 10 threads up and running. JMeter allows the creation of more complex scenarios, e.g., by combining *samplers* with *controllers*. During a test run, JMeter uses *controllers*, among others, to control the number of executions of a sampler. The *controller* object can be combined with *assertion elements* that verify a response to a sampler's request against a pre-determined object. We can use this kind of setup to check the response object of HTTP requests to a web application. In the scope of this work, we do not consider such complex test plan configurations.

2.1.7 Resilience Testing

Resilience describes an system's capability to recover from conditions that cause deviations from the system's normal state [VWAM12]. As such, resilience is a measurable metric that relates to other dependability metrics, e.g., reliability and fault tolerance. O'Regan [ORe17] describes a dependable system as system that operates in a safe and reliable manner without causing malicious side effects while being available. Testing resilience requires preparation and a well designed testing strategy. A common practice for resilience testing are fault-injections [HTI97] and chaos experiments [BBR+16]. Both strategies aim to test different dependability metrics, such as resilience but differ in methodology. In traditional fault-injection approaches, the injection engine injects the fault into the hardware or software layer to investigate a system's dependability measures in a test environment. Chaos engineering is about empirical exploration of weaknesses in a *random* manner by exposing the system to extreme conditions, e.g., service or database outages [BBR+16]. Although, there have been recent approaches that demonstrate a *controlled* approach to running chaos experiments in assistance of safety engineering methods such as Fault Tree Analysis (FTA) and Failure Modes and Effects Analysis (FMEA) by Kesim et al. [KHFH20]. In that sense, we use

MUST	
Object name	Description
version	Version of the current experiment file
title	Experiment title
description	Description of the experiment
method	Comprises of actions and probes to change the system state and verify the hypothesis
SHOULD	
Object name	Description
steady-state-hypothesis	Defining the expected working behavior of the application under test
rollbacks	Actions to reverse the actions of the method block

Table 2.1: Chaos experiment objects declared by ChaosToolkit

the term resilience test as a synonym for chaos experiments since a resilience test can transform into a chaos experiment and vice versa. However, any strategy can be considered for resilience testing a system.

Many tools emphasize on creating chaos experiments or resilience tests. Prominent examples are Gremlin [Gre], Chaos Monkey [Net], and ChaosToolkit [Chaa]. In the scope of our work, we focus on ChaosToolkit as we have the most experience with this tool, similar to JMeter. Kesim et al. [KHFH20] and Frank et al. [FHW+22] have demonstrated practical usage of ChaosToolkit in different contexts. Also it benefits from a large community. The following information origin from the official ChaosToolkit documentation [Chab].

As a python based, open source platform, ChaosToolkit is a lightweight solution to create chaos experiments for software applications. The tool achieves fault injection using *drivers* that enable *probes* to inject different kinds of behavior depending on the selected *driver* and use case. The most common *drivers* are *chaostoolkit-spring* for applications using the Spring framework and *chaostoolkit-kubernetes* for applications hosted on a Kubernetes cluster. In ChaosToolkit, the user can choose to define experiments either in Javascript Object Notation (JSON) format or in Yet Another Markup Language (YAML). A resilience experiment consists of a (1) version identifier, a (2) title, a (3) description, a (4) method array, a (5) steady-state-hypothesis, and a (6) rollback array. Table 2.1 shows these objects and a description of each. ChaosToolkit distinguishes between objects that *MUST* occur in every resilience test and objects that *SHOULD* occur in a resilience test to achieve better results. Although, the steady-state-hypothesis is an optional object, it is considered best practice to include a hypothesis as it verifies if the application behaves as expected.

Inside the *method*, the user declares a number of probes that determine the fault type of the resilience test. For instance, a probe provided by the *chaostoolkit-kubernetes* driver, may cause that a Kubernetes pod becomes unavailable until it restarts. Probes that have a specific target artifact, e.g., Kubernetes pods, allow to determine how often the probe should execute the fault type. For instance, the user can decide to apply the fault type randomly to all available artifacts, or determine that the fault type is only applied once to a specific artifact given its identifier. Lastly,

Apdex Level	Multiplier	Time (e.g., 1.2 seconds)
Satisfied	T or less	≤ 1.2 seconds
Tolerated	$T >$ or $T < 4T$	between 1.2 seconds and 4.8 seconds
Frustrated	$T > 4T$	greater than 4.8 seconds

Table 2.2: Example for the Apdex Performance Index

the *method* allows to define the total duration of the resilience test given in seconds as well as a pause period between the execution of multiple probes. However, ChaosToolkit does not collect information about the execution context of the resilience test. We have learned that resilience tests can be executed in production and in more secure environments where the end user is not negatively affected by the test run. This context can not be declared within a resilience test specification of ChaosToolkit, but the user implies the context by selecting the appropriate artifact identifiers inside the probes. For instance, a Kubernetes Pod that runs in production has a unique identifier inside the production cluster. However, a Kubernetes Pod that runs in a testing cluster has a different identifier. Therefore, the user must declare the correct identifier in order to run the resilience test in a specific environment.

We can conclude that a resilience test needs the following four information, i.e., (1) the fault type, (2) the repetition of the fault type, (3) the execution context, and (5) the steady-state-hypothesis. In addition, we need to declare the (6) duration of a resilience test and the duration of pauses if necessary.

2.1.8 Apdex Performance Index

The apdex performance index [Apd] is an industry-standard measure to determine the user satisfaction level concerning software performance analysis results. The apdex performance index uses a threshold value T to determine value ranges for software performance analysis results and assign them to apdex levels. The Apdex Users Group⁶ illustrates the usage of the index as follows. Assuming a threshold value $T = 1.2$ seconds for the response times of a web application, we can determine the apdex levels as shown in Table 2.2. The apdex levels *satisfied*, *tolerated*, and *frustrated* describe a multiplier using the threshold T concerning the base value of T . Thus, the level *satisfied* comprises all requests which have response times with a value of T or less, i.e., the actual response time is equal to 1.2 seconds or lower. The second level, *tolerated*, comprises requests that have response times that are between the threshold T and a multiple of T , in this example, it is $4 * T$. Thus, the actual response times must be either greater than 1.2 seconds or below $4 * T = 4 * 1.2 = 4.8$ seconds to count as *tolerated*. The last level, *frustrated* is the worse, as it comprises requests which have a response time of 4.8 seconds or larger. The Apdex Users Group explains that the threshold value for T and the apdex levels can be defined for any application.

Depending on the use case, there can be as many levels as needed to describe different ranges of quality metrics. Taking this approach further, T must not even be defined as a threshold value, rather, we can apply it as a reference value for describing categories. A simple constructed example is to define categories of workload for load tests using the apdex performance index. Assume that

⁶<https://www.apdex.org/>

Apdex Level	Multiplier	Total amount of requests
Low	T or less	≤ 4000 req. / min.
Medium	$T >$ or $T < 4T$	between 4000 req. / min. and 16000 req. / min.
High	$T > 4T$	more than 16000 req. / min.

Table 2.3: Example using the Apdex Performance Index describing workloads

we want to create a load test for a web application but do not want to require the developer to provide exact values. Further, we assume that we know from past monitoring results that we have a base load of 4000 requests per minute. We assign our base load to the reference variable T . We can then define the apdex levels as shown in Table 2.3

2.2 Related work

This chapter elaborates on other scientific works that are relevant to this thesis. Thus, this chapter is structured as follows. Section 2.2.1 describes the search strategy for exploring relevant works. Section 2.2.2 outlines the identified works with regard to our initially formulated problems P1, P2, and P3.

2.2.1 Literature Research Methodology

We conducted our search on Google Scholar⁷ and Semantic Scholar⁸ with the keywords and synonyms declared in Table 2.4. In the first iteration, we included papers that mentioned a strict combination of keywords, e.g., "domain-driven design"& "non-functional requirements". We filter irrelevant papers based on the paper titles, abstracts, and section headings. For instance, we excluded results such as *Microservices identification strategies: A review focused on Model-Driven Engineering and DDD approaches* as the title and abstract concludes that the authors do not address the issues of our work. Using not only the keywords but also different synonyms, we minimized the chance on missing relevant works by using another, yet similar keyword. Due to the scarcity of results, we only used one keyword at a time to increase the amount of results. We also considered non-scientific resources for literature review such as blog posts for works on DDD. As the primary focus of our work is in the context of DDD, we primarily focus on papers that belong into DDD related research. Finally, we reviewed relevant papers that were cited by papers which we have considered relevant in the first iteration.

2.2.2 Results

In the following, we outline the identified scientific works we consider as relevant to our contribution. We discuss the results according to our formulated problems P1, P2, and P3.

⁷<https://scholar.google.com/>

⁸<https://www.semanticscholar.org/>

Keywords	Synonyms
domain-driven design	DDD
non-functional requirements	quality requirements software quality requirements software quality software quality attribute quality attribute
domain storytelling	domain story-telling collaborative modeling domain stories
modeling quality requirements	modeling modeling quality attributes modeling non-functional requirements quality attribute modeling quality attribute model
model driven development	model driven software development
model transformation	quality model transformation model transformation language

Table 2.4: Keywords for identifying literature sources

(P1) Modeling Quality Requirements in DDD

Until today, the DDD methodology does not include practices for domain-centric modeling of quality requirements. Evans [Eva04] who proposed DDD in 2004, used generic lines-and-boxes drawings to describe a domain model and used annotations to describe quality properties as business rules. Domain Storytelling (DST) uses similar annotations by describing additional properties of domain story elements. However, both annotation types lack a well-defined formalism for modeling domain-centric quality requirements. Perillo et al. [PGF09] emphasized the need for precise domain annotations and made a contribution for Java-based applications that use annotations to create more detailed descriptions of domain models. However, their solution is entirely technical and does not apply on the domain model from a non-technical perspective. Apparently, they emphasized the usage of UML diagrams to describe domain models even in a DDD context. Further, they do not consider quality requirements in their annotations nor in their domain model. We attempt to solve this issue by using domain-centric annotations in DDD that apply on the domain model from a non-technical perspective.

Annotations are also common to other modeling approaches such as UML [Obj17] and BPMN [Obj10]. UML offers profiles that focus on different quality aspects. For instance, the MARTE profile extends UML by annotations about performance and availability properties. Unlike DDD and DST related annotations, UML profiles and BPMN use a formal language that focus on dedicated quality requirements. Although, UML MARTE and BPMN have an expressive notation, they lack a description of their properties from a domain perspective. Though MARTE allows to separate the domain model from its implementation, formal specifications do not fit into the DDD or DST landscape as they lack the expressiveness of an Ubiquitous Language. A combination of both approaches would be a valuable contribution to DST by leveraging a formal language notation such as MARTE and the domain-centric language of an Ubiquitous Language.

Furthermore, annotations already exist in current DDD and DST practices. Thus, we figured that it is a suitable approach to use formal annotations from UML as a guide to express their formalism on a different model.

An older contribution by Brito et al. [BMA02] proposes a process for modeling quality requirements and integrate them with functional requirements. Brito et al. [BMA02] propose UML use case diagrams as text descriptions as models for quality requirements. Refining the use cases with domain-centric information the requirements become more expressive and increase in quality. However, the contribution by Brito et al. [BMA02] emphasizes the relationship and trade-offs among quality requirements but lacks expressiveness on a domain model. Furthermore, a textual or graphical notation of use case diagrams does not align with DDD or DST as they do not consider domain-centric properties.

(P2) Transformation of Annotated-Models

Due to the scarcity of scientific works that propose a solution for our problem P2, we have included other scientific works of interest.

Le et al. [LDN18] have attempted to combine the UML specification with DDD by proposing a Domain-specific Language (DSL) that extends UML classes by additional domain properties. The proposed DSL simplifies the description of domain-centric properties on a technical plane by adding domain properties to UML class diagrams. A solution to our problem P2 requires a transformation step from annotated domain-centric models into technical specifications. Although they do not explicitly contribute towards our formulated problem P2, we believe that their DSL based approach may become a supportive asset in attempting to transform annotated domain models by using their DSL as a set of transformation rules.

We consider the lack of a uniform data model for annotations that describe a technical specification, such as a resilience test, a major issue in finding a solution for P2. Frank et al. [FHW+22] made use of quality scenarios, in particular ATAM, to uniformly describe different quality attributes. Furthermore, in their work, Frank et al. [FHW+22] described resilience and load tests using the ATAM scenario description. Unfortunately, they have not elaborated on automatically transforming their scenario description into executable tests that would have been a major step towards solving P2. However, they have demonstrated that ATAM scenarios serve as a skeleton for a uniform data model that is a part of finding a solution to P2. We are convinced that we can leverage their contribution in our work by using ATAM scenarios as a uniform description of runtime quality analysis tests on the domain level.

Although we do not intend to provide an implemented solution to P2, we attempt to create a conceptual solution on transforming an annotated domain model into executable runtime quality analysis tests. Model-driven Software Development (MDS) is a well-known research area focusing on creating solutions from abstract meta-models by using model transformations [Lid11]. A principle difficulty is the transformation of an abstract (meta) model to platform-specific models. JMeter and ChaosToolkit are examples of platform-specific models in the context of our work. We would even argue that DDD and domain stories created through DST are examples of platform-specific models. There are numerous approaches that pick up on the concepts of MDS such like Model-driven Architecture (MDA) and Domain-specific Languages (DSL). In their article, Sendall and Kozaczynski [SK03] examined different approaches to model transformation and discussed

characteristics of languages to describe a model transformation. In the context of our work, a model transformation language would require a detailed understanding of a meta-model for domain models that follow DDD principles. According to Sendall and Kozaczynski [SK03] model transformation languages offer the most potential for describing model transformations as they provide a DSL that precisely defines the context and transformation rules. Although, we have not found existing solutions, we consider that the concept of model transformation languages and the contribution by Le et al. [LDN18] may assist in future iterations to find a automated transformation process to our problem P2. However, the work by Sendall and Kozaczynski [SK03] emphasizes on UML, and modeling languages with a similar technical notation are the basis for current model transformation languages. Furthermore, introducing a meta-model in DDD to describe an already abstract (domain) model would potentially lead to a more complex notation. Furthermore, the work by Sendall and Kozaczynski [SK03] and Le et al. [LDN18] do not consider to apply model transformations on runtime quality analysis tests as we attempt to do with our contribution.

Since we have not found dedicated scientific works or other contributions that combine DDD with model transformations, we figured that a future evaluation of scientific works may yield better results. DDD is yet a widely applied practice, yet, it lacks contribution in terms of scientific work. To the best of our efforts, we have not found a scientific contribution that focuses on model transformations in a DDD or DST context, yet alone with regard to runtime quality analysis.

(P3) Reporting Analysis Results of Software Analysis Tests

Reporting analysis results has been a part of the works by Kesim et al. [KHFH20] and Frank et al. [FHW+22]. However, both contributions did not focus on reporting readable analysis results. Instead, they used graph visualizations based on technical metrics such as response times for reporting their results. In our contribution, we intend to create a domain-centric readable result report that aggregates technical metrics into a format understandable by domain experts. Reports displaying raw data is perfect for reasoning about actual numbers. However, this requires fundamental knowledge about the metrics' influence on the application. Okanović et al. [OHZ+19] confirms our statement by arguing that data-driven reports do not yield much value to domain experts as they do not have the capability to make decisions based on data they do not understand entirely. Therefore, Okanović et al. [OHZ+19] proposed a concept to describe performance and reliability concerns using natural language and to report the results in prose text containing experiment details and a summary of the initially phrased concern.

Yet, the author's prototype offers a template consisting of pre-determined parameters for a chosen template related to performance properties. The analysis results report consists of the initially phrased concern, an answer in prose text with details about the test run, as well as data to support the claim of the answer. However, the solution by Okanović et al. [OHZ+19] is not related to DDD or DST but rather concerns about reporting performance analysis results to users in a readable manner without using data-driven charts or dashboards. In our work, we provide Runtime Quality Analysis (RQA) results to domain experts in a similar way. Although, we do not only consider load tests as part of our analysis results. Further we intended to include reports for resilience tests and monitoring results which do not significantly differ from load tests results besides using different parameters. From our perspective, we consider the solution by Okanović et al. [OHZ+19] as an asset for our own solution since we also concern about performance analysis as part of RQA. However,

in this work we do not use the concern specification of the author's prototype but we have used the concept of the report generator. Although we hold onto the possibility to include the concern specification by Okanović et al. [OHZ+19] in a future iteration of our concept.

2.2.3 Summary

In conclusion, to the best of our knowledge, there are no profound scientific work providing solutions to our concerns P1, P2, and P3. However, we have identified several scientific works that contribute towards a solution but work primarily on the technical plane by using formal notations (UML). Further, existing contributions require awareness of stakeholders for technical details such as in the contribution by Le et al. [LDN18]. We conclude that we provide a novel solution for our concerns P1, P2, and P3 that currently have not been solved from a domain-centric perspective. In contrast to the contributions made by Le et al. [LDN18] and Sendall and Kozaczynski [SK03], we enable a concise modeling of domain-centric runtime quality analysis without assuming technical expertise in UML or modeling notation. We have combined the concept of using annotations from existing UML profiles (e.g., MARTE) with using annotations in DST and extended the annotated information by RQA related properties. Thus, proposing a well-integrated solution to P1. Further, we have used the ATAM scenario description similar to the works by Frank et al. [FHW+22] but extending their concept by a conceptual mapping that allows transformation of annotated models into technical specifications, thus, solving P2 conceptually. At last, we have used the report generation concept by Okanović et al. [OHZ+19] and extended it by additional content related to resilience tests and monitoring specifications to solve P3.

As of now, there is still a lack of scientific contributions concerning DDD and DST in general. We believe that in the future, interesting contributions emerge that need to be considered for the next iterations of our concept.

3 User Requirements Elicitation

Requirements Engineering is a comprehensive process that comprises different methods to elicit and evaluate data from multiple, possibly distinct information sources [Poh10]. Practitioners, i.e., requirements engineers support stakeholders to become aware of their actual business needs and formulate user requirements. It is essential for the quality of the elicitation process to identify all necessary information sources. According to the information sources, requirements engineers then decide on elicitation techniques that yield the most value to gather their information, e.g., interviews, questionnaires, and such [Poh10]. In this chapter, we elaborate on the requirements elicitation process.

This chapter is structured as follows. Section 3.1 states the incentive of the elicitation process and provides an overview of the data of interest. Section 3.2 describes the technique and structure of the elicitation process.

3.1 Objective

This elicitation had two objectives. First, we needed to get a better understanding of issues domain experts experience in their current processes for modeling non-functional (or quality) requirements constrained to performance and reliability. Second, we wanted to identify requirements for a possible modeling solution. We have separate our questions into three categories. The first category (D) consisted of questions to elicit demographic data from the participants. We have used demographic information for analyzing our target group and the domain expert's experiences in their current positions. The second category (NFR) consisted of questions to identify the as-is state of describing and modeling performance and reliability requirements in the domain expert's environments. We intended to identify potential issues of domain expert's methods for modeling quality requirements. The last category (M) consisted of questions concerning understanding issues in the domain expert's current processes and questions to elicit requirements for the first solution towards a modeling concept. We have conducted our first interview as a pilot interview to examine whether our procedure works and whether we receive the results we expected with the questions we have prepared for the interviews. Depending on the outcome of the pilot interview, we have changed our procedure to some extent to achieve our objectives more efficiently.

3.2 Data Collection and Evaluation Methodology

In the following, we summarize the data that we have collected during the elicitation process, how we elicited this information, and how we evaluated the collected information.

3.2.1 Data Collection and Information Sources

For our elicitation we intended to consider the following information sources. Stakeholders involved in dqualizer, technical or legal documents, and systems that currently provide a solution to our problems P1, P2, and P3 [Poh10]. After thorough consideration we figured that we did not have access to any documentation or to relevant technical solutions that would be worth considering as information sources. Therefore, we have figured that the stakeholders of the companies involved in dqualizer were our principal information source.

Due to the participation of two companies in dqualizer, we could choose from a large variety of domain experts. We got in touch with more stakeholders from target group by asking known stakeholders about other people in their cooperate unit. This is a commonly used method proposed by Pohl [Poh10] to reach out to other stakeholders that were initially not known to us. However, due to time constraints and the limited scope of this work, we only considered a small amount of stakeholders for the elicitation process. As being involved in dqualizer, we also had access to workshop documents and results granting us a first impression on the stakeholder's expectations towards our modeling concept and prototype requirements.

We decided to use one-on-one interviews as our elicitation method since it aligned with our identified information sources. Pohl [Poh10] argues that survey-based elicitation methods such as interviews are the best choice for eliciting unbiased and precise requirements from experts. The author further argues that new questions can be addressed immediately and reveal hidden concerns or subconscious requirements. Another advantage of one-on-one interviews is that we have actively avoided the group thinking bias that typically occurs in interview sessions which involve multiple participants [Jan08].

According to Paetsch et al. [PEM03] and Pohl [Poh10] we had to decide between closed interviews, open interviews and semi-structured interviews. The latter is a mix of the first two interview methods. Pohl [Poh10] advises to combine supporting methods with other elicitation techniques to balance out potential weaknesses. For example, lacking the ability to ask detailed questions in an ongoing discussion is a common pitfall for semi-structured interviews if conducted by an inexperienced moderator. Furthermore, questions in semi-structured interviews are not as strictly phrased as in closed interviews. Therefore, it occurs that participants have difficulties in understanding poorly phrased questions. For this purpose, we decided to use prototyping as a supporting elicitation method [Poh10]. Prototyping uses illustrations of potential solutions to assist interview participants in case they only have a vague understanding of a question or their requirements. For our purposes, we have used the following material listed in Section 3.4.1.

As we have already explained, we will categorize our questions into three different categories with the labels D, NFR, and M. Table 3.1 shows and explains the categories by describing each. We have used Likert scales [Lik32] in the elicitation of demographical data to describe the participant's level of expertise based on their judgment. Figure 3.1 shows the scale we have used in the interview.

3.2.2 Interview Data Evaluation

We have conducted the interviews remotely because of the current COVID situation and other location-related issues, i.e., distance to the stakeholder's locations. We have planned to provide a Zoom session and have recorded the interviews in the process. The recordings were only made

Figure 3.1: Likert scale to determine the participant's expertise

Category	Description
Demographical (D)	Includes information about the participant's age, occupation, work experiences, and the like. Commonly researchers ask demographical questions at the beginning of an interview
Non-functional (NFR)	Comprises questions to identify non-functional requirements that are most important to the participants with respect to their use cases
Methodological (M)	Describes the methodological approaches that the participants have used in the past to model and describe non-functional requirements and how they proceeded to create appropriate technical solutions to ensure their fulfillment

Table 3.1: Description of question categories

available to us and not to the public. At the end of each interview we created summaries of each interview for evaluation purposes. Afterwards, we sent the summaries to the participants to avoid misunderstandings or misinterpretations. We have processed drawings or diagrams by the participants in situations where they have been in a non-readable state such as handmade scribbles. The interview summary and supplementary material will only be available to the researchers and participants akin to the interview recordings.

3.3 Stakeholders Selection

In Section 3.2.1, we have already elaborated that we have selected our participants from two companies involved in the dqualizer research project. Therefore, we have used a convenience sampling approach since we only reached out to potential participants that were available to us [BR22]. We got in touch with four participants in total from both companies, i.e., we received the contact information from two potential participants from the insurance company and two from the wage taxing company. In the process, we reached out to more cooperate units within both companies to get in touch with different domain experts. The cooperate units were the same units of the stakeholders from both companies who were responsible for representing their unit in dqualizer. Thus, these units were of most interest to us since they had an actual interest in our work and provided the use cases for dqualizer and our work.

3.4 Interview Preparation

This section elaborates on the steps we have executed to prepare ourselves for conducting the interviews. Thus, Section 3.4.1 shows the preparation of supporting material. Section 3.4.2 outlines our question catalogue. Lastly, Section 3.4.3 describes the planning and results of our pilot interview.

3.4.1 Supporting Material

We have prepared the following supporting material. First, we have created two fictional domain stories with regard to the participant's business domain (i.e., insurance and wage taxing). We have used the illustrations for the questions of the category M where we tried to find potential prototype requirements. Further, we have added prototype-related annotations based on our prototype drafts. Although the user stories and metrics could not be considered prototype illustrations, we determined that they are a precondition of our prototype and thus, were valuable for illustrating our modeling concept. Second, we have phrased sample business-related questions in combination with business metrics in natural language for questions of category NFR. We used natural language to make the samples better readable and understandable for the participants instead of using a dedicated requirements standard [Poh10]. At last, we only prepared the user stories for situations where the participants had difficulties answering the questions. The domain stories illustrated two fictional scenarios for the insurance domain and the wage taxing domain. The following list enumerates the rephrased user stories.

- As a *product owner* I would like to *observe* the response times and throughput of external services as a means to *guarantee* the fulfillment of our Service Level Agreement (SLA).
- As a *sales representative* I would like to *receive* the response times of our business processes in real time as a means to *take action* for solving potential problems before they occur.
- As a *faculty staff representative* I would like to *know* how efficient my contract processes are as a means to *identify and optimize* potential bottlenecks.

Subsequently, we phrased the metrics in natural language as follows.

- An insurance contract should be created and stored by the system within 3 seconds during regular working hours.
- The system's response time deviates at most by 0.1% from its determined response time threshold if the number of users increases by 30%.
- The response time of our services stays below 3 seconds, if any external services fail.

Lastly, Figure 3.2 shows one of the domain stories we have used in the interviews. The content of the domain stories should not reflect an actual domain model of either company, rather we wanted to create samples that appeared familiar to the participants. The purpose of these samples was to illustrate a potential solution for our proposed approach. A precondition of our concept is the existence of well-defined domain stories. Thus it was not in our interest, to verify the participant's understanding of DST. Therefore, we did not require from participants to understand DST-related terminology such as *work objects* or *activities*.

Figure 3.2: (Translated) domain story of an example insurance system

Figure 3.2 shows the fictional domain story for the insurance company. In this domain story we have modeled a generic process where an insurance commissioner creates an insurance contract on behalf of a customer. Next, the insurance sends the previously created contract to other institutions to request further data like clinical pictures and confirm that the customer data has been registered at these institutions. Afterwards, the external institutions send a confirmation that the data is valid. Now, the insurance stores the insurance contract in some customer table in their database and assigns the contract an ID. Lastly, the insurance commissioner attempts to request all insurance contracts from the customer table. For brevity reasons, we do not discuss the domain story for the wage taxing domain as it follows the same intend as Figure 3.2. However, we have attached the wage taxing domain story in Appendix A. For the purpose of demonstrating our concept, we prepared two problems that may serve as use cases for our modeling concept. In addition, we have prepared four modeling artifacts to model a solution to a problem statement which may either be one of the samples we prepared or a problem that the participants phrases.

At first, we phrased the two problem statements for the insurance domain story as follows.

- Q_1 : Is it possible to request new insurance contracts from the customer table if the saving process fails for new insurance contracts?
- Q_2 : Is it possible to create insurance contracts if the number of concurrent insurance commissioners increases by 30%?

ID	Question	Category	Confidential
D1	Where do you work?	D	Yes
D2	What is your current role?		
D2.1	With which role would you associate yourself with?	D	No
D3	How many years of experience do you have?		

Table 3.2: Question catalogue – demographical questions

ID	Question	Category	Confidential
N1	How did you formulate/capture non-functional properties so far?		
N1.1	(follow up) Have you been using any specific procedure?		
N1.2	(follow up) What would you consider the biggest problem in your current approach?	NFR	No
N1.3	(follow up) Where exactly do these problems occur?		
N1.4	(follow up) If you had the money, manpower, and time would you change your approach? If yes, how would it look like?		
N2	How would you like to be involved in this process?		

Table 3.3: Question catalogue – questions towards non-functional requirements

For the modeling artifacts, we created four distinct icons with sample properties to describe the solution in more detail. The first artifact *Service call delay* represented a delay of a service request to some target, e.g., an HTTP request to a REST endpoint. The second artifact *Service failure* expressed a service failure. The third artifact *Load increase* described a variation of a load test where the target system experiences an increasing workload of a predetermined period. The last artifact *Monitor Service X* represented a monitoring specification to observe a certain HTTP endpoint about some metric over a dedicated period.

3.4.2 Question Catalogue

Table 3.2, Table 3.3, and Table 3.4 show the initial question catalog that we have used as a guide for the interviews. Table 3.2 lists all demographical questions we asked at the beginning of the interview. Note that answers to question D1 will not be distributed or cited in this work.

Table 3.3 covers all questions we asked for eliciting and documenting non-functional requirements in the participant's business domain. We expected to gain information about problems that occur during the elicitation of non-functional requirements and how they are translated to the technical environment (N1 to N1.3). Furthermore, we expected to find out how the participants would like to improve this process from their point of view (N1.4).

Table 3.4 shows the list of questions about how domain experts phrase operational questions to technical experts and what information they provide along with their questions (M1 to M1.2). Moreover, we were interested in how these information translate to the technical environment and

ID	Question	Category	Confidential
M1	Can you give examples of questions from operational business you would like an answer to?		
M1.1	Can you identify metrics that you would state within your question?		
M1.2	How important are these questions for your daily business?		
M2	With whom do you communicate to receive answers to operational questions?		
M2.1	(follow up) Can you give an detailed explanation of this process?		
M2.2	(follow up) What would you consider the biggest problem?		
M2.3	(follow up) Where exactly do problems occur?		
M3	How would you like to be involved in this process?		
M4	(Demonstration of Example Model with Annotations)		
M4.1	Do you consider this approach as reasonable for modeling questions?	M	No
M4.2	Could you specify further metrics for your question?		
M5	Assuming you have successfully prepared a question and your tool collected the results. What representation of the results would you prefer?		
M5.1	(follow up) Assume that your tool would also return technical details about the results. How likely is it that you use them?		
M5.2	(follow up) What information would you expect to be included in the result?		
M5.3	(follow up) What kind of information would you not want to be included in the result?		
M5.4	(follow up) Which metrics would you expect to be included in the result?		

Table 3.4: Question catalogue – operational business questions

how technical experts communicate the analysis results back to the domain experts (M2 to M3). The residual questions intended to get feedback on a first draft of our modeling concept as shown in (M4 to M5).

The interview language was German as the participants are German natives which diminished the chance of misunderstanding a question or giving misleading answers. We prepared a consent form that the participants had to sign in order to proceed with the interview. The consent form assured that we were eligible to process the information in our research. Further, it granted us permission to record the audio and video of the interviews for a post-interview analysis to create the interview summary. The participants received invitations to the interview with information about the interview's objective, research context, interview duration, and a kind request to forward the

Figure 3.3: Likert scale for classifying the participants domain & technical knowledge

Figure 3.4: Likert scale for domain knowledge classification

invitation to other stakeholders in case there are stakeholders available that fit into our target group. Lastly, we attached the consent form to the interview invitation. We attached the consent form and interview question catalogue in Appendix A together with the residual interview material.

3.4.3 Pilot Interview

The first interview has been conducted on July 29th 2022 as a pilot interview for refining our question catalogue and practice the use of our supporting material. We followed the interview procedure as we have defined it in the previous sections. At the end we collected feedback about the interview process. Although, we received positive feedback, we decided to change the closed questions D2 and D2.1 by changing the Likert scales. In our first iteration, we created the Likert scale as seen Figure 3.3. During the pilot interview, we have noticed that it may be confusing to the participant where to classify himself according to the terminology we have used in the Likert scale. For instance, the participant asked if a technical expert with little domain expertise has less technical expertise than the technical expert aligned at the most right on the scale. Thus, we have changed the Likert scale by separating the classification of the domain and technical expertise into two different scales.

Figure 3.4 and Figure 3.5 shows the new scaling. Therefore, Figure 3.4 shows that we specifically asked for a classification of the participant’s domain knowledge where they could classify themselves between having very little domain knowledge (1) to being a domain expert (5). Figure 3.5 provides a classification for technical knowledge ranging from having very little technical knowledge (1) to being a technical expert (5). We have used the new Likert scales for questions D2 and D2.1 in subsequent interviews expecting a better classification of the participant’s knowledge.

Figure 3.5: Likert scale for technical knowledge classification

3.5 Results

In total we conducted four interviews in three weeks with participants from two distinct employers. The interviews took approximately 45 to 55 minutes in addition to collecting feedback from the participants about the interview process. To protect the participant's identities, we use acronyms to address individual answers. The acronyms were selected according to the participant's business domains. Hence, I_{p_1} and I_{p_2} reference the participants from the insurance business domain. Respectively, WT_{p_1} and WT_{p_2} reference the participants from the wage taxing business domain.

This section is structured as follows. Section 3.5.1 shows the elicited demographic data of the participants. Section 3.5.2 summarizes concerns and issues of the participants concerning non-functional requirements elicitation. Section 3.5.3 explains and itemizes operational business questions and concerns occurring in the wage taxing and insurance domains. Section 3.5.4 itemizes how the participants perceived the first approach to our modeling concept and prototype.

3.5.1 Demographic Data

The answers to demographic questions comprised the names of the participants and their current employer. Further, we asked them to name their current position and in which environment they work in. As we are not allowed to give detailed information about the participants' employers, we only referred to the participants' business domain they are working in, i.e., insurances and wage taxing, and their currently employed position. In the beginning, we asked the participants to classify their expertise with regard to their domain and technical knowledge on a Likert scale, i.e., Figure 3.4 and Figure 3.5, which we have shown in the previous chapter.

The plot in Figure 3.6 shows the results of this classification along two axes. The y-axis represents the domain knowledge on a scale from one to five (one being the lowest amount of expertise, five being the highest amount). Vice versa, the x-axis represents the technical knowledge on a scale from one to five (one being the lowest amount of expertise, five being the highest amount). The participants with the ID WT work at the same employer in the wage taxing industry. Vice versa, participants with the ID I work at the same employer in the insurance industry. The coordinates on the plot represent a participant's knowledge concerning their business domain and their technical expertise within a particular position. An exception is the position of I_{p_1} who was the participant from the pilot interview. As we did not provide a clear separation of the domain and technical knowledge at first, we determined the y-coordinates based on the answers the participant provided to us and what he stated to know about the business domain. We decided to classify the participant's domain knowledge on the Likert scale with a value of two point five. This value is a mere subjective interpretation and may deviate from the participant's actual domain knowledge.

Figure 3.6: Participant classification with regard to domain and technical knowledge

3.5.2 Non-functional Requirements Elicitation

We continued asking about procedures for eliciting and verifying non-functional requirements (N1 to N2 in Table 3.3). As we have interviewed employees from two different employers, we inspected their answers one after another to identify similarities and differences in their approaches to elicit non-functional requirements. We did not ask further questions about the participant's problems within a particular business domain nor the business' needs they have to meet. However, they provided us little information on their own during the conversations. In the insurance domain, I_{p_1} and I_{p_2} explained that different insurance coverage exist for clients depending on their status and contracts. Subsequent calculations must consider these contractual differences. This implies that they must gather information from multiple sources, e.g., tax offices or the like. Thus, there exist external dependencies to their applications where they do not have much influence on the application's capabilities. Another critical concern are periodic differences in the calculation tables for clients. For instance, clients that did not exceed certain insurance thresholds for a determined period of time have a different insurance contribution than someone who recently exceeded this threshold. According to I_{p_1} and I_{p_2} , there exist multiple sources from which the application receives its input. Combined with the other concerns, I_{p_1} and I_{p_2} explained that monitoring is one of their prime interests.

In the wage taxing domain, stakeholders have to consider similar issues according to WT_{p_1} and WT_{p_2} . There exist external dependencies to third party offices, such as tax offices and health insurances that receive contractual information about clients. A major difference between the two domains is the periodic occurrence of peak workloads in the wage taxing domain. WT_{p_2} reported that wage taxing offices must meet reoccurring submission deadlines. However, these deadlines differ among German states. Thus, the workloads are predictable but must be handled nonetheless. In conclusion, WT_{p_1} and WT_{p_2} voiced principle interest in making their applications resilient towards heavy workloads.

Figure 3.7: Communication among domain experts, mediator, and technical experts

Figure 3.8: Iterative communication to gather technical information from domain experts

Insurance Domain

I_{p1} and I_{p2} work in similar environments, thus, it is likely that they work with similar tools. In this case, the answers about working processes and concerns yielded similar answers to the questions N1 to N2. However, as I_{p2} holds a responsible position, answers about technical information were not as detailed as from I_{p1} . Starting with the question N1, I_{p1} and I_{p2} reported that, in the past, their processes were inefficient with regard to the communication between the different stakeholders. A prime issue was the lack of a common language (see problem P1 as mentioned in Chapter 1) that allows both parties efficient communication about their concerns. Therefore, over the past years, they have established an iterative process for non-functional requirements elicitation that introduces a mediator responsible for communicating concerns between both parties. This process strictly separates the management from technical departments. I_{p2} mentioned that this separation is meaningful and should be maintained to a certain degree. Although, I_{p2} prefers that the management becomes more proficient with the technical details of their application landscape. Figure 3.7 illustrates this process and shows the communication between the domain expert, the mediator, and the technical experts. According to I_{p1} and I_{p2} , all requirements originate from the domain experts or a higher management department. At first, these requirements were formulated as headlines lacking detailed information. The mediator produces a formalized specification from these headlines and forwards the document to the technical experts. We have been told, that I_{p1} and I_{p2} are not eligible to give us precise information about the language or structure of the formalized specification. However, I_{p1} mentions that this document is phrased in a way that it is understandable for the technical experts and domain experts. In the last step, the technical experts inspect the specification and attempt to create a technical solution based on the given information.

However, according to I_{p1} , the provided specification lacks vital technical information necessary to create a solution, e.g., a monitoring specification. I_{p1} mentions that when the technical experts receive notification about the specification, they miss information on percentiles, measuring points,

Figure 3.9: Cross functional teams leading to strong collaboration

time intervals, and the like. In that case, the technical experts had to gather more information, initiating an iterative communication process. Figure 3.8 illustrates this iterative process in case there are missing information. At first, the technical experts request further information from the mediator with regard to fulfilling the previously stated specification. Then, the mediator forwards this request to the domain experts. Neither I_{p_1} nor I_{p_2} told us how the mediator elicited more information from the domain experts. However, I_{p_1} remarks that, if necessary, the mediator assists the domain experts in understanding technical terms as best as possible. Afterwards, if the domain experts provide further information, the mediator forwards the information to the technical experts. In the last step, the technical experts review the specification again with the additional information and decide if they are able to create a solution. In case there is still information missing, they will start all over again by requesting missing information from the mediator. Otherwise, if the technical experts decide to have gathered enough information, they will continue in attempting to create a technical solution for the specification. I_{p_2} stated that despite the higher efficiency this process takes time especially if there are multiple iterations due to a lack of information.

Wage Taxing Domain

WT_{p_1} and WT_{p_2} . WT_{p_1} and WT_{p_2} reported that there is not a strict separation between the stakeholders as shown in Figure 3.7, but they enforce a strong collaboration between domain and technical experts. WT_{p_1} explained that they promote the idea of cross-functional teams that reduce the dependencies on external departments by involving product owners, requirements engineers, and technical experts such as developers and testers in the team composition. As each team focuses on a specific fraction of the wage taxing business domain, WT_{p_2} explained that the teams are collaborating with a team of product owners who focus on strategic decisions that comprise the entire wage taxing domain of the company. In contrast, the team product owner is responsible for domain-related questions that only affect the team's business domain. Figure 3.9 shows this concept and what a potential team composition looks like according to WT_{p_1} .

The teams include at least one team product owner responsible for arguing on behalf of the strategic product owners and end users. The product owner is an integral part of the team as he is responsible for prioritization of non-functional requirements. The product owner supports requirements engineers who are also familiar with the problem domain but can communicate on a more technical level than the product owner. Lastly, the teams consist of developers and testers who lead discussions from a technical perspective. WT_{p_1} mentions that, depending on the project context, there may be other roles involved, e.g., security or user experience experts.

In a typical scenario, WT_{p_2} reports that the strategic product owners pass down the requirements to the cross-functional teams via the team product owner. WT_{p_1} and WT_{p_2} stated that their non-functional requirements are abstract and do not include precise technical information, e.g., percentiles or similar. In that case, the technical experts support the team product owner and requirements engineer with their knowledge to gather the necessary information collaboratively. In the next step, the team product owner and requirements engineer evaluate and prioritize the requirements. WT_{p_2} further explains that, if necessary, they consult senior experts that assist them in prioritizing and understanding requirements that involve legacy systems or interfaces.

WT_{p_1} remarks that the team constantly exchanges information and discusses changes in the requirements. In some cases, the team involves product owners from the strategic team. In particular, this is the case when metrics for non-functional requirements change in the course of a project. Unlike the process shown in Figure 3.7, the team collaborates with the strategic product owners to precisely define the non-functional requirements, quality goals, and metrics necessary to create technical solutions. The team uses the arc42¹ software architecture template to document different views, viewpoints and design decisions toward fulfilling the quality goals.

In the end, WT_{p_1} and WT_{p_2} did not state any problems with this approach besides the necessity to communicate extensively. However, this is a benefit of cross-functional teams as there are merely a few dependencies to other stakeholders. Additionally, WT_{p_2} mentioned that this approach is quite exhaustive to execute on an enterprise level as many teams have to organize across the organization.

3.5.3 Operational Business Questions

In the second part of the interview, we asked the participants about operational business questions (M1 to M5.4). For these questions, we have used the prepared prototype illustrations shown in Figure 3.2 and Figure A.2. We have prepared the domain stories in Miro² and shared our screen to make the illustrations accessible to the participants. During demonstration, we made clear assumptions about the technical context to allow participants to focus on the understandability and usability of the proposed modeling elements and descriptions. We made the following assumptions.

1. A suitable domain story modeling tool integrates our modeling concept.
2. There exists a precise technical mapping between the modeled domain story and the application's architecture to ensure a valid mapping.

¹<https://www.arc42.de/>

²<https://miro.com/de/>

3. The modeling tool connects to a black box application that receives the modeled elements to create technical test specifications.
4. The black box application initiates test runs using appropriate monitoring, load- and resilience tools, and receives the results from the test runs and/or simulations.

However, the participants still received the chance to give feedback and express any problems with the proposed approach independent of the previously made assumptions.

Insurance Domain

The answers given by I_{p_1} concerning questions M1 and M2 were more detailed than the answers of I_{p_2} . Note that according to the self-evaluation, I_{p_2} stated to have a major domain knowledge encourages the fact that I_{p_2} holds a leading role as a technical product owner. Table 3.5 shows examples of operational business questions as stated by I_{p_1} and I_{p_2} .

We decided to phrase these questions as user stories to stay consistent with the results from previous dqualizer workshops. I_{p_1} and I_{p_2} mentioned that we are not eligible to receive detailed information about specific threshold values or names of used measuring endpoints due to confidentiality reasons. I_{p_1} provided two detailed user stories (US1 to US2) with regard to availability and performance. Whereas I_{p_2} provided more user stories (US3 to US8.2) although being formulated more abstract than the user stories provided by I_{p_1} . Moreover, I_{p_1} and I_{p_2} emphasized that their major focus is on monitoring and less on resilience. Although, they do consider resilience for their application's quality, they do not have profound experiences with resilience tests. Thus, the user stories US1 to US8.2 are primarily about knowing what the system does at all times. Although that US3 to US8.2 are very abstract, they reflect concerns the teams have to deal with on behalf of the domain experts. I_{p_2} remarks that the issue persists that such concerns lack detailed technical information in order to be answerable. Even though that we were familiar with that issue, we wanted to know if domain experts provide any metrics along with their concerns or requirements. According to I_{p_1} and I_{p_2} , domain experts do not provide detailed information in the first iteration. However, both mentioned that they typically aim to get information about these metrics in the second or third iteration. Afterwards, I_{p_1} enumerated on some metrics relevant to almost every requirement they have to satisfy. Table 3.6 shows an excerpt of those metrics as stated by I_{p_1} using fictional thresholds. Additionally, I_{p_1} made references to the previously stated user stories that require the metrics from Table 3.6.

During the interview, I_{p_1} mentioned the duration of measurements as another relevant metric, e.g., for performance which is quite important for technical experts. I_{p_2} did not provide as detailed metrics as I_{p_1} . Rather, I_{p_2} mentions few top-level metrics such as response times as typical metrics they aim to retrieve from the domain experts.

At the time we conducted the interviews, I_{p_1} and I_{p_2} explained that due to their experience in this domain, they predicted some questions that may become relevant to the domain experts. However, since they lack vital information about the business domain, their predictions are not always precise enough. Yet, they try to accommodate the domain expert's concerns by preparing measurements in advance to the best of their knowledge. According to I_{p_2} , the domain experts request information as stated in Table 3.5 too late. Most of the time, they happen when an incident occurred. In these cases, it is almost impossible for the technical experts to create technical tests or a monitoring

ID	Description	Stated by
US1	As a IT-service responsible, I would like to continuously measure and record the <i>availability</i> of IT services and use the records for evaluation	I_{p_1}
US2	As a IT-service responsible, I would like to continuously measure and record the <i>performance</i> of IT services with regard to certain endpoints considering caller specific requirements.	
US3	As a domain expert, I would like to know how well my system performs	I_{p_2}
US4	As a domain expert, I would like to know how the performance of my system has changed since the last release	
US5	As a domain expert, I would like to know if the total amount of processed artifacts has changed since the last release	
US6	As a domain expert, I would like to know how many orders each product line creates	
US7	As a domain expert, I would like to know the response times between two endpoints to verify if my SLA still holds.	
US8.1	As a domain expert, I would like to differentiate my measures in domains within my application landscape to identify problems in each domain more efficiently	
US8.2	As a developer with a focus on monitoring, I would like to differentiate my measures in domains within my application landscape to identify problems in each domain more efficiently	

Table 3.5: Operational questions as user stories from the insurance domain

Relevant for	Metric	Stated by
US1	Availability of at least 99.85% on a yearly basis without considering agreed on downtimes	I_{p_1}
US2	The 90th percentile for a specific endpoint must be below a given thresholds stated in milliseconds	I_{p_1}
US2	The maximum average standard deviation must be below 2.0 without considering agreed on downtimes	I_{p_1}

Table 3.6: Fictional metrics that are relevant for the stated questions in Table 3.5

specification to identify the root cause for the incidents in such a short time. Moreover, the issue remains that even in the case of an incident, domain experts do not provide enough information to address the incident adequately.

Wage Taxing Domain

Unfortunately, both participants from the wage taxing employer could not give us as precise examples as the previous participants. WT_{p_1} and WT_{p_2} reported that their team is new and they did not have as many interactions with the strategic product owners in terms of receiving operational business questions as we phrased them. Moreover, they reported that it is very likely that the strategic product owners receive such requests and incorporate them into the requirements that were forwarded to the team product owners.

However, WT_{p_1} mentioned that in the past such operational questions occurred. Therefore, they decided to incorporate cross-functional teams. WT_{p_1} did not explain why it was necessary to do this, nor how such questions were phrased in the past. Currently, decision makers as WT_{p_1} called them, use AppDynamics³ as a tool to get some information about the system's state and healthiness. The decision makers use the aggregated data from these dashboards to infer decisions from the collected metrics. However, this process seemed inefficient according to WT_{p_1} since the decision makers do not know to derive conclusions from the observed data. Therefore, WT_{p_1} proposes to create requirements in collaboration with the decision makers and then create the necessary tests to gather measures. At last, the test results should be discussed with the decision makers.

WT_{p_2} mentions that there are collaborations with business analysts. In case operational questions arise, business analysts can provide answers to them. Although, WT_{p_2} explains that it would be possible to prepare operational questions and potential solutions in the form of tests and let the business analysts evaluate the results. Unfortunately, WT_{p_2} stated that there has not been a situation that required interaction with business analysts.

3.5.4 Prototype Illustrations

During the presentation of the prototype drafts, most participants concluded that the approached solution is understandable and provides value to enable domain experts to model their concerns. However, I_{p_2} and WT_{p_1} mentioned some concerns. I_{p_2} explained that the proposed solution is not suitable to be used by domain experts alone as they do not have the necessary information available nor the understanding of the technical services that make up their application landscape. Moreover, I_{p_2} stated that the proposed solution does not provide enough details to answer detailed operational questions that require deeper knowledge of the underlying technical services. I_{p_2} thought that this approach is better to use in collaboration with the technical experts. However, in this case I_{p_2} claimed that a manual approach is more efficient. For example, eliciting the requirements from the domain experts and generating the technical specifications seems more efficient than providing a software-based solution, as it also potentially requires multiple iterations.

WT_{p_1} made comments on the maintainability of the underlying domain model. In particular, WT_{p_1} explained that it must be guaranteed that the domain story is kept up-to-date at all times. Otherwise, it may occur that the created tests do not fit the underlying architecture. Furthermore, WT_{p_1} stated that the context menus should contain supporting text to assist domain experts in understanding the shown information and how it connects to the technical level. WT_{p_1} mentioned that most domain experts do not understand technical terms and most terms can not be rephrased in a manner for domain experts to understand them. Further WT_{p_1} mentioned that it could be possible to use the prototype in collaboration with technical experts. As such, it would not be necessary to help domain experts understanding every detail of the modelling elements. Lastly, WT_{p_1} suggested to provide a means to model multiple tests on one element, that can be executed together in a subsequent step. This prevents users from modeling and executing multiple tests one at a time.

³https://www.appdynamics.com/de_de

Figure 3.10: Dqualizer as an improvement to the mediator process shown in Figure 3.8

3.6 Problems and Potential Solutions

In the following, we summarize issues with the modeling concept that the participants mentioned during the interviews. Moreover, we enumerate the problems existing in the participant's work environment where we believe dqualizer would fit in as a solution. Table 3.7 summarizes the previously mentioned user stories.

A noteworthy issue every participant mentioned was the lack of details for requirements. I_{p_1} and I_{p_2} elaborated that they included a mediator role to resolve this issue to a certain degree, see Figure 3.7. Although the mediator eases the communication between the parties, I_{p_1} and I_{p_2} noticed that the issue remained and they need to do multiple iterations with the domain experts via the mediator to receive all necessary information a requirement, see Figure 3.8. We believe that dqualizer improves this process by reducing the number of iterations to receive all required information to create a minimal test specification. Figure 3.10 illustrates how dqualizer improves the process. When the domain experts initially phrase their requirements, the mediator does not forward the information to the technical experts, as usual, instead, the mediator provides the information to dqualizer and motivates the domain expert to provide additional information concerning the modeled scenario. The mediator assists the domain experts to understand and model the requirements directly in dqualizer. Although, the produced dqualizer model may not include every detail necessary to create a test specification, however, it probably contains much more information than in the previous process which reduces the communication overhead on behalf of the technical experts. This improved mediator process can be further extended by allowing technical experts to include additional data fields on the modeled test specifications. Furthermore, technical experts may be enabled to flag certain data fields as mandatory and others as optional to make the process more understandable. This also creates an awareness of the underlying application and interfaces, which has been expressed by I_{p_2} as an improvement. P_1 , P_2 , P_3 , P_4 describe first user stories towards this improvement.

Another issue is the timeliness of the modeled information and underlying domain story. Since dqualizer and the prototype intend to create technical specifications automatically, there must be a mapping procedure that allows to identify the underlying technical services and interfaces to run

ID	Description	Derived from
P ₁	As a mediator in the insurance domain, I would like use dqualizer to motivate domain experts to issue requirements sooner so that the technical experts can attempt to retrieve information from the applications faster	I_{p_1}, I_{p_2}
P ₂	As a technical expert interested in runtime quality analysis results , I would like to add additional data fields to the modeling elements to receive more information from the domain experts	I_{p_1}
P ₃	As a technical expert interested in runtime quality analysis , I would like to mark data fields as important and others as neglectable to assist domain experts in providing mandatory and optional information	I_{p_1}
P ₄	As a technical expert interested in runtime quality analysis results , I would like to add additional data fields to the modeling elements to receive more information from the domain experts	I_{p_1}, I_{p_2}
P ₅	As a domain expert and technical expert interested in runtime quality analysis , I would like to be informed if the mapping between the current domain story and the application architecture has changed	WT_{p_1}
P ₆	As a domain expert and technical expert interested in runtime quality analysis , I would like to be informed if the mapping between the current domain story and the application architecture has changed	WT_{p_1}
P ₇	As a technical expert interested in runtime quality analysis , I would like to check the environment in which the prototype executes the load tests and resilience tests	WT_{p_1}, WT_{p_2}

Table 3.7: User stories that describe open issues & problems

the tests accordingly. However, as software changes constantly, there may occur changes in the architecture and implementation that may not be reflected on the domain level immediately. Thus, the domain stories become outdated. This is also the case if software engineers and domain experts do not apply DDD throughout the entire software development cycle. Since the mapping between the domain stories and application architecture is not the core contribution of this work, we will not elaborate on efficient solutions. However, as this is a principle concern for the future use of the prototype and dqualizer we will consider this as future user stories that needs to be addressed. P₅ and P₆ describe this issue.

The last issue occurred during the interview with the participants from the wage taxing domain. While discussing resilience scenarios, the participants mentioned that there exist different environments in which resilience scenarios may be executing depending on the quality goal, approach, and maturity of the company with regard to resilience testing. However, as the prototype aims to be usable by domain experts, there must be some kind of safety guard to ensure that domain experts do not execute resilience tests in the production environment by accident. Otherwise, this may lead to disastrous outcomes. Unfortunately, this is a technical challenge as this depends on other implementation details as well as on the toolchain used for resilience testing. Therefore, this must be postponed to be addressed in the future. P₇ describes the explained problem.

4 Annotation-based Concept to Extend Domain Storytelling

This chapter explains our contribution, i.e., an annotation-based modeling concept for domain stories as part of Domain Storytelling (DST). We explain how our approach solves the initially phrased problems P1 and P3. Further, we demonstrate a possible solution for P2 by transforming the data model into an executable resilience and load test by using a sample domain story from literature. We emphasize that we introduce the finalized modeling concept in this chapter since we have made improvements to the modeling concept based on the results of the expert evaluation. Chapter 6 outlines the expert evaluation in detail.

This chapter is structured as follows. Section 4.1 discusses the requirements we elicited in the expert interviews that are relevant to creating our modeling concept. Section 4.2 explains the usage of annotations on domain story elements to create RQA tests. Section 4.3 elaborates the produced data model to uniformly describe resilience tests, load tests, and monitoring specifications. Further, this section describes the concept of reporting the RQA analysis results on the domain level. Section 4.4 shows a first strategy for a transformation between domain stories and the software application using dedicated mapping rules. Section 4.5 demonstrates an end-to-end workflow on how the proposed approach works in the context of dqualizer.

4.1 Modeling Concept Requirements

In Chapter 3 we have elaborated our study design for conducting expert interviews and discussed the results at the end. However, the participants have phrased the requirements in natural language without any particular textual structure. For this purpose, we decided to rephrase the requirements using the template for user stories known from Scrum [SS11]. Thus, we use the following textual pattern to describe a requirement [All18]:

As a *<Role>* I would like to *<Action>*, so that *<Reason>*.

Thus, we achieved a uniform and readable description for the elicited requirements. In total, we have identified twelve requirements during the expert interviews. However, not all of them were relevant to the modeling concept. Therefore, we decided to separate the requirements relevant for the modeling concept from requirements relevant for implementing technical features in our prototype. In Chapter 5 we discuss the latter. Table 4.1 shows the requirements that we perceive to be related to the modeling concept.

At this point, we would like to remind that we used pseudonyms as a reference for individual experts that participated in our interviews. The pseudonyms consisted of an acronym representing the expert's business domain, i.e., *WT* for wage taxing and *I* for insurance. Further, we used index numbers to differentiate between the four experts. Table 4.1 consists of three columns.

4 Annotation-based Concept to Extend Domain Storytelling

ID	Description	Source
CR ₁	As a domain expert interested in resilience , I would like to specify the fault type of resilience test to determine in which application context I will inject the fault	WT _{p₂}
CR ₂	As a domain expert interested in resilience , I would like to specify the target for the injection to identify affected services in my application	
CR ₃	As a domain expert interested in resilience , I would like to specify the expected response for a resilience scenario to verify if my system responds correctly	
CR ₄	As a domain expert interested in resilience , I would like to specify the environment in which the prototype executes a resilience test to receive realistic measures	
CR ₅	As a technical expert interested in runtime quality analysis results , I would like to receive technical metrics in the results of a runtime quality analysis to make a concise conclusion	WT _{p₁} , I _{p₁} , I _{p₂}
CR ₆	As a technical expert interested in runtime quality analysis results , I would like to include the response times in the results of a runtime quality analysis to make a concise conclusion	
CR ₇	As a technical expert interested in runtime quality analysis results , I would like to include percentiles in the results of a runtime quality analysis to make a concise conclusion	
CR ₈	As a domain expert interested in monitoring , I would like to specify multiple measuring endpoints to observe different interfaces within my application	I _{p₁} , I _{p₂}
CR ₉	As a domain expert interested in monitoring , I would like to specify a response time threshold to see if my subsystems and components respond within the permitted threshold	
CR ₁₀	As a domain expert interested in monitoring , I would like to specify a 90 th percentile for the monitored services to receive detailed information about my system's response times	
CR ₁₁	As a domain expert interested in monitoring , I would like to specify a time period in which I can observe different interfaces within my application	

Table 4.1: Requirements that describe the capabilities of our modeling concept

The first column shows the requirement's ID. The second column contains the description of the requirements with regard to the user story template we have explained in the beginning. The last column references the expert by whom we derived the requirement.

CR₁ to CR₄ were stated by WT_{p₂} and relate to resilience testing. The three requirements list the information domain experts are typically interested in according WT_{p₂}. At first, WT_{p₂} stated that in their business domain, they differentiate between different types of resilience scenarios. Upon rephrasing the requirement, the expert stated a requirement as follows.

As a domain expert interested in resilience, I would like to specify the type of resilience scenario to identify affected services and components in my application.

However, upon asking for more information, we figured that this statement consisted of two requirements that focus on different aspects of a resilience test. Thus, we divided the previously stated requirement into two distinct requirements. We labeled them with the ID CR₁ and CR₂ in

Table 4.1. Therefore, we can differentiate between the fault injection type of a resilience scenario and the services that will be affected by the fault injection. In particular, WT_{p_2} mentioned that they perform fault injections on the application-level in their domain.

At first, I_{p_1} phrased CR_5 generally as it applies to the report of analysis results of RQA tests. In a more detailed discussion, I_{p_1} revealed that there should be allowed to include specific metrics in the analysis results report. In this context, I_{p_1} mentioned the metrics percentile and response times. Thus, we added two more requirements to Table 4.1 with the IDs CR_6 and CR_7 that include both metrics mentioned by I_{p_1} . Although that CR_6 and CR_7 are also related to the prototype requirements, we figure that it is also relevant for our modeling concept as we need to consider storing this information in our data model.

Lastly, we elicited the requirements CR_8 to CR_{11} from the experts I_{p_1} and I_{p_2} with regard to monitoring specifications. Although CR_9 and CR_{10} sound similar to CR_6 and CR_7 , we emphasize that they are not related to the analysis results. They describe the definition of a threshold that is mandatory to a monitoring specification as exclusion criteria for the observed artifacts or activities. In the following sections, we will create our modeling concept based on these requirements and make design decisions according to them.

4.2 Annotation-based Modeling in Domain Storytelling

A fundamental step in our concept is to annotate existing domain story elements to elicit the information required in the data model for RQA tests. In particular, annotating specific elements is important for the requirements CR_2 , CR_3 , and CR_8 as we have to determine a specific target for the RQA test. Further, it is important for CR_3 and CR_4 to determine the context for the RQA test with regard to a specific element. For instance, to determine the environment for a RQA test (see CR_4), we need to select a specific element first. Otherwise, it is not possible to determine its environment.

A vital aspect of annotations is to *attach* additional information to an element. Therefore, an annotation creates a relationship between the annotated element and the information declared in the annotation. This is similar to the usage of annotations in other modeling languages such as UML profiles, where the user adds additional information to a particular object to specify the object in more detail. Figure 4.1 shows a very simplified example of an annotation using MARTE.

However, using this kind of visual annotation as seen in Figure 4.1, domain stories would become confusing as soon as domain experts start to model multiple RQA tests on a single domain story. Nonetheless, we decided to use a modified approach of annotating elements by allowing domain experts to create RQA tests for specific domain story elements, i.e., for *actors*, *work objects*, and *activities*. We determined to separate the annotation into two components. The first component is the view where domain experts define the RQA test and determine the content of the annotation. The second component is the visual reference that distinguishes an annotated domain story element from the others.

At first, the domain expert selects a domain story element of interest for making an annotation in form of a RQA test. Then, a context menu shows several RQA tests available for the selected element. The mapping rules determine the availability of certain RQA tests on domain story elements (see Section 4.4). Next, the domain expert selects a RQA test. In our case, domain experts

Figure 4.1: Annotation of a sequence diagram using MARTE [LN]

Figure 4.2: Domain story with two annotated (complete and incomplete) elements

can decide between resilience tests, load tests, and monitoring specifications. Then, the GUI would open a separate view allowing to enter the information for the RQA test. When the domain expert presses the *save* button, the Domain Story Modeler checks if the annotation will be marked as complete or incomplete.

The visual reference on the domain story elements distinguishes between complete and incomplete annotations. A red border line surrounds incomplete annotations if the annotation misses mandatory information. Otherwise, a green border line indicates a completed annotation. Figure 4.2 shows an example of both visual references on the domain story *Entrance Control* (in german: *Einlasskontrolle*), where the work object *E-ticket* holds a complete annotation, and the actor *Employee App* holds an incomplete annotation.

Listing 4.1 EBNF of the RQA object

```

runtimeQualityAnalysis = resiliencetest, loadtest, monitoring .
resiliencetest = artifact, stimulus, environment, responseMeasure .
loadtest = artifact, stimulus, environment, responseMeasure .
monitoring = artifact, stimulus, environment, responseMeasure .

```

4.3 Description of the Data Model

Resilience tests, load tests, and other RQA specifications require different information and exist in many formats. For instance, ChaosToolkit [Chaa] allows providing specifications as either JSON or YAML. In contrast, JMeter [The19a] allows external configuration using the CLI, or a bash script. The report of analysis results also differs significantly. Since ChaosToolkit is a CLI tool, the report shows in the CLI output. However, ChaosToolkit offers to generate a PDF file with the analysis results. JMeter typically generates a Comma-separated Values (CSV) file for reporting the analysis results making it easier to process by other applications unlike the report generated by ChaosToolkit.

This inevitably leads to a large variety of data formats that we must consider for creating a data model. Therefore, it is in our interest that our prototype produces a data model to describe resilience tests, load tests, and monitoring specifications in a uniform manner. Throughout our concept and prototype implementation, we aim to hide as much technical complexity and terminology as possible from domain experts to reduce the cognitive load and increase usability. Though, this also means that must describe technical information in natural language. However, we have noticed that this is possible in some cases. Therefore, we have used supporting information text in our prototype to assist domain experts in understanding the information we request for our modeling concept (see Chapter 5).

For the structure of our data model, we use the scenario description template of ATAM [KKB+98]. This allows us to describe the content of RQA tests in a well-established structure according to the ATAM using predetermined keywords, i.e., *artifact*, *stimulus*, *environment*, and *response measure*. Previous works by Frank et al. [FHW+22] have already demonstrated that the ATAM scenario description is a well-established format to describe different quality attribute scenarios for different use cases. Therefore, we consider this a suitable approach to describe the data model for resilience tests, load tests, and monitoring specifications.

From our perspective and based on the experts' requirements, we used a parent node in our data model, called *runtimeQualityAnalysis* that contains three children for *resilience tests*, *load tests*, and *monitoring specifications*. Listing 4.1 shows the structure of the parent node using the Extended Backus-Naur Form (EBNF). The Domain Story Modeler produces the data model using the JSON format because dqualizer's interfaces will be built for accepting JSON formatted data. Thus, we ensured that the data model integrates well with the dqualizer ecosystem.

4.3.1 Resilience Test Data Model

Following the resilience test specification by ChaosToolkit [Chaa] as shown in Table 2.1, we must include the following information into our data model.

1. Target service
2. Fault type
3. fault repetition
4. Injection type
5. Steady-state-hypothesis
6. Duration
7. Execution context

In theory, a ChaosToolkit-based resilience test also requires declarative objects such as a title, a description in natural language, and a version number. However, for simplicity reasons, we assume that dqualizer automatically creates and appends this information to our data model before executing the resilience test. We have explained the information (1) to (7) in Table 2.1. As we try to hide as much technical information from the domain expert as possible we need to use alternate terminology for (1) to (7). Using the keywords of the scenario description template, we can assign (1) to (7) to our preliminary data model. For this purpose, we will assign (1) to (7) to the following keywords. We assign the (1) target service to the keyword *artifact* because this will be the object affected by the stimulus during execution. We assign the (2) fault type, the (3) fault repetition, the (4) injection type, and the (6) duration to the keyword *stimulus*. Further, we assign the (7) execution context to the keyword *environment* and the (5) steady-state hypothesis to the keyword *response measure*. Table 4.2 summarizes the mapping of the terminology of ChaosToolkit-based resilience tests and the ATAM keywords. The second column in Table 4.2 also shows a preliminary selection of alternative terms for the information of a ChaosToolkit-based resilience test. We have already mentioned that it will not be possible in every case to use an alternative terminology. However, in many such cases, the information will not be visible to the domain expert at least in the first iteration of a prototype, e.g., the injection type will be determined automatically depending on the type selected by the domain expert during the annotation. We point out that the alternative terms are just a preliminary choice to demonstrate our concept in a prototype. A future evaluation may find different terms that provide a better mapping than what we have chosen.

As a result, Listing 4.2 shows the EBNF for resilience tests. The EBNF shows that every resilience test consists of four components, i.e., artifact, stimulus, environment, and response measure. We have shown the assignment of the information in Table 4.2. Thus, we only explain the values the individual information fields can take on. The *artifact* stores the name of the annotated element that will be designated as the target for the *stimulus*. The *Type* in *stimulus* may be one out of three options, i.e., *Failed request*, *Late response*, and *Unavailable*. We decided to use these three options as they are the most used in ChaosToolkit for application-level fault injections [KHFH20]. Furthermore, we currently only consider application-level fault injection as it is the easiest to implement on the domain level. Other fault injection types such as infrastructure or network injection may require additional information that is not available in the domain story. As this requires more research, we determined that this is out of the scope of this work. However, for extensibility purposes we decided

ChaosToolkit	Alt. Terminology	ATAM Key Words
Fault type	Type	
Fault repetition	Occurrence	stimulus
Injection type	Injection type	
Duration	Confidence	
Target Service	artifact	artifact
Execution context	environment	environment
Steady-state-hypothesis	response measure	response measure

Table 4.2: Mapping the terminology of ChaosToolkit-based resilience tests to ATAM keywords

Listing 4.2 EBNF of a resilience test

```

resiliencetest = artifact, stimulus, environment, responseMeasure .
artifact = "Domain Story Element Name" .
stimulus = Type, InjectionType, Confidence, Occurrence.
Type = "Failed request" | "Late response" | "Unavailable" .
InjectionType = "Application" | "Infrastructure" | "Network" .
Confidence = 0..100 .
Occurrence = "Once" | "More than once" .
environment = Environment, Context .
Environment = "Testing" | "Production" .
Context = [DuringOfficeHours], [PostOfficeHours], [ExistingLoadTest] .
DuringOfficeHours = "08:00 am to 16:00 pm" .
PostOfficeHours = "After 16:00 pm" .
ExistingLoadTest = <LoadTest> .
LoadTest = loadtest . /* see EBNF for loadtest in Listing 4.3 */
responseMeasure = ResponseTime | RecoveryTime | ErrorRate .
ResponseTime = Satisfied | Tolerated | Frustrated .
RecoveryTime = Satisfied | Tolerated | Frustrated .
ErrorRate = None | Low | Medium | High .
None = "0" .
Low = "2.5" .
Medium = "5" .
High = "10" .
Satisfied = "1.2" .
Tolerated = "2.4" .
Frustrated = "4.8" .

```

to integrate the *injection type* information into our data model with the three options *Application*, *Infrastructure*, and *Network*. Therefore, the injection type will be set to *Application* by default as the *type* only lists application-level injections. By this, our data model satisfies the requirements CR1 (specify a *fault type*) and CR2 (declare a *target service*).

We identified an issue about determining the *duration* of a resilience test. We believe that it is not in the interest of the domain expert to provide a duration in form of minutes, hours, or the like. Furthermore, we have gathered evidence from experts that domain experts do not know to decide how long a RQA should take to achieve reliable results. Therefore, we decided to use the term *confidence* with a value between 0% a 100%. The domain experts select confidence that represents the reliability of their results. The higher the confidence the better the quality of the results. However, we need a determined time frame for executing a resilience test. At this point, we decided that this is a task for other dqualizer services to determine a suitable duration based on the selected confidence value. Furthermore, we think that in a future implementation the confidence may also result in multiple executions of one resilience test to get even better results instead of just executing the resilience test once for a long time. In a future version of dqualizer it should be possible for technical experts to store a configuration for the confidence that precisely defines the duration of a resilience test or how often a test should be repeated to achieve the desired level of confidence.

The *occurrence* determines how often the *stimulus* triggers against the *artifact*. At this point, we decided between two choices, i.e., *once* and *more than once*. In many resilience testing tools such as ChaosToolkit, it is common practice to randomly apply the *fault* to one or multiple services. For instance, an occurrence of *more than once* triggered for a single service instance of an *artifact* using a *failed request* results in multiple failing requests during the duration of the resilience test.

The *environment* differentiates between the execution environment, i.e., *Production* or *Testing*, and additional *context* information that is necessary in case the execution environment is *Testing*. In a testing environment, the application does not experience any workload. Therefore, it is necessary to provide additional context. Missing context information leads to non-representative data because there is no user behavior. A common approach in resilience testing is to use data from the production environment that reflects various usage patterns of application users between regular office hours and post office hours [BBR+16]. These two are considered in most cases by chaos engineers because they consider work times where engineers are available to fix any upcoming threads and emergency cases where engineers are typically not available. Depending on which of the two a domain expert selects, dqualizer retrieves appropriate load tests from the backend that represent the specified application usage pattern. By declaring the *environment*, our data model satisfies the requirement CR4.

Lastly, the *response measure* consists of three options, namely *Response time*, *Recovery time*, and the *Error rate*. Similar to the duration of a RQA test, we want to take the burden off domain experts to provide exact values. Also, the interviewed experts voiced that in most cases, domain experts do not have enough information to know the thresholds besides the ones stated in the Service Level Objective (SLO)s. However, this is not enough to make a precise conclusion on a suitable threshold for a *response measure*. At this point, we decided to use Apdex Levels of the Apdex Performance Index [Apd]. In our case, we have to use the Apdex Levels *Satisfied*, *Tolerated*, and *Frustrated* from the example provided by the Apdex Users Group. We believe that these three levels are understandable to domain experts but also they are considered industry standards according to the Apdex Users Group [Apd]. Following this example, we have used the same values for response

times and recovery rates of the Apdex Levels provided by the Apdex Users Group. The values for the three levels are examples and must be changed depending on the investigated domain. We determined that this will be implemented in a future iteration of dqualizer where a technical expert can save actual values for response and recovery times. Domain experts may then get information about the stored values in the Domain Story Modeler if they choose to do so. This way, it is not necessary to enter exact threshold values but at the same time, the data model considers the SLOs of the application. The *Error rates* object is separated into three Apdex Levels, namely *Low*, *Medium*, and *High*. The preliminary values for these Apdex Levels are shown in percentage. Thus, a *Medium* value for *Error rates* states to be below 5%. Lastly, we have added Apdex Level for *Error rates* called *None*. We consider this as suitable as there may be cases where a domain expert would like to verify that a certain operation does not result in any error.

In the end, our data model does not satisfy the requirement CR3. We have already elaborated that declaring a response object would require more research on how to display the information and how to transform the declared object into a valid response object. Furthermore, we would require more technical details that are not illustrated in a domain story. We consider this as a future work package that happens concurrently with implementing other fault-injection types such as infrastructure and network injections. As we have already applied the expert's feedback from the evaluation to our data model, the prototype does not reflect the data model shown in Listing 4.2. We have explicitly changed the naming of the values for the *Type* object. However, in that case, we have only changed the spelling of the values, e.g., the data model implemented in the prototype states *FAILED_REQUEST* instead of *Failed request*. Further, the prototype currently implements the *confidence* as *accuracy*. We have noticed that the term *accuracy* is confusing to the domain experts and that many of them have interpreted it as the *confidence* of a RQA test. Therefore, we have changed it accordingly in our data model. In the finalized data model, we have added the *InjectionType* for extensibility. However, the prototype does not consider the *InjectionType* so far. Lastly, the prototype in its current state does not implement sample values for the Apdex Levels for the *ResponseMeasure*. Currently, the prototype does not show any particular value for the Apdex Levels.

4.3.2 Load Test Data Model

During the requirements elicitation, we did not get detailed information about the contents of a load test or what domain expert typically know about its content. Table 4.1 only shows requirements related to monitoring specifications, resilience testing, or reporting the analysis results. Therefore, we have reviewed and discussed potential solutions for a data model in a separate dqualizer workshop. In Chapter 6 we discuss the expert's feedback on our data model and prototype concerning load tests. Prior to finalizing the data model, we have created a preliminary mapping of the terminology of JMeter [The19a] to the ATAM key words and provided an alternative terminology. Table 4.3 shows the result.

We assign four JMeter concepts to the *stimulus*, i.e., the *sampler*, and *loop count*. The *sampler* requires more configuration as there as a multitude of different samplers, e.g., HTTP, SOAP, and the like. We decided to consider HTTP samplers only since anything else would require more effort to distinguish the different samplers from each other. Moreover, this requires a detailed analysis of the application's architecture in case a domain expert decides to use a SOAP sampler. In that case, the mapping from the domain story to the software application would become difficult. However,

JMeter	Alt. Terminology	ATAM Key Words
sampler loop count	Sampling type Confidence	stimulus
Endpoint	artifact	artifact
number of threads ramp up	Base load / Highest load Growth rate	environment
assertion	response measure	response measure

Table 4.3: Mapping the terminology of JMeter-based resilience tests to ATAM keywords

due to the limited scope of our work, we will postpone this issue to future work packages similar to enabling multi-level fault injection in resilience tests. The *loop count* perfectly fits into our definition of the *confidence* which we have elaborated earlier.

We assigned the concept of an *endpoint* to the *artifact* and assigned the *assertion* rules to the *response measure*. In general, it is possible to create multiple endpoints in JMeter that will be affected by the stimulus, e.g., an HTTP request. However, this information can not be elicited on the domain story as we can only observe the high level domain model and not specific implementation details of the model itself. For example, one *activity* in the domain story may be part of multiple HTTP requests. This requires detailed information about the technical implementation which impedes the simplicity of our concept. Therefore, we determined to hide this complexity from the domain experts by only selecting one artifact by which dqualizer will determine the appropriate HTTP endpoint. We have elaborated this concept in Section 4.5.

Further, we assign the concepts *number of threads*, and the *ramp up* time to the ATAM key word *environment*. As an alternative description of the *number of threads*, we decided to use two different terms that apply to the model at different cases. The first one is the *Highest load* which applies when there happens a change in the workload after a dedicated time frame which is defined by the *Growth rate*. The second one, i.e., *Base load* only applies when the workload does not change during the load test, i.e., it remains static.

In the end, we have defined the data model shown in Listing 4.3. In the following, we do not discuss the objects that have similar semantics to the objects in the resilience test data model. In particular that relates to *confidence*, *artifact*, and *ResponseTime*. The latter includes the three Apdex Levels as they are semantically equal to the Apdex Levels we have defined in the resilience data model. Again, we emphasize that the Apdex Levels can be changed in a future version of dqualizer as the value for each level depends on the application's actual data and the defined SLOs.

According to the mapping shown in Table 4.3, the *stimulus* consists of two objects, i.e., the *SamplingType* and the *Confidence*. We have already explained that we only consider the HTTP sampler for our purposes. Therefore, the *SamplingType* can only take on one value. Future versions of dqualizer may add more types. The *environment* consists of a multilevel object, i.e., the *LoadProfile*. The *LoadProfile* determines how the load is applied to the *artifact* and allows different configurations. The *Type* is an information which we believe will be relevant for dqualizer in a future version. At this moment, we differentiate between two load types, i.e., *Load peak*, and

Listing 4.3 EBNF of a load test

```

loadtest = artifact, stimulus, environment, responseMeasure .
artifact = "Domain Story Element Name" .
stimulus = SamplingType, Confidence .
SamplingType = "HTTP" .
Confidence = 0..100 .
environment = LoadProfile .
LoadProfile = Type, BaseLoad, GrowthRate, HighestLoad .
Type = "Load peak" | "Continuous load" .
BaseLoad = Low | Medium | High .
GrowthRate = "Linear" | "Cubic" | "Quadratic" .
HighestLoad = Very high | Extremely high | Dangerously high .
responseMeasure = ResponseTime, [ResultMetric] .
ResponseTime = Satisfied | Tolerated | Frustrated .
ResultMetric = ["Response Times"], ["90th Percentile"], ["95th Percentile"] .
None = "0" .
Low = 5000 .
Medium = 10000 .
Very High = 15000 .
Extremely High = 25000 .
Dangerously High = 50000 .
Satisfied = "1.2" .
Tolerated = "2.4" .
Frustrated = "4.8" .

```

a *Continuous load*. Both types are common load patterns occurring in many other contexts, such as Cloud Computing where they describe them as workload patterns [FLR+14]. In their work, Frank et al. [FHW+22] discuss the occurrence of load peaks in the taxing domain that happen at well-known times. Therefore, we consider both types are meaningful and sufficient for a first approach to describe a data model. The *Type* determines if dqualizer has to use the value *Highest load* in addition to the *Base Load*. Otherwise, only the *BaseLoad* will be used to describe the *thread group* in JMeter.

The *BaseLoad* separates into three Apdex Levels, i.e., *Low*, *Medium*, and *High*. We have added preliminary values to each Apdex Level for demonstration purposes. We have already elaborated why we did this. Similar, the *Highest load* divides into three Apdex Levels as well, namely *Very High*, *Extremely High*, *Dangerously High*. We have used three different descriptions for the Apdex Levels because we believe that it should be obvious for domain experts that the *Highest load* is significantly higher than the *BaseLoad*. The values for the Apdex Levels related to the *Highest load* and *BaseLoad* are sample values that illustrate the number of concurrent requests an application experiences. It is up to the technical experts to declare appropriate values in dqualizer with regard to existing monitoring data. Furthermore, it will be possible to declare in which intervals these requests occur.

The last component of the *stimulus* is the *Growth rate*. According to our mapping in Table 4.3, the *Growth rate* determines the *ramp up* time of JMeter. As of now, the *Growth rate* can take three values, i.e., *Linear*, *Cubic*, and *Quadratic*. We have decided to use these based on our own experiences during a dqualizer workshop and based on the experts feedback during the prototype evaluation. In its current state, our data model does not calculate the *ramp up* time on its own. However, we determined that dqualizer will use the value of the *Growth rate* to apply a factor to the declared load (*Base load* or *Highest load*) to modify the gradient of the workload. By that, dqualizer will calculate based on the processed gradient.

The *Response measure* consists of the *ResponseTime* and an optional object called *ResultMetric*. The first is semantically equal to the *ResponseTime* in the resilience test data model. The latter describes a range of metrics that may be included into the analysis results report. We have included the metrics *Response Times*, and two percentiles, i.e., the *90th* and the *95th* into the *ResultMetric* object according to the requirements CR₆ and CR₇. By including these metrics, we also satisfy CR₅.

In the end, we have made the following changes to the data model currently implemented in our prototype. Similar to the Apdex Levels of the resilience test data model, the load test data model does not consider actual values for the *LoadProfile* as well as for the *ResponseMeasure*. This has also been criticized by the experts since it complicates the design of load tests. Furthermore, we have changed the description of the Apdex Levels of *HighestLoad* from *High*, *Very High*, and *Extremely High* to the ones shown in Listing 4.3. We perceived that the Apdex Levels of do not separate the *HighestLoad* from the *BaseLoad* strictly enough. Therefore, we have changed them to make a more strict separation and emphasize the difference in the workload. We have made noticeable changes to the structure of the data model. The finalized data model shown in Listing 4.3 assigns the *LoadProfile* to the *environment* and does not differentiate the execution context. In the prototype's data model, we have assigned the *LoadProfile* to the *stimulus* and added a default value (*Testing*) for the environment. Furthermore, we have added the *SamplingType* to the data model for similar purposes we added the *InjectionType* for resilience tests. We have also changed the *accuracy* to *confidence*. We have explained this change previously in context of the resilience testing data model.

4.3.3 Monitoring Specification

According to the expert's feedback, a concise data model for monitoring specifications requires too much technical information that can not be elicited on the domain level. Furthermore, the experts have stated that from it does not make sense to create a monitoring on the domain level as the domain model represented in a domain story does not offer to elicit the information required by a monitoring specification. In addition, they experts voiced that it is impossible to phrase the technical contents of a monitoring specification in a natural language similar to what we did with resilience and load tests. However, for integrity purposes, we provide the information we have gathered until this point to give a conceptualized view on the data model for a monitoring specification. Furthermore, we will also considered the requirements we have elicited so far.

Thus, Listing 4.4 shows a conceptual approach for a monitoring data model. The parent node of a monitoring is similar to the other data models, i.e., it consists of an *artifact*, a *stimulus*, the *environment*, and *response measure*. However, we have figured that the *artifact* must be interpreted

Listing 4.4 EBNF of a monitoring specification

```

monitoring = artifact, stimulus, environment, responseMeasure .
artifact = <artifact> | "Domain Story Element Name" .
stimulus = Trigger .
Trigger = <artifact>, <TriggerCondition> .
TriggerCondition = "Condition" .
Confidence = 0..100 .
environment = Environment .
Environment = "PRODUCTION" .
responseMeasure = ResponseTime, <Metric> .
Metric = "Execution time" | "Count" .
ResponseTime = Satisfied | Tolerated | Frustrated .
Satisfied = "1.2" .
Tolerated = "2.4" .
Frustrated = "4.8" .

```

differently. In the context of a resilience or load test, the artifact represents the service, component, or subsystem that will be affected by a stimulus. As a monitoring does not have a stimulus that has an effect on the *artifact*, we decided to structure the *artifact* differently by allowing to store multiple domain story elements a monitoring tool observes over a dedicated duration. According to the experts statements in the elicitation interviews, the most common artifact is an HTTP endpoint selected for observation. However, we have discussed the issue of retrieving HTTP endpoints on the domain level, but we suggested to acquire these information in other dqualizer services. However, similar to the other data models, we assume that dqualizer is capable of retrieving this information. Thus, we consider the requirement CR₈ as satisfied in our data model.

The *stimulus* in a monitoring contains only one object, i.e., a *trigger*. As its name implies, a trigger will cause something else to happen, e.g., a rollback mechanism or similar. Unfortunately, we did not elicit potential actions that may be defined after the condition of a trigger is met.

In the scope of a separate dqualizer workshop, we have identified that a monitoring specification requires information similar to resilience and load tests, i.e., one or multiple (observation) targets (*artifact*), and a metric (*response measure*). In contrast to our other data models, a monitoring specification requires a trigger. A trigger causes something else to happen when a (trigger) condition has been met by the observed artifact or artifacts. Unfortunately, we did not elicit potential actions that occur when the trigger condition has been met. For completeness, we have added a *TriggerCondition* symbol in EBNF notation to the *Trigger* that contains a string value as a placeholder. The *TriggerCondition* may be added in a future iteration of our work.

Similar to the resilience test and load test data model, we have the *Confidence* with a value between 0% and 100%. In the previous sections, we have elaborated how we can leverage the *Confidence* as a measure for the duration. Thus, we do not discuss this again. Nonetheless, we consider the requirement CR₁₁ to be satisfied. Further, we have assumed that a monitoring almost always applies in a production environment. Therefore, we have assumed a default value for the *environment*. Lastly, we define the *responseMeasure* with two objects, namely *ResponseTime* and *Metric*. From

the experiences of our dqualizer workshop, we know that typical metrics are the *Execution time* of a piece of code and the total number of executions called *Count*. We know that there exist more metrics of interest but lacking the information and data. We leave this for future work packages to extend the metrics. The *ResponseTime* consists of three Apdex Levels similar to the *ResponseTime* of the other data models. Thus, the specification of a *responseMeasure* inevitably satisfied the requirement CR₉ since it allows us to specify a threshold for response times of observed HTTP endpoints (artifacts).

In the end, we were not able to satisfy CR₁₀ due to the lack of information from experts. However, we are convinced that we have created a meaningful preliminary data model for monitoring specifications that serves as a suitable extension to our prototype. Unfortunately, we were not capable to implement this data model into our prototype due to time constrains. We consider this to be part of a future work package.

4.3.4 Analysis Results

The analysis results are a fundamental part of our concept as it makes the process of creating and executing RQA tests on the domain level complete. A suitable solution to P3 for reporting the analysis results has to consider two concerns. First, we need to ensure that the analysis result report contains enough information in order to make the result comprehensible to the domain expert. Second, we need to display the analysis results in a readable manner for domain experts. Tools such as Grafana display data in graph-like visualizations. However, as we have identified during the elicitation (see Chapter 3), it happens that domain experts do not have the necessary knowledge to derive a conclusion from these reports. Thus, we have to ensure that the analysis report integrates the data in a suitable manner.

In Section 2.2 we explained that the work by Okanović et al. [OHZ+19] established a valuable solution for our problem P3 which we stated in Chapter 1. Although, Okanović et al. [OHZ+19] proposed their solution in a different context, we figured that it is a well-fit solution for our context as the authors had a similar intention. Therefore, we decided to use a modified version of the report generator by Okanović et al. [OHZ+19] in our concept for reporting analysis results on the domain level. However, we have to emphasize that the results of RQA tools can vary significantly. For instance, ChaosToolkit is currently not able to deliver its results in a JSON format but rather as a PDF file. In contrast, JMeter typically provides its results as a CSV file. However, since the calculation and aggregation of the analysis results is out of scope of this work, we assume that dqualizer implements a suitable service that performs these tasks automatically. Thus, in our concept we only consider the reporting of the analysis results after they have been aggregated and formatted by dqualizer.

Similar to the report generator by Okanović et al. [OHZ+19], the result report is made up of two components. The first component is the summary statement. As the name suggests, the summary statement summarizes the details of the RQA that have been modeled prior to the execution of the test. We have demonstrated an example using the contents of a resilience test data model in the box below. The summary allows domain experts to get an overview of the previously modeled RQA test in one view. This becomes especially important, if we consider that the execution of one or more RQA tests may take several hours or days. Therefore, it may occur that domain experts have forgotten the details of the tests they have specified.

Summary statement: We executed the resilience test with the stimulus **Failed request** using ChaosToolkit, in the environment **TESTING**. You stated that the test should be executed **during regular office hours, i.e., between 08:00 am and 16:00 pm**. You also added **existing load tests to simulate real user behavior**. The stimulus was repeated **once**. The test results should have an Accuracy of **56%**. As a hypothesis you stated that the **Error rate** should be **low**.

The second component is the conclusion statement. This last component, draws a conclusion from the analysis results by showing actual values from the results. The grey text box below shows an excerpt of an conclusion statement with regard to the results of a resilience test data model. The conclusion statement includes details of the RQA test run in natural language using selected technical metrics that are related to the *response measure* declared in the modeled RQA test. This enables domain experts to get a direct relationship between the *response measure* and the actual result. Depending on the actual result, the conclusion statement declares that the test run was either successful in case the actual result is lower than the threshold specified in the *response measure*, or declares the test run as failed otherwise.

Conclusion statement: Sadly, your experiment was not successful!. The hypothesis did not hold because the error rate was higher than the measure you specified.

Since our concept allows to execute multiple RQA tests, it occurs that multiple analysis results display at once. For this purpose, the report separates the view using headlines for *Resilience Test Results* and *Load Test Results*. Considering the user experience it may be best to use a better separation elements in the GUI, e.g., separation lines or dropdown menus to reduce the cognitive overload of reporting more than one test result in one view.

4.4 Mapping Rules

As a part of our concept, we need well-defined rules that allow dqualizer to transform the annotated domain models into RQA tests based on the data models shown in Listing 4.2, Listing 4.3, and Listing 4.4. For this purpose, we have explained the tactical design patterns of DDD and how domain stories can be implemented according to Hofer and Schwentner [HS21] in Section 2.1. The mapping rules assist dqualizer in finding missing information for the transformation process.

Listing 4.5 shows an excerpt of sample mapping rules about the domain story *Entrance Control*. We have attached the domain story in Appendix B.2. Note, that for this demonstration we have translated the contents of the domain story into English. The mapping rules contain three items, namely *work objects*, *activities*, and *actors* where each of them has an array of items. For instance, *work objects* has an array of work objects, *activities* has an array of activities, and so on. Next, each item in a category holds additional information that describes its relationship to its implemented pendant. In general, we distinguish between *classes* that represent either a work object or an actor, *class variables* that may represent a work object, and *methods* that represent activities. We emphasize that mapping of domain story elements on Java keywords is an example according to the rules by Vernon [Ver17]. We do not discuss alternative mappings to other programming languages or architecture elements as this would require more research and is not in the scope of this work.

Listing 4.5 Description of mapping rules 1 of 2

```
"mapping":
  {
    "work objects": [
      "E-Ticket": {
        "implemented as": "Class",
      }
      "Movie": {
        "implemented as": "Class",
      },
      "playtime": {
        "implemented as": "Instance Variable",
      }
      "available seats": {
        "implemented as": "Instance Variable",
      },
      "cinema auditorium": {
        "implemented as": "Class",
      }
    ],
    "activities": [
      "shows": {
        "implemented as": "Method",
      },
      "validates": {
        "implemented as": "Method",
      },
      "opens": {
        "implemented as": "Method",
      },
      "returns": {
        "implemented as": "Method"
      }
    ]
  }
}
```

The first item in *work objects* in Listing 4.5 is *E-Ticket*. The *E-Ticket* item has the property *implemented as*. This property describes whether the work object is implemented as a class, instance variable, or method. The *work object's* item *playing time* has been implemented as a class property. The first item in *activities* is *zeigt* which is implemented as a method.

Listing 4.6 Description of mapping rules 2 of 2

```
"mapping": {
  "actors": [
    "Employee": {
      "implemented as": "Class",
    },
    "Cinema visitor": {
      "implemented as": "Class",
    },
    "Employee App": {
      "implemented as": "Class",
    }
  ],
}
```

4.5 Workflow

In the following, we demonstrate how our concept applies in the context of `dqualizer` from start to end. For demonstration purposes, we only consider the happy path, thus, ignoring potential edge cases or errors that may occur in between the steps. Furthermore, we assume that we use the finalized data models which we have introduced in this chapter and not the data models that are currently implemented in our prototype. Before we start, we must distinguish between the following two cases.

Case 1: The organization and project teams do not use DDD, thus, the application under test does not implement tactical design patterns.

In *Case 1*, the organization which would like to use `dqualizer` does not follow the DDD methodology nor does the application under test implement tactical design patterns such as entities, and value objects to reflect the organization's domain model. Unfortunately, this makes it impossible to use our modeling concept and `dqualizer` to model and run RQA tests. It is possible to use the Domain Story Modeler for the purpose of creating domain stories as a first step towards establishing DDD in the organization. However, we do not concern about proceeding in this case since it does not suit our demonstration.

Case 2: The organization and project teams live to the DDD methodology and successfully implemented tactical design patterns within the system's architecture using entities, and value objects.

This is the ideal state of an organization and business application to make our modeling concept and `dqualizer` applicable. At this point, we need to make some more assumptions about the setting since a demonstration of a complete workflow requires much more data than we have currently available. First, we assume that there exists at least one valid domain story that illustrates one process. Second, we assume that the developers have used OOP for implementing the business application, e.g., by using Java as a programming language.

Figure 4.3: A possible system context diagram of dqualizer

4.5.1 System Context

At this point, we make some assumptions about the system context of the Domain Story Modeler and dqualizer. Figure 4.3 illustrates a potential system context of both components. For our purpose, we assume that the domain experts use ChaosToolkit for resilience tests, and JMeter for running load tests in their application. ChaosToolkit and JMeter are considered state-of-the-art and well-established tools for their purpose, thus, we consider them suitable for a demonstration of our modeling concept. However, in future iterations dqualizer may be connected to other tools as well.

First, we view the dqualizer application, ChaosToolkit, and JMeter as black boxes. This gives us the chance to ignore any details on how dqualizer or the other tools perform data handling. The Domain Story Modeler connects to dqualizer using two dedicated message queues, namely Queue q_1 and Queue q_2 . Following this principle, dqualizer communicates to ChaosToolkit and JMeter through the message queues Queue q_3 and Queue q_4 . From our point of view it is irrelevant how these components communicate with each other. Therefore, other means that promote service communication apply in this context as well. However, we decided to use message-based communication as we believe that dqualizer as a whole will be designed for message-based communication.

4.5.2 Determine the Mapping

To make the transformation work, we assumed that the Domain Story Modeler retrieved the mapping rules in memory. Further, we assumed that we use the mapping rules for the domain story *Entrance Control* (in German: Einlasskontrolle) as shown in Listing 4.5 and Listing 4.6.

4.5.3 Modeling RQA Tests

For brevity reasons, we assumed that an appropriate domain story has been imported into the Domain Story Modeler by a domain expert. In a real scenario, the domain expert selects a bounded context in the Domain Story Modeler which requests the domain story and mapping rules from dqualizer. The mapping rules allow the Domain Story Modeler to determine on which elements a resilience test, load test, or monitoring is possible. We assume that the domain expert models two RQA tests, i.e., a resilience test and a load test. The incentive to model a RQA test also requires a business question. For now, we consider $Q_{resilience}$ as our business question for a resilience test,

Listing 4.7 Example configuration for *Q_{resilience}*

```

"resiliencetest:" [
  {
    "artifact": "Employee App",
    "stimulus": [
      "Type": "Failed request",
      "Injection type": "Application",
      "Confidence": 100%,
      "Occurrence": "More than once"
    ],
    "environment": [
      "Environment": "Production",
      "Context": [{
        "After 16:00 pm"
      }]
    ],
    "responseMeasure": [
      "Error rate": "Low"
    ]
  }
]

```

and *Q_{load}* as our business question for creating a load test. We will use actual values and questions from domain experts which we have elicited in other dqualizer workshops for *Q_{resilience}* and *Q_{load}* to demonstrate that our approach works for real use cases.

Q_{resilience}: As a domain expert, I would like to know if the error rate of verifying an E-Ticket in my Employee App is below 5% when the validation process for E-Ticket's fails in the Employee App.

Q_{load}: As a domain expert, I would like to know if my Employee App can handle an extremely high load peak for validating E-Tickets.

In the Domain Story Modeler, the domain expert selects the *Employee App* to create the resilience tests. In contrast, the domain expert decides to select the *validiert* activity for a load test. At this point, we do not demonstrate the domain expert's navigation through the Domain Story Modeler's UI. We emphasize that there are many possible configurations to approach a solution for *Q_{resilience}* and *Q_{load}*. However, we do not want to emphasize on a possible exploration of multiple configurations but focus on a single modelling and execution process. We assume that the domain expert saved two configurations for valid models to solve *Q_{resilience}* and *Q_{load}*.

Listing 4.7 shows the configuration for *Q_{resilience}*. We assume that the domain expert selected the *Employee App* as the artifact for the resilience test. The stimulus describes a *Failed request* since the objective is to verify the error rates of validating an E-Ticket. The domain expert expects a *confidence* of 100%. Due to insecurity of the domain expert, the test runs in a testing environment for now. Further the stimulus occurs *More than once* at the artifact. Since the test runs in a testing

Listing 4.8 Example configuration for *Q_{load}*

```
"loadtest": [
  {
    "artifact": "validiert",
    "stimulus": {
      "Sampling type": "HTTP",
      "Confidence": 100%,
    },
    "environment": {
      "Load Profile": {
        "Type": "Load peak",
        "Base load": "Low",
        "Growth rate": "Linear"
        "Highest load": "Dangerously high",
      }
    },
    "responseMeasure": [
      "Response time": "Satisfied"
      "ResultMetris": [
        "Response times"
      ]
    ],
  }
]
```

environment, the domain expert must provide further context information. We assume that most customers go to the movies past regular office hours, i.e., after 16 : 00 pm. At last the domain expert defines the error rate to be *Low*. Thus, the total error rate must be below 5%. Upon pressing the save button, the Domain Story Modeler persists the configuration as seen in Listing 4.7.

Lastly, Listing 4.8 shows the configuration for *Q_{load}*. In this case, the domain expert selected the *validated* activity as the artifact of the test. The stimulus describes a *Load peak* and expects confidence of 100%. The load profile has the following properties. The highest load is set to be *Dangerously high* and the growth rate describes *Linear* gradient. The domain expert assumes that the *Employee App* is quite robust and figures to set the response measure for the application's response time to be *Satisfied*. Lastly, he expects in the analysis results a report about the *Response times*.

4.5.4 Executing the RQA Tests

We have illustrated a detailed process of the execution in Figure 4.4. The domain expert executes the modeled RQA test by pressing the *execute* button in the Domain Story Modeler. At this point, the application sends the configuration to *dqualizer* to find additional information and execute the tests.

Figure 4.4: Activities involved in the execution of an RQA test

The Domain Story Modeler loads the configurations from its storage and pushes them to the message queue q_1 . Since *dqualizer* subscribes to q_1 , it pulls the configurations from the queue eventually. Unfortunately, ChaosToolkit and JMeter can not process the configuration files in their current state because of two reasons. First, they are missing relevant information that we are not capable to elicit on the domain level, e.g., HTTP endpoints. Second, they need to be formatted correctly to be processed by both tools.

For demonstration purposes, we assume that *dqualizer* already implements the services *dqmapping* and *dqtranslator*. *dqmapping* is responsible for finding missing information in the system's implementation and attaching this information to the data model using the mapping rules. *dqtranslator* is responsible for transforming the data model into a readable format for ChaosToolkit and JMeter. This includes the transformation of the information in the data model into the concepts of ChaosToolkit and JMeter. We have demonstrated in Table 4.2 and Table 4.3 how a transformation works. *dqtranslator* may use these tables for the transformation process. When the processed configuration files arrive at the end of our process, ChaosToolkit and JMeter execute the tests according to our specifications. When the tests have achieved the desired confidence, both tools report their analysis results back to *dqualizer*. We assume that *dqualizer* is capable of aggregating and transforming the analysis results into a computer-readable format using *dqtranslator*. Then, *dqualizer* pushes the analysis results to the message queue q_2 on which the Domain Story Modeler subscribed. The Domain Story Modeler then pulls the analysis results from q_2 eventually. In the end, the Domain Story Modeler processes the analysis results and creates a view for the domain expert which he can access by pressing the button *Show results*. The text boxes below show an excerpt of the analysis report according to the format we specified in Section 5.6.5.

Load Test Result: We executed the **Load peak** test for the artifact **validates** with the tool JMeter in the environment **Testing**. the load peak was set to **Dangerously high**. The growth rate was set to **fast**. You stated that the request's response times should be **satisfied** during the load test in order to be successful. The test results should have a confidence of **100%**. The calculated average response time of the load test was 2x faster than the specified threshold! Therefore, your system's specifications are satisfied!

Resilience Test Result: We executed the resilience test with the stimulus **Failed request** using ChaosToolkit, in the environment **Testing** for the artifact **Employee App**. You stated that the test should be executed **after 16:00 pm**. You also added **existing load tests to simulate real user behavior**. The stimulus was repeated **more than once**. The test results should have a confidence of **100%**. As a hypothesis you stated the **error rate** to be **satisfied**. Sadly, your experiment was not successful!. The hypothesis did not hold because the error rate was higher than the measure you specified.

From the results, the domain expert can directly determine that the load test was successful since the response times were in the specified range. Whereas the resilience test failed because the actual error rate was higher than what he specified in the configuration.

5 Prototype Development

This chapter explains our development process for implementing our modeling concept into the Domain Story Modeler. We showcase the GUI for modeling the RQA tests and how domain experts can navigate through the Domain Story Modeler using our prototype.

Thus, this chapter is structured as follows. Section 5.1 shows the drafts, we created and the beginning of this work to get a first impression of a potential interface. Section 5.2 elaborates the requirements from the expert interviews that are relevant to our prototype. Section 5.3 explains how we setup our development environment and which tools we have used to develop the prototype. Section 5.4 itemizes the most important technologies and programming languages we used for the prototype. Section 5.5 shows how our modeling concept integrates in the existing ecosystem of the Domain Story Modeler. Section 5.6 enumerates the GUI for the individual RQA tests. Lastly, Section 5.7 explains future extensions to the Domain Story Modeler based on our requirements backlog.

5.1 Drafts of Modeling Concept

In the context of the requirements elicitation, we have created drafts of a preliminary GUI for our modeling concept. We have elaborated that this was a substantial part of our elicitation method (see Section 3.4.1). The prototype illustrations assisted us in receiving the first impression of the expert's behavior and usage pattern regarding our modeling concept. Furthermore, the drafts served as guidance for implementing our modeling concept. In our drafts, we have used icons from material.io¹ but changed them afterward (see Section 5.3).

Figure 5.1 shows the first draft of the GUI with regard to a drag-and-drop feature and describing the RQA tests. We decided to use drag-and-drop for the RQA elements because we wanted to stay consistent with the features of the Domain Story Modeler. On the Modeler's canvas, every element can be moved onto the canvas by drag-and-drop. The Domain Story Modeler shows an icon panel on the left that contains the work objects and actors for a potential domain story. We wanted to create a separate icon panel apart from the domain story elements to avoid potential confusion among the users. Furthermore, we did not want to mix concerns by adding RQA related icons among work objects and actors. We had the idea to drop an RQA icon next to a domain story element to create a relationship between the domain story element and a RQA test through proximity. Visual proximity is a common design pattern that allows the establishment of a visual relationship between two elements [WC95]. Furthermore, our idea contributes to our goal of creating annotation-based modeling that relates to UML annotations where the annotated information is attached directly to the element. Lastly, clicking on a RQA icon opens a context menu similar to the other domain story elements.

¹<https://material.io/>

Figure 5.1: Draft of the icon panel, input menu, and runtime analysis summary pre execution

In the drafts we did not include actual input fields for collecting information. However, we intended to use native input fields for entering information such as *loop count* and *type of error*. We intended to include supporting text documentation on the input fields in the context menu to better support the user in the modeling process. On the top right, we intended to show a separate view for summarizing the modeled RQA tests. A summary view is common in many shop applications to verify that all steps have been correctly executed, e.g., Amazon shows a summary view before checking out an order.

Furthermore, a summary view reduces the effort to verify the content of the modeled RQA tests. In the beginning, we thought to include a visual reference showing the completeness of a modeled RQA test. We figured that a colored highlight of the icon is appropriate to indicate whether a test has been fully specified (grey outline) or lacks mandatory information (grey outline with a red question mark). Form fields in other applications use visual references to highlight mandatory input fields if they have been left out. We apply the same pattern not only on input fields but also on the icons on the domain story. Thus, a user does not have to open the context menu to verify that something has been left out.

Figure 5.1 shows an alternative idea for displaying the analysis results. Instead of using color codes as outlines of the icons themselves, we figured that it would be possible to simply add additional icons for successful analysis results (green check) or failed results (red cross). This achieves the same objective as a color outline of the icon's border. A separate view would show a summary of the analysis results with an indication of the result.

We emphasize that these were drafts of a potential GUI. In the end, we did not apply all of the concepts of our drafts. However, we explained which features we decided to not use and which ones we implemented from our drafts in Section 5.6.

Figure 5.2: Draft of the runtime analysis results view

5.2 Prototype Requirements

This section enumerates the requirements relevant to the development of our prototype. Table 5.1 shows the list of requirements that we determined to contain information with regard to technical features such as implementing particular views or buttons. The table consists of three columns similar to Table 4.1 that shows the ID, a description, and the source of each requirement. Further, we have used the user story template according to Alliance [All18] for describing the requirements. We perceive the requirements of Table 5.1 different from the modeling concept requirements mainly because they describe a technical feature rather than a conceptual one. However, we emphasize that the modeling concept requirements did contain important information that we had to consider for implementing the prototype. For instance, CR1 to CR4 of Table 4.1 describe to specify the fault injection type, the environment, and a fault injection target. Although, these information were relevant for describing the data model of our modeling concept, we derived technical requirements from CR1, CR2, CR3, and CR4. Moreover, all elicited requirements were broken down into smaller, implementable tasks since they only described a concept or technical feature on a high level. Unfortunately, this would have led to many task descriptions that we did not want to include in this work for brevity reasons. Therefore, we only discuss an excerpt of the prototype requirements that were explicitly stated by the experts during the interviews. Any smaller task that we have created from the prototype or modeling concept requirements were added to our project management tool ZenHub².

A majority of the prototype requirements relate to implementing different views for distinct concerns. The requirements PR_{1,1} to PR_{1,3} describe that the prototype should have separate views for each RQA test type, i.e., resilience test, load tests, and monitoring specifications. Similarly, I_{p1} and WT_{p1} voiced the need for a summary view in PR₂ as a means to have a summary of all previously modeled RQA test in one view. This would significantly improve the user experience, as domain experts would not have to click on every annotation to see what they have created before. Furthermore, two experts have stated in PR₄ to require a separate view that contains the analysis results. WT_{p1} argued that this view should be separate from the modeling views to reduce the cognitive load on the user.

²<https://www.zenhub.com/>

ID	Description	Source
PR _{1.1}	As a domain expert interested in runtime quality analysis , I would like to have a separate view for resilience tests to focus on one test specification	WT _{p1}
PR _{1.2}	As a domain expert interested in runtime quality analysis , I would like to have a separate view for load tests to focus on one test specification	
PR _{1.3}	As a domain expert interested in runtime quality analysis , I would like to have a separate view for monitoring specifications to focus on one test specification	
PR ₂	As a domain expert interested in runtime quality analysis , I would like to summarize multiple tests to get a better overview of already modeled tests	I _{p1} , WT _{p1}
PR ₃	As a domain expert interested in runtime quality analysis , I would like to be assisted with supporting text on the runtime quality analysis tests to get a better understanding of the required information	I _{p1} , WT _{p1} , WT _{p2}
PR ₄	As a domain expert interested in runtime quality analysis results , I would like to have a view that shows the received analysis results to make an interpretation from the received results	I _{p1} , WT _{p1}

Table 5.1: Requirements that describe technical features for our prototype

A very important information has been given by three experts who explained that they consider it as a vital criteria to have supporting information text on the UI elements that require some input from the user (see PR₄). However, they did not give us any examples for supporting information text nor what kind of input seems to raise the most confusion from their point of view.

We presumed that each requirement that states the need for a particular view required a corresponding UI element to open that view, e.g., a button or similar. Thus, we did not consider it as necessary to include additional requirements for implementing smaller UI elements in Table 5.1. However, they have been included in the task list as a guidance for our implementation process.

5.3 Development Environment and Method

The development environment consisted of two parts. First, we created a git repository for version control. And second, we setup our local development environment using an Integrated Development Environment (IDE). In the git repository, we created a fork from the original Domain Story Modeler since we did not have the necessary access rights. The git repository is a part of the dqualizer GitHub organization and can be accessed under the following link: <https://github.com/dqualizer/domain-story-modeler-thesis>. In the dqualizer GitHub organization, we use ZenHub as our own project management tool to create and track issues with regard to the Domain Story Modeler and other dqualizer related repositories. In a first iteration, we have migrated the prototype requirements written in Table 5.1 into our ZenHub board. In a second iteration, we prioritized the requirements according to their complexity and the time required to implement them into our prototype. We did not use ticket estimations or similar since this was not suitable for the scope of our work. We attempted to split the requirements into smaller tasks, after we prioritized them. As this was quite time consuming, we decided to not write out similar tasks for each requirement. For instance, implementing a view for resilience tests and load tests according to PR_{1.1} and PR_{1.2} required to

have a button that opens both views. In this case, we did not write two individual tasks but created one task for both requirements. We have phrased the tasks as user stories similar to the prototype and modeling concept requirements. In addition, we have added acceptance criteria for each task to determine when a task has finished.

It is considered best practice in software engineering to create a new branch for every user story. These feature branches were merged into the master branch when all tests were successful. Thus, we followed these conventions but we created a separate main branch apart from the master branch. We figured it is best to keep the master branch clean at all costs and only merge our feature branches into the main branch until this work has finished. After finishing a user story according to its acceptance criteria, we merged the branch into the main branch.

We have used Microsoft Visual Studio Code as our IDE due to personal preference. We remark that the selection of the IDE does not influence the behavior of the application. Thus, we decided to use the IDE that is best known to us. During implementation we have not used of any specific IDE plugins besides code formatting or code highlighting. To the best of our efforts, we followed the Javascript code conventions from Google³ using the ESLint plugin.

5.4 Technologies

The Domain Story Modeler runs as a basic web application inside the browser using plain Javascript, HTML and Cascading Style Sheets (CSS). For our purposes, we did not make any changes to the underlying technologies or remove any dependency that has been included in the Domain Story Modeler package.json. However, we introduced two libraries to the project. First, we included the bootstrap⁴ library to access pre-styled components such as Buttons, Cards, and other layouts. Second, we have used the bootstrap-icons⁵ library for including icons with regard to displaying the RQA tests. As the Domain Story Modeler does not use any framework, we decided to not use on either as this would have required extensive migration of the existing code base. This has the advantage that the impediment of having framework-related issues is low. Furthermore, we did not have to learn any framework-specific concepts or other technologies in order to implement our modeling concept.

During development, we have executed the Domain Story Modeler using the build-in NPM scripts to start the application locally in a Google Chrome⁶ browser. We have tested finished user stories using a Docker⁷ container on our local machine. The docker image has already been provided in the Domain Story Modeler application.

³<https://google.github.io/styleguide/jsguide.html>

⁴<https://getbootstrap.com/>

⁵<https://icons.getbootstrap.com/>

⁶https://www.google.com/intl/de_de/chrome/

⁷<https://www.docker.com/>

Listing 5.1 Context pad action to build a resilience test template view

```
function addResilienceTest(actions) {
  assign(actions, {
    'experiment': {
      group: 'type',
      className: 'icon-domain-story-chaosexperiment',
      title: translate('Resilience Test'),
      action: {
        click: function (event, element) {
          selectedID = element.id;
          createResilienceTemplate(selectedID);
        }
      }
    }
  });
}
```

5.5 Extended Features

The Domain Story Modeler is a basic web application using no frameworks or external dependencies. Therefore it is similar to a monolithic architecture consisting of a single deployment artifact. The application contains multiple directories, where each directory corresponds to one feature of the application.

We have added directory called *runtime-quality-analysis* where we have put code for implementing our modeling concept. Figure 5.3 shows an excerpt of how our features integrate into the Domain Story Modeler. The left side of the diagram shows a subset of Domain Story Modeler's existing features. We only included a subset of the existing features in the diagram for brevity purposes. We did not remove any of the other features. The *context-pad* is responsible for displaying the context pads of the domain story elements. In this component we have included additional functions for creating the RQA tests. We have illustrated one of these functions for resilience tests in Listing 5.1. The function *addResilienceTest* follows the signature of already implemented functions in the context-pad component. We have added a dedicated action with a *click listener* that calls the function *createResilienceTemplate* with the ID of the selected domain story element.

In Figure 5.3, we have outlined the structure of the *runtime-quality-analysis* component, which implements our modeling concept as introduced in Chapter 4. The red dotted lines represent the dependencies of the *saveResilienceTemplate.js* file. The green dotted lines represent the dependencies of the *saveLoadTestTemplate.js* file.

When a user clicks the resilience test icon in the context pad of a domain story element, the *context-pad* calls the *createResilienceTemplateView* function that builds the view for resilience tests as an overlay UI element. The *createLoadTestTemplateView* function builds the view for load tests in a similar way. When the user saves an RQA test, *saveLoadTestTemplate* or *saveResilienceTemplate* build the summary and data model for the tests using the constructors of the corresponding template classes in the *classes* directory. The save functionality also implements a *generate* function.

Figure 5.3: Extending the features of the Domain Story Modeler

As of now, the *generate* function does nothing since there exists no interface for the backend services of dqualizer. However, in a future iteration, we expect that dqualizer provides a message-queue where the Domain Story Modeler subscribes to. The *generate* function will then implement the code for pushing and pulling information from dqualizer's message queues.

The *runtime-quality-analysis* component includes the folder *analysis-results*, *classes*, *rqa-summary*, *rqa-test*, *util*. *analysis-results* contains the Javascript files that implement the view and logic related to the *rqa* analysis results. *classes* contains two Javascript classes for resilience tests and load tests where each class implements one constructor. *rqa-summary* contains the Javascript files related to the RQA summary view. *rqa-test* contains the Javascript files that are primarily responsible for rendering and saving the RQA tests. Lastly, *util* contains a set of utility codes such as constants or finding HTML nodes.

To the best of our knowledge, we followed the practices *Separation of Concerns* and *Single Responsibility* from the well-known SOLID development principles if possible. Due to language restrictions and other feature-dependent reasons, the other SOLID principles were not meant to use in the prototype. We provided the input fields through basic HTML input fields by creating them dynamically with Javascript. We separated these UI features according to the RQA categories, i.e., resilience- and load tests. We followed OOP principles for creating the data model from the read input.

Figure 5.4: Extended context showing a resilience test

5.6 User Interfaces for RQA

In the following, we demonstrate the implemented GUI for each RQA test in our prototype. We explain the implemented dialogues for modeling resilience and load test within our prototype. However, as the time did not allow us to implement the monitoring UI as well, we demonstrate and explain our UI concepts for the monitoring interface.

5.6.1 Select and Open RQA Tests

In our initial drafts of our modeling concept, we had the idea to use a separate icon panel that contains the RQA test icons which can be moved onto the canvas using drag-and-drop features. Unfortunately, due to technical limitations, we were not capable of implementing these ideas. As an alternative solution, we decided to extend the existing context pads of the domain story elements to include the icons for a RQA test. Figure 5.4 shows the extended context menu hovering over the resilience test icon.

In Section 4.4, we have elaborated that using dedicated mapping rules determines which RQA test will be available for a particular domain story element. In the current version of our prototype, we did not consider the existence of mapping rules. Therefore, every domain story element can be annotated with a resilience or load test.

5.6.2 Visual Reference for RQA Tests

Initially, we have proposed two ideas to create a visual reference for the status of RQA tests about their completeness and the analysis results. The first idea was to create a color outline of the icon's border. The second idea was to attach an appropriate icon. Again, due to technical limitation, we were not capable to implement the second idea. Therefore, we decided to use to highlight the icon's border using two colors. Figure 5.6 illustrates the implementation of our idea.

A red border colour indicates that a RQA lacks mandatory information. A green border colour indicates that a RQA is completely specified. We determine the colour of the icon by checking whether the user has provided all mandatory or not. We explain the input fields in the subsequent sections.

Figure 5.5: Coloured icon for a complete test **Figure 5.6:** Coloured icon for an incomplete test

Figure 5.7: Implementation of the resilience test UI

5.6.3 Resilience Test Interface

Figure 5.7 shows our implementation of the resilience test UI in the Domain Story Modeler application. The resilience test UI opens when the user selects a domain story element and clicks on the icon for resilience test. We have attached a screenshot of the context menu in Appendix D. (1) displays the *artifact* showing the name of the domain story element the user initially selected to model a resilience test. The resilience test UI displays six input fields (two to seven) that enables the user to provide us with the information for our data model. Next to each input field is a notification icon that shows an additional information text to the user that explains the information required by using examples. (2) provides a dropdown menu for the *stimulus*. The individual dropdown items are shown in Listing 4.2 under *fault type*. (5) illustrates the accuracy value using a slider element. Moving the slider to the left reduces the accuracy value to a minimum value of 0, vice versa moving it to the right increases the accuracy value to a maximum of 100. (4) shows the collection of *response measures* we provide to the user for the individual *fault types*. (5) is a dropdown menu representing the *stimulus repetition*. The individual dropdown items are shown in Listing 4.2 under *environment*.

(6) asks the user if he wants to execute the resilience test in the production or testing environment by stating that the resilience may affect the end user of the observed domain in case it is executed in production. If not, then the resilience test will be executed in a testing environment. In the

Figure 5.8: Implementation of the load test UI

latter case, the user has to provide the information shown at (7). We decided to keep the amount of additional information small for a first prototype evaluation. We have added two checkboxes describing two distinct execution times related to a regular eight-hour working day. We got the idea from the concepts of chaos engineering where experiments often run in a production environment during and off the working hours of employees [BBR+16]. Thus, the user can decide to simulate a production environment using two checkboxes, i.e., run the test during regular office hours between 08 : 00 am and 16 : 00 pm or after office hours post 16 : 00 pm. In situations where the user checks either one of those or both, the dqualizer backend provides suitable pre-configured load tests that simulate the provided behavior. If necessary, the user can also opt for using existing load tests that dqualizer has run in past iterations on the domain story element.

The mandatory fields in the resilience test UI are marked with a (*) symbol. This is a common pattern also used in other web application forms of all kinds. After the user has provided all mandatory information, he can save the modeled test using the (8) save button. Then, the Domain Story Modeler creates the resilience test data model shown in Listing 4.2 from the specified resilience test.

5.6.4 Load Test Interface

Figure 5.8 shows our implementation of the load test UI in the Domain Story Modeler application. We tried to stay consistent with our design and color choices. However, as we require different information for a load test, the layout differs by a fraction to the layout of Figure 5.7. Similar to the resilience test UI, the load test UI shows at (1) the *artifact* the user selected to model the load test.

The input fields (2) to (4) are similar to the input fields (2) to (4) of the resilience test UI by asking the user to provide a *stimulus*, *accuracy*, and *response measure*. It is self-explanatory that the dropdown items of the *stimulus* differ from items used in the resilience test UI. Further, we only require one *response measure* for all selected stimuli instead of asking for different metrics for each stimulus. Significantly different to the resilience test UI is the (5) *Load Design* where the domain expert can design the gradient of the workload. The domain expert may either define the information fields *Highest Load* and *Time to Highest Load* for a *Load Peak*, or *Type of Increase* for a *Load Increase*. As we have already explained in the load test data model, see Listing 4.3, the domain expert may select one out of the following options, i.e., linear, quadratic, and cubic where each describes a different gradient for the load test. The last option is to define the *Base Load* for a *Continuous Load* stimulus.

According to the expert's feedback during the interviews, we included the information fields for (6) result metrics. There, the domain expert can select a metric which he would like to include in the analysis results. We used check boxes in that case, as the domain expert may decide to include all three of the metrics in the analysis results or only a subset of them.

5.6.5 Analysis Results

In the following, we will explain the implementation of the analysis results. In the current state of the prototype, we did not have backend services or interfaces that could provide us with real data. Therefore, we prepared a set of possible result description for the expert evaluation to illustrate the concept. Figure 5.9 shows the analysis results for a completed and successfully executed resilience test. Vice versa, Figure 5.10 shows the same view for a complete and successfully executed load test.

For our solution, we have taken advantage of the work by Okanović et al. [OHZ+19] about reporting software analysis reports in a human readable manner. Okanović et al. [OHZ+19] separate their report into two different section, which we also followed in our design. The first one is displayed as the red box (1) in Figure 5.9 and Figure 5.10 which shows a brief summary of the modeled RQA test. We also believe that it makes sense to summarize the details of the RQA test that is the cause for the analysis results as it makes it easier for the user to understand the results without alternating between the result and model view. Furthermore, we figured that the time until the results arrive at the Domain Story Modeler may be quite long depending on the test case and the accuracy. At this point, the user may have forgotten the specific details he modeled prior to executing the test. This is especially the case when the user modeled and executed multiple tests.

The second part of the view (2) is shown in the purple box of Figure 5.9 and Figure 5.10 and phrases the actual result of the test runs in prose text. In the prototype's current implementation, we used a prose text representation of the analysis results because a mere itemization of the key metrics would not make much sense as domain experts will likely not be able to interpret them correctly. However, we included the metrics of the analysis results in the second box as it helps the domain expert to better understand the results. In that case we also stay consistent with the original concept of the report generator by Okanović et al. [OHZ+19] where the report contains details of the experiment runs. In our design, we aimed to illustrate this by stating that a test is either successful or not by arguing that the declared response measure deviates from the actually measured values. Figure 5.10 shows this with regard to the response times.

Figure 5.9: Description of Resilience Test results

Figure 5.10: Description of Load Test results

The calculated average response time of the load test was 2x faster than the specified threshold!

By reading this, the domain expert will know that the measured response time was better than what he had specified without providing the actual response time. Based on the expert's feedback from the insurance domain, we figured that domain expert's are typically not interested in the actual values but whether their system is fast or slow. In dqualizer we will have to distinguish which metric the analysis results contain in order to provide a suitable explanation to the user.

5.6.6 Monitoring Specification UI – Concept

In the following, we demonstrate the first concept of the monitoring specification UI and our design choices for resilience and load tests. We have gathered these information in a separate dqualizer workshop that was not part of our work.

Figure 5.11 shows a conceptual draft of the monitoring specification UI. We followed the design choices of the residual UI about font size, and color choices. According to the data model in Listing 4.4, the information fields *Targets*, and *Trigger* contain multiple elements each. In our

Monitoring Spezifikation

Target for observation ⓘ
 Target...1 ▾

Triggers ⓘ
 Target...1 ▾

Context ⓘ
 PRODUCTION ▾

Metric to look out for ⓘ
 Execution times
 Count

Save Close

Figure 5.11: Base concept of the monitoring specification UI

draft, achieve to add multiple elements by using an *add* button that is seen on the right of the respective dropdown menus. In the dropdown menus, we display the elements of the observed domain elements that the user may then add to the specification object. So far, we do not have a concept for displaying the already added elements in the drafts. However, a suitable approach would be to create a small overview of the already added elements next to the dropdown menus of *Target for observation* and *Triggers*.

On the right side of the specification UI, we will request the *Metric* which the domain expert would like to observe during the monitoring. We decided to use check box elements similar to the result metrics in Figure 5.8. For brevity reasons, we will not show the drafts in this section that contain the folded-out dropdown menus of the three input elements *Target for observation*, *Triggers*, and *Context*. However, we included these drafts in Appendix C.

We would like to emphasize that the drafts are based on our personal experience. However, due to time reasons, we were not able to put much effort into the actual design of a comprehensible data model and UI drafts. Furthermore, we did almost receive no feedback in the elicitation interviews about the information we would need to collect on the domain level to the extent of the resilience and load tests.

5.7 Requirements Backlog

In Section 5.2, we have discussed the requirements as a guide for implementing our prototype. Due to time constraints and technical limitations, we were not able to implement all of the prototype requirements. However, we consider the leftover requirements as future work packages. In Table 5.2, we have summarized the requirements we were not able to implement in the scope of this work. In general, we were not capable to implement the UI and data model for monitoring specifications, thus, this concerns the requirements PR_{1,3}, CR₈, CR₉, CR₁₀, CR₁₁. We emphasize that we have

ID	Description
PR _{1.3}	As a domain expert interested in runtime quality analysis , I would like to have a separate view for monitoring specifications to focus on one test specification
CR ₃	As a domain expert interested in resilience , I would like to specify the expected response for a resilience scenario to verify if my system responds correctly
CR ₆	As a technical expert interested in runtime quality analysis results , I would like to include the response times in the results of a runtime quality analysis to make a concise conclusion
CR ₇	As a technical expert interested in runtime quality analysis results , I would like to include percentiles in the results of a runtime quality analysis to make a concise conclusion
CR ₈	As a domain expert interested in monitoring , I would like to specify multiple measuring endpoints to observe different interfaces within my application
CR ₉	As a domain expert interested in monitoring , I would like to specify a response time threshold to see if my subsystems and components respond within the permitted threshold
CR ₁₀	As a domain expert interested in monitoring , I would like to specify a <i>90th</i> percentile for the monitored services to receive detailed information about my system's response times
CR ₁₁	As a domain expert interested in monitoring , I would like to specify a time period in which I can observe different interfaces within my application

Table 5.2: Requirements we have not implemented in our prototype

applied the requirements with a *CR* prefix in our modeling concept but did not implement them in the prototype. The main reason was the lack of time to implement these requirements as many technical issues emerged during the implementation of the other requirements. We expect that in future iterations, the requirements related to monitoring specifications will not cause as many issues as with the other requirements.

We recognized, that the objective of CR₃ was ambiguous as it stated to define the response of the system. However, from our understanding this could either mean the definition of metrics such as response times, or describing response objects in a predetermined format for HTTP calls. We have included a specification for response metrics using Apdex Levels as we have explained in Chapter 4. However, we did not have the time to create a suitable UI and concept for describing response objects for HTTP fault injections or load tests. Therefore, we consider this requirements as not implemented.

We partially implemented CR₆ and CR₇ in our prototype. Unfortunately, we recognized that the metrics were not processed properly in the report generation of the analysis results. As a result, the metrics were not included in the analysis results report. However, we considered this a minor issue to fix but for completeness we decided to consider both requirements as not implemented.

In the end, we managed to implement the requirements listed in Table 5.3. We must remark that we did not implement any test cases. During development, we have performed manual tests of the prototype by running the application on our local machines and navigating through the UI using sample domain stories by Hofer and Schwentner [HS21].

ID	Description
PR _{1.1}	As a domain expert interested in runtime quality analysis , I would like to have a separate view for resilience tests to focus on one test specification
PR _{1.2}	As a domain expert interested in runtime quality analysis , I would like to have a separate view for load tests to focus on one test specification
PR ₃	As a domain expert interested in runtime quality analysis , I would like to be assisted with supporting text on the runtime quality analysis tests to get a better understanding of the required information
PR ₄	As a domain expert interested in runtime quality analysis results , I would like to have a view that shows the received analysis results to make an interpretation from the received results
CR ₁	As a domain expert interested in resilience , I would like to specify the fault type of resilience test to determine in which application context I will inject the fault
CR ₂	As a domain expert interested in resilience , I would like to specify the target for the injection to identify affected services in my application
CR ₄	As a domain expert interested in resilience , I would like to specify the environment in which the prototype executes a resilience test to receive realistic measures
CR ₅	As a technical expert interested in runtime quality analysis results , I would like to receive technical metrics in the results of a runtime quality analysis to make a concise conclusion

Table 5.3: Requirements we have implemented in our prototype

ID	Description
T ₁	As a domain expert I would like to receive error messages when I press save in the UI of a RQA test to know if I have provided all mandatory information
T ₂	As a domain expert I would like to delete an already modeled RQA test from a domain story element to undo any previous actions
T ₃	As a domain expert I expect that the visual reference of an annotation disappears when I remove an annotation from a domain story element to keep my domain story clean
T ₄	As a domain expert I would like to not switch views when creating multiple RQA tests on the same element to reduce the effort of modeling
T ₅	As a domain expert I would like to save the configuration of an already modeled RQA permanently on the domain story to reduce repetitive work in the future

Table 5.4: Tasks for extending the prototype in future iterations

During development, we have identified additional tasks (Table 5.4) that were not in the initial prototype requirements. Task T₁ was implemented partially, but due to time constraints and other technical difficulties this feature did not work as expected. Therefore, we decided to postpone it and focus on other tasks. However, we considered this could confuse the expert evaluation in situations where a user misses entering mandatory information.

Task T₂ describes a feature that we believe is not mandatory but significantly improves the prototype's usability. Yet, the prototype does not implement an *undo* action. If a user models a RQA test on a different domain story element than intended, the user had to reload the Domain Story Modeler to reverse the actions. This is unpleasant and will change at some point in time. T₃ is the immediate consequence of T₂ and merely reflects that T₂ has been successfully implemented.

T₄ is another optional feature that improves the domain expert's navigation through the prototype's UI. At present, domain experts must perform multiple clicks to switch between two or more RQA tests on the same domain story element. From our experiences of performing manual tests of the prototype, we experienced this as tedious and that there should be a better solution for switching between RQA tests. Lastly, T₅ describes a potential global setting that stores the configuration of the already modeled RQA test on a domain story. We have partially implemented this feature using Javascript's built-in *localStorage* interface that stores the data models in the browser's local storage. However, since this is volatile storage, the information will be lost eventually. Moreover, the data models only have a reference to the domain story element they are annotated to but not the domain story itself.

In conclusion, we expect that the effort to implement the residual tasks of Table 5.4 is manageable and may be finished within approximately 30 developer hours. The requirements of Table 5.2 may require more effort as they must be split into tasks first. From our experience, a single requirement may hold more than two to three tasks depending on the size of the task.

6 Evaluation

This chapter explains the process to evaluate the proposed annotation-based modeling concept introduced in Chapter 4. We have used the Domain Story Modeler as described in Chapter 5 for this evaluation.

This chapter is structured as follows. Section 6.1 explains the evaluation objective and the research question. Section 6.2 explains the evaluation methodology. Section 6.3 explains the setting in which we conducted the evaluation. Lastly, Section 6.4 discusses the evaluation results and answers our research questions.

6.1 Objective

The evaluation served the purpose of quantitatively evaluating our proposed annotation-based modeling concept that we introduced in Chapter 4. In the following, we phrased five research questions. The first research question concerns how well our proposed modeling concept improves the currently implemented processes of domain experts to model runtime quality analysis on the domain level. The second research question is about what information domain experts can provide for modeling runtime quality analysis within our modeling concept. The third research question concerns the feasibility to model business questions of domain experts with our proposed modeling concept. The fourth and fifth research questions aim at the understandability of the modeling elements and the representation of analysis results.

The research questions are formulated as follows.

RQ1: How well does the proposed modeling concept improve the currently implemented processes of domain experts to model runtime quality analysis on the domain level?

RQ2: Are domain experts capable of giving the information we need for modeling runtime quality analysis on the domain level within our proposed modeling concept?

RQ3: How well can domain experts model their business questions within our proposed modeling concept?

RQ4: How understandable is the representation of specification elements for modeling resilience- and load tests within our proposed modeling concept?

RQ5: How understandable is the representation of runtime quality analysis results within our proposed modeling concept?

6.2 Evaluation Methodology

The stated research questions investigated how well our proposed modeling concept improves the processes of domain experts for modeling non-functional requirements in the scope of DDD and domain storytelling. Thus, they required the participation of domain experts or stakeholders with profound domain knowledge without having merely technical expertise. Furthermore, our approach aimed at modeling technical specifications without demanding technical understanding. Therefore, the most intuitive approach to validate our concept and answer the stated research questions was to ask domain experts for their judgment. Another factor that encouraged the participation of domain experts is that our approach assumes that domain experts operate on an abstract domain-level to extend their domain model by additional information prior to a translation into a more technical context. As our approach is quite novel, there existed no other established solution which focuses on modeling non-functional requirements in the context of DDD and domain storytelling. Therefore, it was difficult to compare our approach to existing solutions and argue for a quantitative evaluation design. In our case, the limited amount of available participants made it worse to consider a quantitative study design.

Greenberg and Buxton [GB08] argue that quantitative study designs may even be harmful for evaluating novel ideas, especially during the prototype design, by creating circumstances that constraint the expert's subjective feedback. However, Greenberg and Buxton [GB08] promote that expert judgment is crucial for evaluating systems or prototypes. Additionally, it is helpful in deciding whether a system or prototype improves the completion of specific tasks.

Isenberg et al. [IIC+13] support the opinion of Greenberg and Buxton [GB08] and complement that in evaluation contexts which requires domain experts, there is no need for generality but rather for transferring the needs of these domain experts to people with a similar knowledge and needs. In such circumstances, Isenberg et al. [IIC+13] argue that a total of four participants is enough to yield valuable results.

For our purpose, we seek subjective assessments of our modeling concept by expert knowledge to identify pitfalls in our design or ideas that improve our proposed approach. We do not want to make broad generalizations or comparisons with other solutions, which is the assumption for performing quantitative studies. Furthermore, a generalization would be difficult because there exists no comparable solution in the context of DDD. We already emphasized in Section 2.2 that the number of available research about DDD is scarce. The novelty of our approach makes it difficult to derive testable, low-level tasks that can be quantitatively measured and assessed. Considering these arguments, we decided to perform a qualitative evaluation design as it better fits our context.

During the evaluation, the participants received a set of tasks that they needed to solve with the assistance of our prototype. We defined the tasks for the fictional domain *arthouse cinema* provided by Hofer and Schwentner [HS21] as the participants did not provide suitable and valid domain stories of their use cases. After the participants completed the tasks, we required them to fill out a questionnaire to gather further feedback and ask detailed questions about the participant's observations. The tasks and questionnaire allow us to answer the research questions RQ1 to RQ5.

6.3 Evaluation Setting

This section is structured as follows. Section 6.3.1 introduces the participating experts and selection process. Section 6.3.2 explains the evaluation schedule. Section 6.3.3 describes the setting in which we conducted the evaluation. Section 6.3.4 explains the context of the tasks concerning the fictional domain arthouse cinema. Section 6.3.5 describes tasks the participants had to solve, and lastly Section 6.3.6 discusses the content of the questionnaire.

6.3.1 Participant Selection

We have already interviewed participants in a previous iteration, see Chapter 3, of whom we know to have the required domain knowledge. Thus, we decided to interview the same participants again based on their availability. Unfortunately, one of the participants who attended the earlier interviews, who work in the taxing domain, was not able to participate in our evaluation. However, we were able to schedule an appointment with another domain expert from the taxing company who did not participate in the previous interviews. We did not discuss the background of already interviewed participants as this has been done in Chapter 3. We did not elicit further background information from the other expert in the taxing domain as he works in a similar setting to the participant who became unavailable.

In total, we interviewed four experts during the evaluation. Two participants, *Participant A* and *Participant B* work in the insurance domain, whereas *Participant C* and *Participant D* work in the taxing domain. A doodle survey has been created to schedule the interview appointments with each participant. Due to the circumstances, we conducted the interviews remotely on Microsoft Teams. The participants were already familiar with the context of this work and with the goals of dqualizer. However, we explained the context of this work and dqualizer a second time to ensure that each participant understood why they were selected. The participants were given a consent form which they had to sign to proceed in the evaluation process. Furthermore, they received an instruction document that contained additional information along with instructions for preparing the prototype locally on their machines. These instructions were sent to the participants at least three days before their scheduled interview appointment.

6.3.2 Procedure

The interviews consisted of three parts. In part one, we explained the interview's procedure and what we expected the experts to do. We made sure to receive the signed consent forms from each participant before advancing to part two. Additionally, we asked the participants if they had read the instruction documents and invited them to ask questions. In part two, we sent them the task description and gave the participants five minutes to read the document quietly. If the participants did not have questions, we proceeded to part three, i.e., the evaluation. In this part, each participant had to solve four tasks. The first three tasks were about creating pre-defined resilience and load tests. The fourth task was an open task where the participant phrased business questions of their choosing with regard to the the domain story. The participants had ten minutes to solve each task. At the end, we asked questions about their modeled solution. Then, we showed the correct solution

to the participant and discussed why and where the participant's solution contained errors, if any. After the participants had successfully worked through all tasks, we shared the document with the questionnaire with each participant and invited them to fill out the questionnaire in time.

6.3.3 Prototype Environment

Due to organizational constraints, we were not allowed to deploy the extended Domain Story Modeler and make it publicly available. Another constraint is the locality of the interviews. As we conducted the interviews remotely, we were not able to provide a stationary machine for the participants. Yet, we had to ensure that each participant operates in a uniform environment to allow a fair evaluation and reduce the risk of impediments that result from different environments. Therefore, we initially proposed three options to setup the prototype environment on the participant's machines.

Option 1 (Virtual Machine): We prepare a Virtual Machine (VM) that runs the extended Domain Story Modeler on Google Chrome within an isolated environment. We exported the appliance of the VM in VirtualBox¹ and shared the Virtual Machine Image (VMI) with each participant through Dropbox². **Option 2 (Docker):** The participants clone the git repository and install the Google Chrome browser, if necessary, locally. Afterwards, the participants start the docker³ container using the command *docker compose up*. Upon execution the docker daemon fetches the dependent libraries and runs the application inside the container.

Prior to the first interview appointment with *Participant A*, the participant informed us that neither Option 1 nor Option 2 were worth considering due to strict organizational requirements. *Participant C* informed us that he would not use the Docker container on his private machine. However, the organizational constraints of *Participant A* also affected *Participant B*. Therefore, we proposed four other options that may be worth considering for *Participant A* and *Participant B*.

Option 3 (TeamViewer): The moderator of the interview and the participants install the software TeamViewer⁴ on their machines to grant access to the moderator's browser. Thus, allowing the participants through remote access to use the prototype on the moderator's machine and browser. **Option 4 (Remote Instructions):** The moderator shares his desktop with the participant and runs the extended domain story modeler. Then, the participants would instruct the moderator on the actions he would take to solve the tasks. We indicated the participants that this option inherently reduces the quality of our evaluation results as it will constraint the intuitive usage of the prototype. Therefore, we would have considered this option only if we could not find another suitable solution. **Option 5 (Expose localhost):** The moderator exposes his localhost port to the internet by appropriate configuration of the moderator's router. Another option was to use networking tools such as ngrok⁵ to expose a localhost port. **Option 6 (MS Teams remote access):** Lastly, the participants will be granted access to the moderator's browser through Microsoft Teams' built in *grant access* feature.

¹<https://www.virtualbox.org/>

²<https://www.dropbox.com/>

³<https://www.docker.com/>

⁴<https://www.teamviewer.com/de/>

⁵<https://ngrok.com/>

Figure 6.1: Simplified component diagram for arthouse cinema [HS21]

In the end, *Participant A* and *Participant B* chose Option 6 for their evaluation appointments. Thus, we prepared the prototype on our local machines by starting the docker container prior to the appointment. The participants were granted access to the browser in which they could perform the tasks.

6.3.4 Arthouse-Cinema Domain Model and Stories

The participants received a brief explanation of the *arthouse cinema* domain which was the basis for the tasks the participants had to solve. Hofer and Schwentner [HS21] provide a large set of domain stories for this domain. Although, these domain stories illustrate old-fashioned customer solutions. Further, Hofer and Schwentner [HS21] did not provide any architectural documentation for the domain stories since the domain stories were meant to demonstrate the usage of the domain story modeler. In the context of dqualizer we have created a context and component diagram as an extension to the examples by Hofer and Schwentner [HS21]. The participants received a simplified component diagram with a simplified notation. Figure 6.1 shows this diagram.

Figure 6.1 illustrates the essential parts of the arthouse cinema domain. We explained to the participants that there are two ways to use the web application of arthouse cinema, i.e., through the official arthouse cinema website or by downloading the mobile application. The web application allows cinema visitors to browse through movies, book seats for a movie at a specific time, and pay for their cinema ticket with a payment method of their choosing. As all of the participants had

fundamental technical knowledge, we assumed this representation of the arthouse cinema domain was appropriate. To match the extended arthouse cinema domain model, we extended a few domain stories to fit the digitalized approach to buying movie tickets.

We attached the altered domain stories as well as the component diagram in Appendix B.2. Additionally, we wrote a fictional scenario for the arthouse cinema domain as a means to give participants more context than merely phrasing a set of tasks. The scenario description is attached in Appendix B.1.

6.3.5 Tasks

We wrote the tasks for the previously introduced arthouse cinema domain. The domain stories by Hofer and Schwentner [HS21] served as the modeling artifacts for the participants using the extended Domain Story Modeler. In total, we created four tasks that each participant had to solve. The participants had 10 minutes to solve the tasks individually. Furthermore, we designed the tasks to be independent of each other. This ensured, that even if a participant failed to solve a task, he could still proceed with the remaining tasks without missing relevant information. The tasks evaluated the prototype by focusing on different features. Task one required to create a resilience test for the domain story *Ticketverkauf*. Task two required to create a load test for the same domain story. In task three, we asked the participants to create a resilience test but this time adding simulated load tests. Task four was an open task where the participant had to phrase a business question of their choice for the domain story *Entrance Control* (in german: Einlasskontrolle). Task four intended to find pitfalls and misleading design choices in modeling a business question for an observed domain. We decided to use a different domain story in task four than in the previous tasks because we did not want to evaluate the participants understanding of creating or analyzing domain stories rather we wanted them to focus on a self-made business question for a particular business domain. We thought that the domain story *Entrance Control* was a better choice for this task since it had a smaller scope than the domain story *Ticket Sales*.

For better evaluation results, we derived the task's business questions for which the participant should model a solution, from an example business question that we collected in a previous dqualizer workshop. Part of this example was a concrete metric threshold for error rates which we also included in the tasks. The original question and metric from the workshop were phrased as follows.

Q1: As a product owner, I would like to know how often requests to the user data service fail to create appropriate support requests.

M1: As a product owner, I expect an error rate of less than 5%.

The business question **Q1** and metric **M1** were phrased for the taxing domain which we indicated in the text of **Q1**. Therefore, we phrased the question differently to fit the fictional domain of arthouse cinema. We wanted to evaluate as much sub-features as possible. Thus, each task had a slightly different business question and metric. Although, each of them had been derived from **Q1** and **M1**. We phrased the business questions and metrics similar to the following.

Q_{Task_1} : Find the actual error rate of the business process *reservation* by creating a resilience test with the following specifications [...].

M_{Task_1} : The error rate of requests for the business process *reservation* that arrive through the web application must be lower than 5% over a measurement period of four weeks.

Q_{Task_2} : Find the actual response times of the business process *reservation* by creating a load test with the following specifications [...].

M_{Task_2} : The response times of requests for business process *reservation* that arrive through the web application must be within a tolerable range.

We did not list the business question and metric for task 3 as they are equal to Q_{Task_1} and M_{Task_1} but require to add pre-configured load tests. As we already mentioned, task four did not have a business question or a metric defined by us as the participants were allowed to model a business question on their own. The tasks one to three help to answer the research questions **RQ1**, **RQ4**, and **RQ5**. Task four also helps to answer the previous research questions but also is mandatory to find an answer to **RQ3**. Although, the participant's solutions to the other tasks can be investigated to answer **RQ3** as well although not as efficient. After the participant worked themselves through a task, we asked them the following questions at the end of each task.

Q_1 : Was your modeled resilience-/load test successful?

Q_2 : Was the actual error rate/response time below the requested threshold?

Q_3 : If the test was successful, can you tell why? If not, why did the test not succeed?

These questions served the purpose to get more information on the understandability and usability of our approach. Answering Q_1 to Q_3 was not included in the ten minute task time of the participants. We included the task description in Appendix B.3

6.3.6 Questionnaire

The questionnaire contained alternating single-choice questions and open questions. The single-choice questions used a Likert scale [Lik32] to indicate whether a participant strongly disagrees (1) or strongly agrees (5) with a statement. This Likert scale is an adaption of the System Usability Scale by Brooke et al. [Bro+96].

The questionnaire was separated into different blocks of questions where the first four blocks were related to tasks one to four. Blocks one to three contain the same six questions. In these blocks, we asked the participants whether they missed any features during the task and if yes, which ones they missed. Next, we asked them if they understood the information they had to provide in the user interface to model a scenario for the task at hand. If not, they were asked which of the required entry forms they did not understand.

Lastly, we wanted to know if they have missed any entry forms for solving the task and if so, which ones they have missed. The question block that belongs to task four contained two questions. The participants were required to state if they have missed any features solving task four and if so, which ones they have missed. The fifth question block asked questions that were related to the analysis results and summary of modeled scenarios. In general, the questions asked the participants if they have understood the description of analysis results and how the scenarios were summarized. Additionally, we asked them to state whether they have missed particular information in the analysis results.

Figure 6.2: Participant’s time to solve the tasks one to four during the evaluation interviews

The last part of the questionnaire, was adapted from the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) TXL [HS88] measuring the cognitive load of the participants by asking questions about their frustration or satisfaction level while using the prototype. The last questions intended to assess the participant’s overall experience and opinion about the usage of the prototype. Furthermore, we asked them to compare our proposed approach to their current processes in modeling non-functional requirements and whether they believe our approach poses an improvement or not. Additionally, we asked which features the participants experienced as being the most effective and most ineffective while working on tasks one to four. We included the questionnaire in Appendix B.4.

6.4 Description of Results

In this section, we describe the results of the expert interviews. We give an overview of the time the participants needed to solve the tasks during the evaluation before proceeding to the task results. These numbers are mere indicators as some participants abandoned their focus at different times to give feedback on a particular feature. We encouraged the participants to focus on the tasks first before giving feedback.

Figure 6.2 shows the time each participant needed to solve tasks one to four. Each bar belongs to one participant. The y-axis shows the time the participants needed to solve each task in minutes. The x-axis shows the tasks by number in the sequence the participants solved the tasks. During the evaluation, none of the participants needed to skip a task. Thus, every participant solved each task successfully. The time was taken with an iPhone 8 using the built-in stopwatch mobile application.

The participants informed us when they wanted to start the task. Thus, when to start the timer. We declared a task as completed when the participant had successfully received the analysis results after pressing the *execute* button.

A first look at Figure 6.2 shows that the time to solve the tasks decreases after the participants had solved task one. A common interpretation of these results is that the participants remembered how to use the UI since they had already seen the interface and became familiar with it. Thus, the time to solve task one for all participants was significantly higher than for the other tasks. Another noteworthy pattern is that the participants took significantly longer to solve task four than the previous tasks. A possible interpretation is that in task four the participant had to model a self-phrased business question and think of a suitable metric. In the previous tasks, the participants received both in the task description. Thus, they could focus entirely on the modeling aspect without phrasing a business question and metric themselves. To summarise, *Participant A* took 4.2 minutes on average to solve the tasks. In contrast, *Participant B* took 5.9 minutes on average and *Participant C* needed 5 minutes on average to solve tasks one to four. Lastly, *Participant D* took 4.44 minutes on average to solve all tasks.

6.4.1 Task 1 – Modeling a Resilience Test

All participants successfully solved task one, i.e., creating a resilience test for the *Kino Application* in the domain story *Ticketverkauf* according to a given specification.

In the beginning, *Participant B* and *Participant C* showed confusion because they did not know where to start creating a resilience test. After exploring the application for some time, *Participant C* asked for a hint on where to find the necessary interaction to create a resilience test. *Participant B* communicated clearly that the icons should be presented more clearly to the user. *Participant C* gave similar feedback because he was apparently irritated that the context menu hid important icons. *Participant A* needed to explore the tool for some time to find the icon for creating a resilience test. He looked through the left icon panel and continued his search in the icon customization tab. Upon reading the task description a second time, *Participant A* figured to click on the *Kino Application* icon on the domain story canvas to open the context pad containing the looked for icons. In contrast *Participant D* did not waste any time on looking for the icons on the left icon panel but directly started to looking for the icons on the domain story elements. Although, *Participant D* modeled the resilience test on the wrong domain story element. He noted that he assumed the task was about creating a resilience test for any domain story element of his choice and not a particular element.

When the participants opened the specification interface for resilience tests, they took approximately one to two minutes to orient themselves and read through the individual input fields. We noticed that every participant, except *Participant D*, read through the information texts first before they started to specify the resilience test. When asked if they missed any input fields, one of the participants stated that they would like to enter numbers by themselves rather than having fixed values. The participant rated with a median value of four that they understood every input field in the interface for resilience tests. When asked if the information texts provided helpful information, the participants rated with a median value of four that the texts did help in understanding the input fields.

According to the task description, all participant selected the correct value for the stimulus, which was *Failed response*. In this case, none of the participants stated any kind of confusion for the selected stimulus. Although, we noticed that all of the participant have read the information text for the data field *stimulus* multiple times even after selecting the correct value.

After some time, *Participant C* explained that he expects to change the language of the tool, as many domain experts in their domain are non-native English speakers and would have a difficult time understanding the descriptions, thus, decreasing the understandability.

Participant A and *Participant B* read the information text for the input field *stimulus repetition* multiple times which took them approximately two minutes in total. Both stated, that they did not quite understand it and acted intuitively, selecting the default value *Once*. As the task description did not specify any stimuli repetition rate, we accepted any value as a solution. *Participant A* remarked that it is somehow irritating because the values did not indicate any kind of time related execution.

Proceeding with environmental information on the resilience test, *Participant A* showed clear confusion when reading the description text that reads *Should the users be affected by the stimulus?*. After some consideration, he identified the meaning behind it and opted for the value *yes* stating, that this probably means that the test would be executed in the production environment. *Participant B* and *Participant C* did not clearly understand the meaning but acted intuitively, selecting the value *no*. When they tried to save their specification, they noticed that the dialogue window did not close as expected since the input field for environmental information required more information when selecting the value *no*. *Participant B* emphasized the necessity of error messages that indicate missing mandatory input fields. Otherwise the user assumes that the application broke in the process. After some time, *Participant B* and *Participant C* noticed the missing input fields and read the task description a second time. Afterwards, they changed the selection to the correct value *yes*. *Participant D* did not have any problems and selected the correct value from the beginning after reading the information text. The participants rated with a median value of four that the input fields for creating a resilience test are clear and understandable.

At the end, the participants successfully executed the test and read the analysis results. None of the participants stated any uncertainties in understanding the analysis results. However, *Participant C* stated, that it is probably not the best idea to provide analysis results in prose text. *Participant B* explains that he expected a lot more detailed information in the analysis results, such as a detailed report on the test execution and response values of the system. *Participant C* complemented this statement by explaining that at least a link to the test report would help understanding the analysis results. *Participant D* shares the same opinion as *Participant B* in missing crucial information in the analysis results about the causes that led to the results. In the end, *Participant B* has voiced that the tool misses an introduction tutorial demonstrating the available features and how to use the modeling concept.

6.4.2 Task 2 – Modeling a Loadtest

We observed that the participants solved task two on average faster than task one. *Participant A* even argued, that the interface becomes more intuitive when using the tool for some time. Nonetheless, the participants successfully solved task two.

For this task, the participants, except *Participant D*, read through the information texts much quicker than in task one. *Participant D* created the impression having substantial knowledge of creating load testing as he modeled a first correct solution quite fast and used the residual time to explore the application. While *Participant B* and *Participant C* felt more comfortable in specifying a load test, *Participant A* took longer reading the information texts to understand the available information compared to task one. Although feeling familiar with the design of load tests, *Participant B* and *Participant C* looked insecure when selecting the stimulus as they did not quite understand the meaning of the available options. After they inspected the residual information that was available, they understood the meaning of the options and selected a value more confidently. However, *Participant C* selected the incorrect value for this task by opting for the *Load increase* stimulus. *Participant A*, *Participant B* and *Participant D* selected the correct value, i.e., *Load peak*.

Participant B felt confused in using the accuracy slider by interpreting it as the percentiles for the response times. This confusion grew as *Participant B* read through the information text for the result metrics and accuracy multiple times in the end. In the end, *Participant B* concluded that the accuracy must be related to the result metrics and mistakenly interpreted the accuracy as the percentiles. *Participant D* emphasized that the accuracy slider is tedious to use as it does not progressively show a change in the value which is similar to the experiences made by *Participant A* and *Participant C*. According to *Participant C*, the accuracy slider does not allow precise specification of a value.

The participants rated with a median value of four that they have understood all input fields for creating a load test. However, one of the participants rated with a value of two that he did not understand every input field. When asked if they missed any features, the participants rated with a median value of four that they did not miss any feature. Although, *Participant A* stated that he missed more types for the input field *Type of Increase*. However, this was not necessary for this task. *Participant C* commented that the design of a gradient for load tests should be made with concrete percentage values instead of abstract input fields as it does not allow a precise modeling of the load test.

After executing the load test and observing the analysis results, the participants stated that the results missed the checked result metrics. In particular the percentiles as they were not in the analysis results. Furthermore, the participants have understood the analysis results but not the cause that led to the described results. *Participant C* argued that a prose text is not a suitable representation of the analysis results. Thus, a concrete itemization of key information points would be more valuable. Furthermore, *Participant C* stated that there should be no interpretation of the analysis results. The results should include raw metrics of the test runs instead of an explanation in prose text. This opinion was also shared by *Participant D* who voiced a similar opinion.

6.4.3 Task 3 – Modeling a Resilience Test with Load

Task three has been successfully solved by all participants and almost as fast as task two. This task was similar to task one in creating a resilience test for the *Kino Application* in the domain story *Ticketverkauf* according to a given specification. Although, the specification differs to the one described in task one with a difference in simulating the production environment by using existing load tests.

Similar to task two, the participant modeled the resilience test faster than in task one as they were already familiar with the interface. *Participant B* and *Participant C* used the extra time to explore other options that were not relevant for this task. *Participant C* explained that the user interfaces misses concrete values for error rates as it is hard to understand the different options. This also counts for response times and recovery times.

When selecting the existing load tests, *Participant A* stated that it is not really obvious which checkbox belongs to the appropriate load test as the layout of the view is not precise enough. Also, all participants stated that they are missing a confirmation button in the *Select existing loadtes* view. In that case the participants opened the view multiple times to confirm that the selected checkbox was still checked.

During the execution, *Participant B* and *Participant C* stated that they expected to see the test runs of the existing load tests to some degree or at least receive detailed information on the results of the individual load tests they have selected. Also both stated that they missed absolute percentage values in the analysis results for the execution of the load tests. In the questionnaire, the participants rated with a median value of four that they understood the relationship between the modeled test and the analysis results. However, when asked about the completeness of the analysis results, the participants rated with a median value of three point five that they did not miss any information in the analysis results. When asked which type of information the participants missed in the analysis results, they answered in the questionnaire that the analysis results should contain more key facts and raw metrics but also a summary of the actual test run results.

Like *Participant C*, *Participant D* also suggested to provide a link to the actual test results in case someone wants to inspect them in detail. He also noticed, that the way the analysis results description were reported, it tempts the user to not make an interpretation himself on the results. However, this is quite dangerous as the analysis results merely provide an indication of what might have happened.

6.4.4 Task 4 – Open Modeling Task

In task four, the participants chose individual business questions that they would like to answer using either a resilience- or load test. We have noticed that almost every participant phrased a similar business question related to the reliability of scanning electronic cinema tickets.

Participant A phrased the following business question.

Q_A: How reliable is the process for scanning an electronic cinema ticket?

Participant A stated that a resilience test could solve the previously phrased question. During modeling the solution, the participant argued that it is not obvious, if the accuracy describes the p-value for experiments or something else. Furthermore, according to *Participant A*, it is not easy to understand the levels of the error rates. In particular, *Participant A* stated that it is not understandable whether these are the expected values as in the SLO or actual values of the system. This became worse as there were no concrete values to select. *Participant A* suggested to use a mapping to explain how the levels for error rates and the other response measures translate to actual number values.

According to *Participant A*, the resilience test was successful as the actual error rates of the *Employee App* are lower than the specified error rate threshold. However, the participant stated that more detailed information would be helpful in order to understand the analysis results.

Participant B phrased the following business question.

Q_B: How reliable is the process for scanning an electronic cinema ticket and how many errors occur during this process?

Participant B expressed that the task description was confusing and that it was not obvious what to do. We provided an abstract example to assist the participant in proceeding with the task. Afterwards, the participant continued by phrasing *Q_B*.

Participant B decided to use a resilience test on the *Employee App* for solving this task. The participant read through the information texts very carefully, especially for accuracy, response measures and stimulus repetition. Upon exploring some other features of the interface, the participant left out to provide further environmental information. The participant then recognized that he did not fill out all mandatory fields and stated that it is necessary to show error messages. Otherwise the user may assume the application broke. Upon finishing the task, the participant argued that it was not clear how the application knew that the resilience test was executed in a testing environment.

Participant C phrased the following business question.

Q_C: What are the response times of the *Mitarbeiter App* for scanning an electronic cinema ticket. The error rates should be none and the availability should be at least 95% after 16 : 00 pm.

Participant C stated to solve this question with a resilience- and load test. Thus, the participant wondered if it was possible to execute two different tests and the same time. *Participant C* proceeded in modeling a resilience test using an existing load test and stated that it was confusing to use existing load tests if the user wanted to model a load test on its own. Furthermore, this becomes complicated if the user would like to execute the resilience test in a non-production environment with a self-modeled resilience test. However, as previously mentioned this did not seem to be possible.

After executing the tests, *Participant C* remarked that the test run was successful. Although, the application had to improve its reliability as the resilience test reported a negative test result. Furthermore, *Participant C* explained that the analysis results for multiple test runs became chaotic and make an interpretation difficult.

Participant D phrased the following business question.

Q_D: How often does the scanning of an electronic cinema ticket lead to a false positive? We assume that the error rate is low.

At first, *Participant D* thought aloud by explaining that a resilience test executed in the production environment would be the best approach to solve this task. Then, *Participant D* considered that a load test would not make sense for this use case. However, it was possible to create a very lightweight load test to increase the quality of the results. After modeling the load test, *Participant D* noticed in the analysis results that the results from the load test disappeared, leading to the conclusion that the prototype must have overwritten the last test run.

Figure 6.3: *I feel confident to use the prototype for my work*

Figure 6.4: *I believe the prototype was easy to use*

All participants claimed with a median value of two point four that the tool required some training to use it properly. This confirmed the median value of two point five, where the participants rated the prototype was easy to use. Further, the participants rated with a median value of three that they have felt insecure in using the prototype. The participants rated with a median value of three point five that they would use the prototype in their daily work.

6.5 Discussion of Results

In this section, we discuss the results of the evaluation interviews and answer the research questions phrased in Section 6.2. Section 6.5.1 discusses how well our proposed approach improves the processes of domain experts. Section 6.5.2 examines if the domain experts were capable to provide information in the prototype. Section 6.5.3 discusses how well domain experts can use our proposed approach to model business questions of their interest. Section 6.5.4 investigates how understandable our representation of specification elements for resilience and load tests are to domain experts. Lastly, Section 6.5.5 investigates how understandable our representation of analysis results is to domain experts.

6.5.1 RQ1: How well does the proposed modeling concept improve the currently implemented process of domain experts to model runtime quality analysis on the domain level?

From our perspective, the participants did not have severe difficulties modeling the specifications provided in the task descriptions. A principle issue we have elicited throughout the requirements elicitation interviews was that in current processes, domain experts do not provide enough information for modeling resilience and load tests as well as monitoring specifications. We visualised this problem in Figure 3.8.

Figure 6.5: *I have not missed any input fields while modeling a resilience test*

Figure 6.6: *I have not missed any input fields while modeling a load test*

The proposed modeling concept improves the currently implemented processes of domain experts by reducing the amount of communication between multiple stakeholders to gather detailed information and by providing a template for domain experts for modeling runtime quality analysis tests.

In the questionnaire, the participants rated with a median value of three point five that they feel confident to use the prototype in their work, see Figure 6.3. More evidence is given by the participants when asked if the prototype is easy to use. The participants agreed to this statement with a median value of four, see Figure 6.4.

Although, our approach reduces the amount of discussions for eliciting certain information pieces in the communication process of the experts from the insurance domain, there are still some improvements necessary to increase the usability. A key concern is the missing of extensive documentation that assists domain experts in providing the information in the resilience and load test models. In addition, it is necessary to guide domain experts, at least in the beginning, with extensive examples to demonstrate how to use the prototype. This is currently missing in the prototype. A noteworthy addition to the prototype is changing the language of the tool. Some participants stated that domain experts have difficulties understanding a particular language which decreases the ease of use of the prototype. Although, domain experts do typically not have the experience to provide exact values for error rates or similar, the participants voiced that it should be possible to provide actual values to increase the precision of the modeled test. Currently, it is not possible to change the language of the prototype. Furthermore, the prototype does not include the possibility to enter exact values for response measures in resilience scenarios or percentage values in the load design of a load test. Moreover, the prototype does not offer an introduction on how to use the modeling concept on existing domain stories.

6.5.2 RQ2: Are domain experts capable of giving the information we need for modeling runtime quality analysis on the domain level within our proposed modeling concept?

According to our observation, the participants did not have difficulties providing the requested information for modeling resilience and load tests. However, there existed problems understanding some of the information, in particular for modeling resilience tests. Most of the feedback from the

Figure 6.7: *I have not missed any features while modeling my own business question*

participants included the lack of precision in providing response measures that verify the success or failure of analysis results. We assumed that domain experts should work with scored values using the Apdex measurement index instead of exact values to decrease the degree of technical detail. Even though the interviewed experts did have fundamental technical knowledge, we agreed with their opinion that even a small indication of the exact values for the response measure increases the understandability of the modeled test.

Domain experts can provide the information we requested within our modeling concept, although, we need to improve the understandability of the information

During the evaluation, we did not collect evidence that domain experts lack the knowledge providing the information we requested for modeling resilience and load tests. The participant's level of agreement seen in Figure 6.5 for resilience tests and Figure 6.6 for load tests shows that they have not missed any features. However, we must emphasize that the interviewed experts have fundamental technical knowledge that may distort our evaluation results to a certain degree. Within the boundaries of our modeling concept we aimed to describe the technical information using common language. However, this approach may lead to ambiguous interpretation by domain experts. Nonetheless, this issue requires additional evaluation with more domain experts who have less technical knowledge to verify that they can still provide the requested information.

6.5.3 RQ3: How well can domain experts model their business questions within our proposed modeling concept?

When the participants worked on task four, we noticed that almost every participant modeled a similar business question. The cause for this could be a mismatch between the domain stories used during the evaluation and the actual domains the interviewed participants work in. Another influencing factor is the time the participants had to think of a suitable business question. One of the participants stated that it is difficult to think of a business question in such a short time.

Despite the existing bugs in the prototype, the participants can model their own business questions quite easily with our proposed modeling concept.

However, we must emphasize that the current state of the prototype does not support business questions that require a more detailed analysis. This becomes evident by the participant's answers in the questionnaire. When asked if the participant missed any features while working on task four, they have rated with a median value of four that they did not miss any features, see Figure 6.7. Although, the participant mentioned several times that they would like to have more control over specifying the response measure for resilience tests or the load design for load tests by providing exact percentage values. Furthermore, one of the participants wanted to include a value for availability in a resilience test.

As of now, there is no possibility measuring the availability through our modeling concept. We noticed several bugs in the prototype that led to broken sequences and processes when the participants tried to model multiple tests on a single domain story element. Another interesting observation we made was a lack of interaction between resilience tests and load tests. So far, the prototype does not offer to make a connection between a resilience test and a load test that serves the purpose to simulate load behavior for resilience tests. Another issue is that the prototype allows to model resilience and load tests on each element of the domain story. This may not be meaningful in the context of domain storytelling as it would not make sense to model any kind of test on a particular domain story element. Unfortunately, we are limited in the practicability of our approach by the existing Domain Story Modeler. Therefore, we can not distinguish elements displayed in a domain story. Despite these issues, the participants stated in the open feedback that this approach is a valuable progression towards a neat solution that allows meaningful modeling of runtime analysis tests. Another participant voiced that our approach is a valuable asset in modeling runtime quality analysis tests, especially because it allows to have everything in one place, i.e., the model test, the domain story and analysis results.

6.5.4 RQ4: How understandable is the representation of specification elements for modeling resilience and load tests within our proposed modeling concept?

We have noticed several times that almost every participant needed to read through the information texts several times before deciding on the modeling specification. The participants voiced critical feedback when it comes to the understandability of the information fields *Response Measure*, *How often should the stimulus occur*, and *Should the users be affected by the stimulus*. However, the participant's feedback in the questionnaire seemed quite positive (see Figure 6.8 and Figure 6.9). While modeling the load tests, the participants had difficulties understanding the load peak design and the checkboxes for including the *Result metrics*. In these cases, the information texts helped to a degree in which the participants were able to make a decision. However, there was still uncertainty involved.

The representation of specification elements for modeling resilience and load tests within our proposed modeling concept proved to be difficult to understand especially for information fields related to resilience testing

During the interviews, we noticed that the participants found it difficult to make a decision towards specifying the response measure of response times using the Apdex index instead of concrete number values. The prototype's current implementation does not provide reference values for response times or other values that may be common for the observed domain story. Reference

Figure 6.8: *I have understood every information requested from me while modeling a resilience test*

Figure 6.9: *I have understood every information requested from me while modeling a load test*

Figure 6.10: *I believe that the representation of the analysis results were understandable*

Figure 6.11: *I have not missed any additional information in the analysis results*

values would be valuable extensions in order to help domain experts to get a better understanding of the individual information fields. Moreover, we have noticed that most participants mistakenly interpreted the information field *accuracy* as another term for availability or p-value. From our perspective, this is a strong indication that we need to review the description of this information field and others in order to make their intention more obvious to the domain experts.

6.5.5 RQ5: How understandable is the representation of runtime quality analysis results within our proposed concept?

In general, we can not confirm that the participants had difficulties understanding the analysis results. The participants agreed with a median value of three point five that the analysis results were understandable from their point of view, see Figure 6.10. Moreover, we even received positive feedback when the participants noticed that the analysis results included a summary of their previously modeled test. However, the participants could not explain why their test failed or succeeded. They could identify that the test was either successful or not. In some cases, the analysis results included example values with regard to the measured response times. According

to the participant's feedback, a detailed summary of key facts for a test run would yield higher value. Figure 6.11 emphasizes that the participants have missed additional information since more participants have voted for a neutral answer.

The representation of the runtime quality analysis results within our proposed concept is understandable from the point of view of a domain expert, although, the results are missing detailed information with regard to the test runs

The participants voiced that the representation of the summary in prose text is irritating and makes the results difficult to read. Another issue is that the representation of results suggests an interpretation made by the application. This representation may lead to a tempting behavior of domain experts to not make interpretations themselves. Rather it could influence domain experts to except the results as they are. Most participants stated that this could cause false beliefs about the application. Another significant issue is the lack of detailed information in the analysis results. For instance, the analysis results do not include a root cause of why a test yielded a particular result.

Unfortunately, we did not have the possibility to fetch real analysis results from external services. Thus, we used prefabricated results tailored towards resilience and load tests to indicate a possible representation of the analysis results. For the prototype we assumed a simplified representation would be sufficient to demonstrate this feature. After receiving the feedback from the participants, we concluded that it is best to phrase the final statement result oriented by listing the key facts instead of using prose text.

7 Conclusion

In this chapter we summarize our work and findings. Furthermore, we discuss the threats to the validity of our approach and the limitations that arise with our concept. Lastly, we phrase a conclusion about the initially phrased problem statements and discuss potential future extensions to our work.

7.1 Summary

In the scope of this work, we have proposed a modeling concept to annotate domain stories by information that allow domain experts to model technical specifications related to RQA without assuming technical knowledge from domain experts. We have prepared and conducted interviews with industry partners of dqualizer to gather evidence about their processes for modeling and running RQA tests. At the same time, we elicited product requirements from our industry partners by asking systematic questions about their issues and bottlenecks in their current processes. As a result, we have derived coarse-grained user stories from the elicited product requirements that constituted towards a first prototype. We have explained how our modeling concept could improve the processes of industry experts and solve the issues voiced by the industry partners. Based on our findings, we created and explained our modeling concept to achieve a first solution towards solving the initially phrased problems P1 and P3. We demonstrated our concept in the big picture when combined with dqualizer as a conceptual solution for P2. We conducted a qualitative study with our industry partners using the arthouse cinema domain story from Hofer and Schwentner [HS21] to evaluate our concept in practice. We used the sample and a set of predetermined tasks to explore the usefulness of our modeling concept and identify problems regards our concept's usability. At the end, we analyzed our findings to answer our research questions. We have gathered evidence that our concept did not miss substantial features in its current version. However, we received feedback that the prototype requires more documentation concerning how it has to be used and using reference values as additional support text. Furthermore the evaluation showed that domain experts perceived our prototype and modeling concept as easy to use even though, they were not acquainted with the selected domain model. Although, there are still improvements to make, the domain experts perceived our modeling concept as a valuable solution for the identified problems.

In light of this evidence, we are convinced to have made key contributions in the context of Domain Storytelling and Domain-driven Design by providing a first prototype that annotates domain story elements with RQA tests and report RQA analysis results to the domain experts. Furthermore, we demonstrated that a transformation from annotated domain models to a technical implementation is conceptually possible. In addition, we have gathered evidence about approaches and issues that prevent domain experts from efficient modeling of RQA tests.

7.2 Threats to Validity

In the following, discuss the major threats to the validity of our work. We ordered the following threats chronological with regard to the content of our work. Therefore, we start with the threats related to the elicitation interviews, then we continue with the threats related to our evaluation methodology.

7.2.1 Threats to Requirements Elicitation

We have conducted the requirements elicitation in the form of expert interviews, where we created a semi-structured question catalogue that we have used as a guide to ask questions to the experts. A common pitfall of interviews is a wrong interview structure, i.e., deciding between structured, semi-structured, and open interview questions. From past experiences we knew that a semi-structured interview is the best choice as it allows us to deviate from our question catalogue and go deeper into details if necessary. We believe that another interview type would not have made sense as our intention was to explore and identify potential issues which would have been difficult with a fixed set of questions. Therefore, we believe that we have reduced this threat to a minimum.

A principle threat in interviews is to ask questions that are not dedicated to find the information we seek. Structured interview questions are a prime example where false questions have a negative impact on the results. Open interview questions are another example for this. Researchers must precisely determine questions and be experienced to ask further questions when the situation requires. Otherwise, it is likely that researchers will miss opportunities to gather valuable information from participants because they did not ask detailed questions. We reduced this risk to some degree by preparing a semi-structured question catalogue that gives us a decent amount of control of the how the interviews proceeded. Consequently, we ensured to repeat the participant's answers to identify a miscommunication and ensuring we have understood the answers thoroughly. However, we did not eliminate this threat completely. Therefore, it is possible that we missed out important questions that could have led to more results.

An important threat to consider is the wrong selection of participants that do not promote towards the identified target group. In our case, we required experts with significant domain knowledge in contrast to technical expertise. We mitigated this threat by searching explicitly for domain experts within the corporate units of our industry partners and made it explicit in the invitations that we did not look for experts who have more technical expertise than domain knowledge. However, due to limited availability and a tight schedule, we could invite experts who consider themselves domain experts but also have a high technical expertise. Therefore, we reduced this threat to a bare minimum.

At the same time, our limitations promote the threat of having too few participants to receive valuable results. However, we have explained in Section 6.3.1 that there existed evidence from other studies demonstrating to receive high quality results in qualitative studies, even though there are merely two to three participants. Therefore, we consider to have mitigated this threat to the best of our effort.

7.2.2 Threats to Prototype Evaluation

The first threat for our evaluation method concerns the participants we have selected for this process. We have selected our participants from the experts we have interviewed in the beginning of our work to elicit requirements. Besides one participant, we have interviewed three experts twice in the scope of this work. A significant threat to the process is that the participant's experience with our modeling concept and idea may result in a bias towards our prototype. Although, we did not intend to introduce a new expert to the evaluation, we consider this a mitigation to this threat. Since the already interviewed experts were the ones who elicited the prototype and concept requirements in the first place, we believe that it advocated our case rather than posing a threat to our methodology. Nonetheless, we have to consider that the participant's bias may have had an influence on our evaluation results.

Other threats to our evaluation procedure are similar to the threats for our requirements elicitation process discussed in Section 7.2.1. We consider the threats as similar because we have used interview-based methods to elicit the requirements of our prototype and concept but also for the evaluation of both. However, there are of course different threats to the validity of our evaluation methodology.

In the scope of the evaluation, the participants had to fill out a questionnaire where we asked detailed questions about their experiences with our prototype. Thus, the first threat is that our questions in the questionnaire were inaccurate and did not provide enough value towards our research questions. We have mitigated this threat to some degree by using the NASA TLX [HS88] as a guideline for creating our questionnaire. Moreover, we have investigated similar qualitative studies and used their questions as an orientation for our own questionnaire. However, there is still a chance that we missed to ask valuable questions.

In our third research question, we stated that we intend to investigate how well domain experts can model their business questions with our modeling concept. For this purpose, we prepared a set of tasks that the participants had to solve during the evaluation. We consider this a significant threat to our research validity. Since the tasks were tailored to our needs to evaluate features and sub-features of our prototype, there is a chance that the tasks did not reflect the use cases of domain experts. Therefore, the method of how we designed the tasks may have influenced our evaluation results negatively. We intended to reduce this risk by creating an *open modeling* task, where domain experts could design a task on their own. Due to time reasons, we only had prepared four tasks, one being the open modeling task. In retrospect, it would have been better to design the tasks equally, i.e., two tasks with a closed scope and two open modeling tasks. This way, we could have reduced the threat significantly more. We have done more threat mitigation by designing the closed tasks around real business questions and metrics we have gathered in separate dqualizer workshops. However, we had to rephrase these questions and metrics to fit the domain model we used in the evaluation. Nonetheless, we believe we have reduced this threat to the best of our effort.

The second threat is about the tasks we provided to our participants to evaluate the features of our prototype. Our main goal was to use real-world data from our dqualizer workshops as a foundation for creating the tasks so that we can evaluate whether our prototype is capable of handling real-world situations. However, the tasks might not have been suitable to evaluate our features. We intended to mitigate this issue by creating a dedicated task for each core feature that we would have liked to be evaluated by our participants. This way, we ensured that a single task corresponds to exactly one core feature, i.e., modeling a single RQA test type. Furthermore, we mitigated this threat

further by establishing an open modeling task where the participants could freely use our prototype. This allowed us to identify potential issues in usability and observe the user's behavior without constraining the participants to a particular task description. In the end, there is a chance that the tasks were misunderstood by the participants. We prevented misunderstandings by allowing the participants to read the task descriptions before running the evaluation and encouraged each participant to ask questions when uncertainties occurred. Furthermore, we reduced the risk of misunderstanding the task description by phrasing the tasks in simple prose text without using detailed technical terminology.

Another threat is that the domain stories (or models) we have used in the evaluation do not reflect real use cases from our industry partners. Before the evaluation appointment, the participants received a description of the fictional *arthouse cinema* domain to reduce to risk of misunderstanding the domain stories during the tasks. Further, we gave the participants time to read and understand the domain stories before they started to work on the tasks. Additionally, we encouraged them to ask questions about the domain stories in case they did not understand them entirely. However, despite our actions to mitigate this threat, we still have to consider that these examples did not reflect the domain of our participants' knowledge. Therefore, the participant's incentive was not as high as if they had worked on a domain model that fits within their domain. Unfortunately, we could not eliminate this threat as we could not use real world domain stories from the industry partners. However, we believe that we have mitigated this threat to the best of our efforts.

7.3 Discussion

We have observed that it is still common for organizations to follow a strict separation between domain experts and technical experts. This separation often leads to a waterfall-like communication pattern between stakeholders that impedes the elicitation of precisely formulated quality requirements and RQA related concerns voiced by domain experts.

Yet, technical experts need to collect many different technically related information from domain experts to efficiently create a RQA to create predictions about the business application's behavior. However, domain experts are typically not capable to communicate their concerns from a technical point of view, rather, they reason about their domain from a business perspective. Considering the difference in understanding the business domain model from a distinct perspective and the impairment by conservative communication structures, it becomes severely difficult to create high-quality RQA results. DDD aims to break these strict separations and encourages strong collaboration between stakeholders leading to a better understanding of the business domain model. Furthermore, many DDD practitioners have demonstrated that a well-established ubiquitous language enables domain experts and stakeholders to effectively reason about the domain model and voice their concerns by assuming extensive knowledge from either the business or technical perspective. Even though DDD enables technical experts to get a better understanding of the domain and reduce the chance of miscommunication for creating RQA, there is yet no profound solution to connect the domain expert's RQA related concerns to the domain model.

We have made the first contribution in this context with a modeling concept that allows us to connect RQA related information with a domain model as a basis for transforming an annotated domain model to a RQA test instance. However, our concept requires concepts to be applied efficiently. The most important precondition is that the organization needs to implement DDD in their business

application from start to finish. Unfortunately, there are many organizations that do not use DDD in their projects, thus, making it impossible to make use of our concept. Even if organizations decide to use DDD there are still limitations to our concept and dqualizer as a whole. A major impediment is a disparity between the existing business application that does not follow the tactical design patterns of DDD and the domain stories that will be created as part of the DDD transformation. This disparity makes it impossible to connect the newly explored domain model with the existing application until the application correctly reflects the domain model. This also emphasizes that our concept requires a GUI that allows domain experts to create domain stories which are at the core of our modeling concept.

Unfortunately, we figured that the Domain Story Modeler by the WPS organization yields multiple limitations with regard to our concept. During the development, we recognized that it is not technologically possible to distinguish the type of the compartments of a domain story. However, it is essential for our concept to categorize the modeling elements according to their role. We need to make this categorization to determine on which compartments we allow to model a RQA test. This is also vital for reporting the RQA analysis results as the domain expert needs to know which compartments of the domain story are affected by the analysis results.

Another limitation is that the current implementation does not use any framework. Although that Javascript is a powerful programming language, it promotes creating duplicate code and using boilerplate code. Hence, leading to a huge time investment that yields small results. However, in our evaluation we have found evidence that the domain story modeler in its current state is powerful enough to allow extensive modeling of domain stories paired with our modeling concept. Additionally, we observed that domain experts consider the domain story modeler as easy to use without the necessity to read a manual or the like. At the same time, it becomes evident that domain experts consider our modeling concept as a part of the domain story modeler to be meaningful and valuable since it promotes to gather many information in one tool. In the big picture of dqualizer, it is left to decide whether it makes sense to depend on an external third-party application that is not entirely in our control instead of creating our own modeling solution. Yet, we did not find any limitations of the domain story modeler that constraints domain experts in any significant way.

Based on our findings in the evaluation, we have received confirmation that domain experts were capable to provide the information in the resilience and load test specification UI without having difficulties in understanding what they were being asked. Although, we have noticed that in order to close the gap between the domain model and RQA, domain experts need extensive documentation and guidance in the form of helping texts, tutorials, and sometimes support from technical experts. Unfortunately, this leads to the assumption that our modeling concept does not promote a self-driven process where domain experts do not need to communicate with technical experts to reach their goal. Though, it is possible to assist domain experts even more in the process by providing reference values, and additional documentation.

A prominent example we observed during our evaluation is the notion of the response measure. Yet, we have only considered a small amount of information that constitute for creating RQA tests. Furthermore, we have restricted ourselves to the tools ChaosToolkit and JMeter as a means to focus on vital key aspects of RQA test. By making this decision, we inevitably considered a mere fraction of existing tools that may work with dqualizer in the future. Furthermore, we have restricted ourselves to a single type of resilience tests, i.e., injecting failures on the application level.

Integrating other types of resilience tests will require to work out different UI interfaces that work on the observed domain model and display the requested information in an understandable manner similar to what we have achieved in our concept.

In conclusion, we have created a first prototype that sufficiently solves P1 and P3 by annotating domain models in DST with RQA related properties. In a thorough qualitative evaluation, we have gathered enough evidence that our concept improves the processes of our industry partners even without adapting their business applications with DDD. In situations where organizations already applied DDD, we demonstrated that a transformation from an annotated domain model to a RQA specification is possible if dqualizer implements appropriate interfaces. We consider this a valuable concept for a solution towards solving P2. Although, there are still improvements to make in order to consider P2 as being sufficiently solved. Furthermore, we demonstrated with our contribution that DDD and RQA could work in relation to each other using a uniform data model that leverages the ubiquitous language and mapping rules for implementing domain stories.

7.4 Future Work

In the following we outline work packages that may become valuable extensions to our work in the future.

7.4.1 Not Implemented Features

Due to a limited schedule and unexpected technological issues, we were not able to implement all of the features we initially sought to finish. A large part of a future work package would include implementing residual features from our requirements backlog (see Section 4.1 and Section 5.2). During development, we identified additional, smaller tasks that were not part of the requirements backlog at the beginning. We have summarized and discussed them in Section 5.7. A majority of these tasks concern about the prototype's usability such as enabling push notifications for received analysis results and implementing *revert action* functionalities. Since we did not focus on user experience nor on creating an attractive UI, we consider that it is in the interest of the end-user to work out a concise design template and adjust the layout of our concept where necessary. As this would potentially require the expertise of dedicated user experience and design experts, we leave it to dqualizer's stakeholders to determine whether this is necessary or not.

A significant part of the work includes the implementation of the monitoring specification UI and data model. In this case, we only have created drafts of a potential UI. However, we believe that it is best to refine these drafts.

In Chapter 4 we have introduced the finalized version of our modeling concept concerning the data models of the RQA tests. However, the prototype currently implements a previous version of our modeling concept related to the provided UI elements, UI navigation, and data model. Hence, future work packages should also focus on adjusting the prototype's version of our concept to the finalized concept.

In view of the future, we figured that the next steps shall include the connection between the Domain Story Modeler and dqualizer. In Section 4.5, we have proposed message-based communication for connecting the prototype with other services of dqualizer. Regardless of the advantages of message-based communication, we think it is reasonable to consider other communication practices as well in a thorough technology evaluation.

7.4.2 Mapping Domain Stories to Architecture

We have proposed a method which we consider to be a valuable attempt in solving P2. Based on our research findings, we believe it is necessary to provide mapping rules to the Domain Story Modeler and dqualizer to understand the relationship between the compartments of domain stories and the business application. Retrieving mapping rules requires a mechanism to request them from dqualizer before a user imports a domain story. The retrieved mapping rules enable the Domain Story Modeler to decide where to enable annotations of RQA tests. Since this also requires implementing a corresponding feature into the prototype, this may also be considered as a part of the previous work package (see Section 7.4.1). Although, we investigated how to leverage tactical design patterns for this purpose, we are convinced that this only counts for very simple RQA test that work on the class level concerning OOP. Furthermore, it is yet unclear whether dqualizer needs to know about the existence of other DDD objects such as aggregates in the observed domain for executing RQA tests.

We also identified that it is currently not possible to distinguish entities with a common denominator which exist in two distinct bounded context. In this case, it would be interesting to evaluate how Context Mapping advances our modeling concept and dqualizer in solving this issue.

Up to now we have only considered the forward mapping, i.e., transformation of RQA tests from the domain level to the technical specification. However, we figured that it is also required to consider the backward mapping as well. This primarily affects the aggregation of analysis results provided to dqualizer by external RQA tools. We believe that this is a vital step to achieve a fully functional prototype of the dqualizer ecosystem.

7.4.3 Finding Uniform Data Model for Analysis Reports

In our modeling concept, we have demonstrated that the report generator proposed by Okanović et al. [OHZ+19] is a valuable solution for reporting analysis results in the domain story modeler. However, as we lacked the data to dynamically generate analysis results from the real-world RQA test, we had to simulate this feature to a large extent to use it in our evaluation. An essential asset for the report generator which we use in our context is to combine analysis results from multiple sources in a unified data model. Therefore, it is necessary to understand how RQA tools produce analysis results and what the output is. Depending on the data format of the tool's produced results, it is important to decide whether the data needs to be aggregated and how the data can be displayed in the domain story modeler. Additionally, we consider a thorough evaluation of multiple RQA tools as a valuable extension to this work to solve the previously stated problems. However, there exists a dependency on the previous work package, thus, making it difficult to work on this extension independently.

7.4.4 Alternative Software for Modeling RQA Tests

We have explained that there exist limitations to the Domain Story Modeler. The licensing of the tool may become a problem in the future and that an external organization maintains the Domain Story Modeler's code base. These facts make it difficult, to extend the Domain Story Modeler without external interferences. Furthermore, we assume that there is currently no support available hampers actions to solve issues that require full access to the tool's repository. A major future impediment will be that we are currently not eligible to distribute the domain story modeler with our modeling concept. As of now, we consider this as not relevant since we have no version that can be considered ready to release. A thorough and detailed evaluation of other modeling libraries followed by an extensive implementation of our domain story modeling tool will be a valuable but time expensive addition to this work. This would also eliminate the dependence on another organization which enables us to make more decisions independently.

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All links were last followed on November 28, 2022.

A Interview Resources

In the following we provide the supplementary material used in the interviews. This chapter is structured as follows.

Section A.1 – Question Catalogue: - Interview Question Catalogue.

Section A.2 – Prototype Illustrations: - Supporting Material – Prototype Illustrations

Section A.3 – Consent Form (unsigned): - Interview Consent Form (unsigned)

A.1 Question Catalogue

Moderator: Dominik Kesim, B. Sc.

Datum

Fragenkatalog – Interview

Masterarbeit im Kontext von Dqualizer

Danke, dass Sie an diesem Interview teilnehmen. Im Rahmen meiner Masterarbeit, wollen wir erste Eindrücke gewinnen, welche Anforderungen potentielle Nutzer an die Dqualizer Plattform haben. Dafür werden wir eine Reihe von Interviews mit verschiedenen Personen durchführen. Hier finden Sie nun einen Ausschnitt der Leitfragen, die ich Ihnen während dem Interview stellen möchte. Ich würde Sie bitten, falls möglich, sich vor dem Interview Gedanken zu den einzelnen Fragen zu machen. Dadurch können wir die Zeit während des Interviews effizienter nutzen und können uns auf die wesentlichen Aspekte konzentrieren.

Falls Sie Fragen über das Interview oder zu meiner Masterarbeit haben, können Sie mich gerne per E-Mail (dominik.kesim@gmail.com oder dominik.kesim@novatec-gmbh.de) kontaktieren. Wichtig ist, dass Sie sich ebenfalls die Einwilligungserklärung genau durchlesen und mir unterschrieben zukommen lassen, sofern Sie mit den dort aufgeführten Bestimmungen einverstanden sind.

Demographie (Einstieg): Klassische Fragen zu Ihrer Person und Arbeitsstelle. Diese Daten werden vertraulich behandelt und im Anschluss anonymisiert.

Nichtfunktionale Anforderungen (1. Block): Hier wollen wir herausfinden, welche Methoden Sie bereits angewendet haben und wo noch Verbesserungspotential liegt.

- N1 Wie werden aktuell nichtfunktionale Anforderungen (NFR) beschrieben und dokumentiert? Benutzen Sie hierfür eine bestimmte Vorgehensweise?
- N2 Was würden Sie sagen, sind die größten Probleme in diesem Ansatz?
- N3 Angenommen, Sie hätten die Kapazität, die Zeit und das Geld um eine andere Methode zu verwenden/zu entwickeln. Welche Methode würden Sie verwenden?
- N4 Wie sind Sie in diesen Prozess involviert?

Operative Fragestellungen (2. Block): Das ist der Hauptteil. In diesem Block wollen wir uns von der operativen Seite annähern und möchten herausfinden, wie Sie als potentieller Nutzer mit Dqualizer interagieren würden.

- M1 Können Sie mir ein oder mehrere Fragen aus dem operativen Geschäft nennen, die Sie gerne beantwortet haben möchten?
 - M1.1 Welche Metriken sind für diese Fragen relevant?
 - M1.2 Wie wichtig ist eine Antwort auf diese Fragen für das operative Geschäft?
(Anschließend möchte ich Ihnen ein paar Lösungskonzepte aufzeigen und darüber sprechen)
- M2 Mit wem müssen Sie kommunizieren, um eine Antwort auf diese Fragen zu erhalten? Wie sah der genaue Prozess dafür aus?
- M3 Angenommen es existiert ein Frage-Antwort System, welches jede mögliche operative Frage beantworten könnte. Wie würde, Ihrer Meinung nach, eine mögliche Repräsentation der Ergebnisse aussehen?

Figure A.1: Question catalogue elicitation interviews

A.2 Prototype Illustrations

Figure A.2: Fictional domain story of a payroll accounting domain

A.3 Consent Form (unsigned)

Datum

Einwilligung zur Teilnahme am Interview im Kontext des Dqualizer Forschungsprojekts

Titel der Masterarbeit: Annotation-based Modeling of Non-functional Requirements and Analysis Results in Domain-driven Design

Moderator: Dominik Kesim

Teilnehmer:in:

Vielen Dank, dass Sie sich die Zeit nehmen an dem Interviewprozess teilzunehmen. Das Ziel dieses Interviews ist ein Verständnis für die Bedürfnisse und Anforderungen möglicher Nutzer der Dqualizer Plattform zu gewinnen. Auf Basis dieser Informationen wollen wir einen ersten Prototypen entwickeln.

Das Interview dauert ungefähr 45 Minuten und wird in Deutsch durchgeführt. Wenn Sie sich gesundheitlich nicht in der Lage fühlen oder das Interview unter den unten aufgeführten Bedingungen nicht durchführen möchten, dann haben Sie die Möglichkeit jederzeit aus dem Interviewprozess auszutreten. Falls Sie weitere Fragen haben oder Informationen über den gesamten Prozess benötigen, können Sie gerne vor Beginn des Interviews Fragen stellen.

Aufgrund der ethischen Richtlinien in der Forschung, benötigen wir Ihr Einverständnis zu dem oben genannten Thema befragt zu werden und alle Informationen, die im Laufe dieses Gesprächs aufgezeichnet werden, speichern und verwenden zu dürfen. Wir bitten Sie, die nachfolgenden Informationen mit großer Aufmerksamkeit zu lesen und dies bei Einverständnis mit einer Unterschrift zu bestätigen:

- Ich nehme freiwillig an diesem Interview teil.
- Ich verstehe, dass ich jederzeit aus diesem Interview austreten kann oder Antworten zu bestimmten Fragen verwehren kann ohne weitere Konsequenzen befürchten zu müssen.
- Ich verstehe, dass ich Gegenleistung für die Teilnahme an diesem Interview erhalte.
- Ich verstehe, dass alle Informationen die ich in diesem Interview preis gebe, vertraulich behandelt werden.
- Ich verstehe, dass meine Identität und die Identität über meinen Arbeitsplatz, Kollegen oder andere sensiblen Kundeninformationen anonym gehalten werden und nicht in irgendeiner Form veröffentlicht werden. Jede Art von Hinweis auf die oben stehenden Informationen werden verschleiert, sodass keine Rückschlüsse auf diese Informationen möglich sind.
- Ich verstehe, dass anonymisierten Informationen in der Masterarbeit von Dominik Kesim (Universität Stuttgart), mit dem Titel: „Annotation-based Modeling of Non-functional Requirements and Analysis Results in Domain-driven Design“ direkt oder indirekt zitiert werden. Die Masterarbeit, wird in Zusammenarbeit mit der Novatec Consulting GmbH und der

1 von 3

Figure A.3: Consent form (unsigned) elicitation interviews 1 of 3

A.3 Consent Form (unsigned)

Datum

Universität Hamburg im Rahmen des Dqualizer Forschungsprojekts durchgeführt. Das offizielle Abgabedatum der Thesis ist der 01. Dezember 2022.

- Ich verstehe, dass die unterschriebene Einwilligungserklärung sowie alle erhobenen Informationen und erstellten Audio/Video-Aufnahmen gespeichert und nur dem Moderator sowie den Prüfern der Masterarbeit zur Verfügung gestellt werden bis die Masterarbeit abgeschlossen ist. Nach Abschluss und Einreichung der Masterarbeit werden alle Audio- sowie Videoaufnahmen vollständig gelöscht.
- Ich verstehe, dass ich nach aktueller Auffassung der DSGVO das Recht besitze die erhobenen Informationen und Aufnahmen einzusehen.
- Ich verstehe, dass ich das Recht habe, die in diesem Prozess involvierten Personen, jederzeit zu kontaktieren.
- Ich stimme zu, dass das Gespräch über Zoom aufgezeichnet wird (sowohl Audio als auch Video).
- Ich stimme zu, dass eine Zusammenfassung dieses Gesprächs von dem Moderator, Dominik Kesim, angefertigt wird.
- Ich verstehe, dass ich die Möglichkeit erhalte, die Zusammenfassung dieses Interviews sowie dazugehörige Materialien auf Richtigkeit zu prüfen bevor diese weiterverwendet werden.
- Zugang zu allen Interviewmaterialien erhalten ausschließlich folgende Personen sowie der Teilnehmer: Dominik Kesim, Dr.-Ing. André van Hoorn (Prüfer und Betreuer, Universität Hamburg), Sebastian Frank (Betreuer, Universität Hamburg) und Matthias Eschhold (Prüfer und Betreuer, Novatec Consulting GmbH).

Einwilligung für Zitate

Ich verstehe, dass meine Aussagen direkt oder indirekt zitiert werden können.

Markieren Sie bitte alle nachfolgenden Aussagen mit einem Kreuz, sofern Sie zustimmen.

<input type="checkbox"/>	Ich wünsche alle Materialien auf Korrektheit zu prüfen, die mit meinem Interview zusammenhängen.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Ich stimme zu direkt zitiert zu werden.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Ich stimme zu direkt zitiert zu werden, sofern mein Identität verschleiert und ein Pseudonym verwendet wird.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Ich verstehe, dass meine Zitate und Informationen in der Masterarbeit von Dominik Kesim publiziert werden könnten.

2 von 3

Figure A.4: Consent form (unsigned) elicitation interviews 2 of 3

Datum

Kontaktinformationen:

Moderator und Student: Dominik Kesim, B. Sc.
Studiengang: Softwaretechnik, M. Sc.
Zugehörigkeit: Student bei Novatec Consulting GmbH,
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Zustimmung des Teilnehmers

Mit Ihrer Unterschrift stimmen Sie den oben genannten Bedingungen zu und bestätigen Ihre Teilname.

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Unterschrift Teilnehmer

.....
Datum

Zustimmung des Moderators

.....
Unterschrift Moderator

.....
Datum

3 von 3

Figure A.5: Consent form (unsigned) elicitation interviews 3 of 3

B Evaluation Material

In the following we provide the supplementary material used in the evaluation. This chapter is structured as follows.

Section B.1 – Domain Description: - Domain Description and Prototype Setup Description

Section B.2 – Domain Stories: - Metropolis Arthouse Domain Stories

Section B.3 – Task Description: - Task Description

Section B.4 – Questionnaire: - Evaluation Questionnaire

Section B.5 – Consent Form Evaluation (unsigned): - Interview Consent Form (unsigned)

B.1 Domain Description

Evaluationsplan – Vorbereitung

Einleitung

Willkommen! Vielen Dank, dass du dich bereit erklärst an dieser Evaluation teilzunehmen. Wir möchten dich bitten, dieses Dokument aufmerksam zu lesen. Wenn du Fragen hast, kannst du dich gerne an den Moderator (Dominik) wenden.

Im Folgenden wirst du als Domänenexperte des Unternehmens Arthouse-Cinema ein Team von Entwicklern unterstützen, um seine Online-Präsenz mit Hilfe einer Webplattform zu verbessern. In diesem Kontext wirst du eine Reihe von Aufgaben bearbeiten, um unseren Prototypen zur Modellierung von Laufzeitqualitätsanalysen zu evaluieren. Im Rahmen dessen haben wir einen Text vorbereitet, welcher deine Rolle und den Kontext näher beschreibt. Die zu diesem Dokument zugehörige Aufgabenbeschreibung erhältst du während unserem gemeinsamen Termin.

Kontext

Das Management von Arthouse-Cinema hat dich als Domänenexperten angefordert zur Unterstützung des Entwicklungs-Team für die Verbesserung der digitalen Plattform. Die Online Plattform erlaubt Kinobesuchern, Tickets zu besuchen, Filmzeiten zu betrachten und gemeinsam mit einer geeigneten Saalplatzierung zu reservieren. Darüber hinaus können die Release-Zeiten für kommende Filme betrachtet werden und Fan-Artikel über den Online-Shop gekauft werden.

Als Domänenexperte unterstützt du dein Entwickler-Team mit wertvollen Informationen und Domänen-Kenntnissen. Da das Management über keine technischen Kenntnisse verfügt und das Entwickler-Team keine Kenntnisse über die Geschäftsanforderungen hat, bist du ebenfalls dafür zuständig, zwischen beiden Parteien zu vermitteln. Die meisten Geschäftsanforderungen benötigen eine Reihe von technischen Metriken wie Antwortzeiten oder Fehlerraten für Fragestellungen wie z. B., wie schnell das System bei einer steigenden Anzahl an Nutzern antwortet. Nahezu alle dieser Metriken benötigen technisches Wissen über die Anwendung und die zugrundeliegende Architektur. Allerdings weiß das Management nichts davon und beschreibt die Geschäftsanforderungen aus seiner Perspektive ohne jegliche technische Details.

Um dieses Problem zu lösen und Domänenexperten sowie andere Fachexperten zu unterstützen, wurde ein Tool entwickelt, welches die Modellierung von Laufzeitqualitätsanalysen auf der Domänenebene ermöglicht ohne jegliches Wissen über die technische Implementierung. In den nächsten Schritten wirst du dieses Tool evaluieren, indem du eine Reihe von Aufgaben bearbeitest, um zu überprüfen, ob es deine Arbeit als Domänenexperte verbessert.

Als zertifizierter Domain-driven Design (DDD) Experte schlägst du vor, bestimmte Techniken des DDD zu verwenden, um die Online-Plattform zu analysieren und zukünftig zu erweitern. Im Zuge dessen hast du gemeinsam mit dem Entwickler-Team und Management eine Reihe von Workshops durchgeführt, um ein Domänen Model sowie Domain Stories über die Anwendung zu erstellen. Die Domain Stories wurden als Grundlage für die Erweiterung der Online-Plattform genutzt, um weitere Funktionen hinzuzufügen.

Figure B.1: Introduction document 1 of 4

Domänenbeschreibung

Wie zuvor beschrieben, ist das Unternehmen Arthouse-Cinema ein größerer Konzern welcher das Kinoerlebnis einzigartig gestalten möchte. In der heutigen Zeit, werden Kinotickets allerdings nicht mehr so häufig vor Ort gekauft sondern online erworben. Aufgrund dessen, haben sich die Entscheidungsträger von Arthouse-Cinema dazu entschieden eine Online-Präsenz mit Hilfe einer Plattform aufzubauen, welche mehrere Features anbietet. Den Benutzern bzw. Kinogängern, soll es ermöglicht werden, ihre Tickets online zu erwerben indem sie sich über den „Movie Catalogue“ einen Film ihrer Wahl und einen einen Sitzplatz reservieren. Die Sitzplatz Reservierung findet über den Prozess „Reservation“ statt. Die anschließende Zahlung wird unter anderem von externen Systemen übernommen um andere Zahlungsmittel zu ermöglichen, wie z. B. Paypal.

Die Benutzer können auf die Funktionen über die Arthouse-Cinema Website zugreifen oder über die Mobile App.

Figure B.2: Introduction document 2 of 4

Aufsetzen der Evaluationsumgebung – Virtual Machine

Im Folgenden möchten wir dich bitten die folgenden Schritte auszuführen. Aufgrund der eingeschränkten Möglichkeiten, findet diese Evaluation remote über Microsoft Teams statt. Um für jeden Teilnehmer ähnliche Gegebenheiten zu schaffen, möchten wir dich bitten das folgende Virtual Machine Image (VMI) herunterzuladen (*) und diese auf einem Hypervisor zu importieren. Das Image wurde mit Hilfe von Virtual Box erstellt. Selbstverständlich kannst du Virtual Box ebenfalls nutzen um das Image zu importieren.

Starte dafür einfach VirtualBox und klicke auf „Datei“ und anschließend auf „Appliance importieren“. Suche nun die VMI Datei die du zuvor runtergeladen hast und importiere sie in VirtualBox (oder einen Hypervisor deiner Wahl). Anschließend kannst du die Virtual Machine (VM) starten.

(*) <https://1drv.ms/u/s!AizNSGeqrBGAngjLGMMnmRrVrhL1?e=JCcEay>

Wenn du dies getan hast, öffne bitte das Terminal. Im Terminal führst du bitte die folgenden Befehle aus:

```
cd home/domain-story-modeler
npm install
npm run dev
```

Anschließend sollte nach einer gewissen Dauer (der Boot-Vorgang kann ein paar Sekunden dauern) sich dein Browser mit dem Domain Story Modeler öffnen. Du bist nun bereit die Aufgaben durchzuführen! :-)

Aufsetzen der Evaluationsumgebung – Git Repo Klonen

Solltest du aus irgendwelchen Gründen den vorherigen Schritt nicht ausführen können, kannst du auch direkt das Git Repository mit dem Domain Story Modeler auf deine Lokale Maschine klonen und ausführen.

Dafür benötigst du allerdings „git“ auf deiner Maschine sowie den Package Manager „npm“. Beides kannst du problems über „chocolatey“ (Windows) oder „homebrew“ (MacOS) downloaden.

Das repository findest du unter <https://github.com/dqualizer/domain-story-modeler-thesis.git> und kannst es wie gewohnt klonen mit Hilfe von:

```
git clone https://github.com/dqualizer/domain-story-modeler-thesis.git
```

Anschließend navigiere in die directory domain-story-modeler-thesis/ und führe die folgenden Befehle aus:

```
npm install
npm run dev
```

Stelle bitte sicher, dass du dich auf dem git branch *DOMINIK-KESIM-THESIS-MAIN* befindest. Solltest du dich auf dem Master branch befinden, kannst du den MAIN branch einfach auschecken mit *git branch checkout DOMINIK-KESIM-THESIS-MAIN*.

Falls du Probleme haben solltest, kannst du mich gerne kontaktieren unter meiner E-Mail Adresse: dominik.kesim@novatec-gmbh.de

Figure B.3: Introduction document 3 of 4

Remote Nutzung über MS Teams

Falls die beiden oben genannten Optionen nicht möglich für dich sind (ob auf deiner privaten oder geschäftlichen Maschine), dann können wir als letzte Option noch Microsoft Team's „Give control“ feature nutzen. Dafür würde ich dir den Prototyp auf meiner Maschine starten und die Kontrolle über meinen Browser geben, sodass du den Prototyp nutzen kannst.

Lass mich bitte wissen, welche Option für dich für unseren gemeinsamen Termin in Frage kommt.

Figure B.4: Introduction document 4 of 4

B.2 Domain Stories

Figure B.5: Domain story *Ticketverkauf*

Figure B.6: Domain story *Einlasskontrolle*

B.3 Task Description

Evaluation – Aufgaben

Beschreibung

Das Management von Arthouse-Cinema hat kürzlich eine Benachrichtigung erhalten, dass einige Anfragen zur Reservierung von Kinositzen fehlschlagen und möglicherweise nicht mehr dem vereinbarten Service Level Objective (SLO) entsprechen (siehe unten). Das Management möchte wissen, wie hoch die Fehlerrate für Anfragen an die Reservierung ist. Du wurdest als Domänenexperte aufgefordert, dieses Problem näher zu untersuchen und eine Laufzeitqualitätsanalyse anhand des Domänenmodells durchzuführen.

Service Level Objective:
Die Fehlerrate für Anfragen an die Reservierung muss unter 5% liegen für Anfragen über die Web-Anwendung über einen Zeitraum von 4 Wochen.

Bemerkung: Du hast für jede der folgenden Aufgaben 10 Minuten Zeit. Am Ende jeder Aufgabe, werde ich dir eine Frage zu deiner Modellierung stellen. Anschließend stelle ich dir meine Lösung, als Vergleich, vor. Bitte mache von deiner Modellierung (vollständiges Dialogfenster) für jede Aufgabe einen Screenshot. Die Screenshots werden für die weitere Analyse der Ergebnisse verwendet. Diese solltest du mir bitte als E-Mail (dominik.kesim@novatec-gmbh.de) am Ende der Evaluation zukommen lassen.

Aufgabe 1:

Beginne die Aufgabe, indem du die Domain Story „Beispiel 8 - Ticketverkauf Happy Path (Kino App).dst“ in den Domain Story Modeler importierst. Die Domain Story findest du unter dem Pfad `/domain-story-modeler-thesis/evaluation-domain-stories`. Inspiziere die Domain Story und vergewissere dich, dass du sie ausreichend verstanden hast. Bei Fragen kannst du dich jederzeit an den Moderator wenden.

Erstelle einen Resilienz Test, um zu untersuchen, ob die Fehlerrate innerhalb der vereinbarten SLO liegt für den Fall, dass Reservierungen von Kunden in der Kino App fehlschlagen. Aufgrund der Dringlichkeit und Wichtigkeit des kommenden Release-Termins eines neuen James Bond Films sollten die Genauigkeit der Ergebnisse bei mindestens 85% liegen. Da die Entwickler von keinen größeren Problemen ausgehen, kann der Test in der Produktionsumgebung ausgeführt werden, dementsprechend kann es passieren, dass unsere Endnutzer von dem modellierten Test beeinflusst werden könnten. Wir gehen davon aus, dass eine Fehlerrate von maximal 5% tolerierbar ist.

Wenn du den Test fertig modelliert hast, speichere deine Eingabe und schließe das Dialog Fenster. Führe anschließend den Test über den Button „execute“ aus. Aufgrund der hohen Genauigkeit wird es einige Zeit dauern (ca. 10 Sekunden) bis die Analyse Ergebnisse zur Einsicht eintreffen. Wenn du die Ergebnisse erhalten hast, siehe dir den Bericht an.

Figure B.7: Task description 1 of 3

Aufgabe 2:

Aktualisieren die Anwendung indem du das Browserfenster aktualisierst. Anschließend importiere die Domain Story „Ticketverkauf“ aus Aufgabe 1 erneut.

Nach einigen Entwicklungsperioden hat das Entwicklungsteam ein neues Feature in der Kino App implementiert, um die Antwortzeiten für Reservierungen zu erhöhen. Um dieses Feature zu testen, möchte das Management einen Test mit simulierten Benutzerzugriffen starten. Wir erhalten die Information, dass ca. 2000 Benutzerzugriffe pro Stunde einem **hohen** Wert entspricht.

Erstelle einen Lasttest, um zu überprüfen, ob die Kino App eine Lastspitze bei 10.000 Benutzerzugriffen pro Stunde (dies entspricht einem **sehr hohen** Anstieg) erfolgreich überstehen kann. Die Business Analysten teilen dir mit, dass aufgrund der durchschnittlichen Zugriffsrate der Benutzer, ein schneller Anstieg bis zur Lastspitze angemessen erscheint. Da sich das Feature noch in der Testphase befindet, möchte das Management eine Genauigkeit der Ergebnisse (accuracy) von mindestens 95%. Darüber hinaus sollten die Antwortzeiten der Reservierung im tolerierbaren Bereich sein.

Nachdem du den Lasttest erfolgreich modelliert hast, speichere deine Eingabe und schließe das Dialog Fenster. Anschließend führe deinen modellierten Test aus, in dem du auf den Button „execute“ klickst. Schau dir die Analyse Ergebnisse an.

Aufgabe 3:

Aktualisieren die Anwendung indem du das Browserfenster aktualisierst. Anschließend importiere die Domain Story „Ticketverkauf“ aus Aufgabe 1 erneut.

Nach dem erfolgreichen Release des neuen James Bond Films möchten die Entwickler den Reservierungsprozess umgestalten. Der neue Prozess soll dafür sorgen, dass die Fehlerrate reduziert wird.

Entwerfe für diese Aufgabe wieder einen Resilienz Test für die Kino App um zu untersuchen ob die Fehlerrate wirklich reduziert wurde. Die Entwickler erwarten, dass die Fehlerrate niedrig ist. Da die neue Implementierung sich noch in der Testphase befindet, schlägt das Management vor, dass die Nutzer der Plattform Arthouse-Cinema nichts von diesem Test mitbekommen sollen. Um bessere Ergebnisse zu erhalten, müssen für diesen Test weitere Annahmen getroffen werden. Die Business Analysten informieren dich darüber, dass die meisten Reservierungen zwischen 08:00 Uhr und 16:00 Uhr an einem normalen Arbeitstag stattfinden. Darüber hinaus soll der Test zufällig ausgeführt werden. Die Genauigkeit der Ergebnisse werden auf mindestens 75% veranlasst.

In der Vergangenheit wurden bereits diverse Tests für den Reservierungsprozess durchgeführt. Diese Tests stehen uns zur Verfügung, so dass wir keinen eigenen Lasttest spezifizieren müssen. Wähle einen von beiden existieren Lasttests aus. Anschließend speichere deine Eingabe und schließe das Dialog Fenster. Bevor du den Test ausführst, schau dir die Zusammenfassung deines Tests in der Übersicht an. Führe nun den Test aus und warte auf die Ergebnisse.

Figure B.8: Task description 2 of 3

Aufgabe 4:

Nachdem alle wichtigen Anfragen des Management beantwortet worden sind, möchtest du herausfinden, ob es noch unentdeckte Probleme gibt. Formuliere dafür eine Fragestellung die dich als Domänenexperte für die Arthouse-Cinema Domäne interessiert.

Erstelle einen geeigneten Resilienz- und/oder Lasttest für die Domain Story „Beispiel 7 - Einlasskontrolle (E-Ticket).dst“ im Bezug auf deine zuvor formulierte Fragestellung. Entwerfe die Spezifikation nach deinen Vorstellungen. Nachdem du deinen Test gespeichert und das Dialog Fenster geschlossen hast, schau dir die Zusammenfassung in der Übersicht an. Anschließend führe deinen Test aus und warte auf die Ergebnisse.

Figure B.9: Task description 3 of 3

B.4 Questionnaire

11.11.22, 02:16

Prototyp Evaluation im Kontext der Masterthesis von Dominik Kesim

Prototyp Evaluation im Kontext der Masterthesis von Dominik Kesim

Willkommen!

Für jede Aussage, gebe bitte deine Einschätzung auf einer Skala von 1 (stimme ich definitiv nicht zu) bis 5 (stimme ich definitiv zu) welche deine Reaktionen auf den Prototypen am besten beschreiben. Am Ende kannst du noch offenes Feedback abgeben.

* Erforderlich

Aufgabe 1 – Modellierung
eines Resilienz Tests

Erstellung eines Resilienz Tests für die Domain
Story "Ticketverkauf"

1. Ich habe in der Modellierung von Resilienz Tests keine Eingabemasken vermisst. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- 1 – stimme ich definitiv nicht zu
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5 – stimme ich definitiv zu

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1L8FH86iSzOEK00QpNjr6Ourj2tiQ_ug52brqpeu1zNc/edit#settings

1/14

Figure B.10: Evaluation Questionnaire 1 of 14

B Evaluation Material

11.11.22, 02:16

Prototyp Evaluation im Kontext der Masterthesis von Dominik Kesim

2. Falls deiner Ansicht nach Eingabemasken für die Modellierung eines Resilienz Tests gefehlt haben, welche waren das?

3. Ich wusste bei allen Eingabemasken für Resilienz Tests welche Informationen von mir verlangt werden. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- 1 – stimme ich definitiv nicht zu
 2
 3
 4
 5 – stimme ich definitiv zu

4. Die Informationstexte für die Modellierung von Resilienz Tests waren zum Verständnis der Eingabemasken hilfreich für mich. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- 1 – stimme ich definitiv nicht zu
 2
 3
 4
 5 – stimme ich definitiv zu

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1L8FH86iSzOEK00QpNj6Ourj2tiQ_ug52brqpeu1zNc/edit#settings

2/14

Figure B.11: Evaluation Questionnaire 2 of 14

11.11.22, 02:16

Prototyp Evaluation im Kontext der Masterthesis von Dominik Kesim

5. Falls du nicht bei allen Eingabemasken für die Modellierung eines Resilienz Tests wusstest, welche Informationen verlangt wurden, welche Eingabemasken waren das?

6. Die Präsentation der Eingabemasken für Resilienz Tests war verständlich und übersichtlich für mich. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- 1 – stimme ich definitiv nicht zu
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5 – stimme ich definitiv zu

Aufgabe 2 – Modellierung eines Lasttests

Erstellung eines Lasttests für die Domain Story "Ticketverkauf"

7. Ich habe in der Modellierung von Lasttests keine Eingabemasken vermisst. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- 1 – stimme ich definitiv nicht zu
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5 – stimme ich definitiv zu

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1L8FH86iSzOEK00QpNj6Ourj2tiQ_ug52brqpeu1zNc/edit#settings

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Figure B.12: Evaluation Questionnaire 3 of 14

B Evaluation Material

11.11.22, 02:16

Prototyp Evaluation im Kontext der Masterthesis von Dominik Kesim

8. Falls deiner Einsicht nach Eingabemasken für die Modellierung eines Lasttests gefehlt haben, welche waren das?

9. Ich wusste bei allen Eingabemasken für Lasttests welche Informationen von mir ^{*} verlangt werden.

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- 1 – stimme ich definitiv nicht zu
 2
 3
 4
 5 – stimme ich definitiv zu

10. Die Informationstexte für die Modellierung von Lasttests waren zum ^{*} Verständnis der Eingabemasken hilfreich für mich.

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- 1 – stimme ich definitiv nicht zu
 2
 3
 4
 5 – stimme ich definitiv zu

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1L8FH86iSzOEK00QpNj6Ourj2tiQ_ug52brqpeu1zNc/edit#settings

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Figure B.13: Evaluation Questionnaire 4 of 14

11.11.22, 02:16

Prototyp Evaluation im Kontext der Masterthesis von Dominik Kesim

11. Falls du nicht bei allen Eingabemasken für die Modellierung eines Lasttests wusstest, welche Informationen verlangt wurden, welche Eingabemasken waren das?

12. Die Präsentation der Eingabemasken für Lasttests war verständlich und übersichtlich für mich. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- 1 – stimme ich definitiv nicht zu
 2
 3
 4
 5 – stimme ich definitiv zu

Aufgabe 3 – Modellierung eines Resilienz Tests mit Last

Erstellung eines Resilienz Tests mit Last für die Domain Story "Ticketverkauf"

13. Ich habe in der Modellierung von Resilienz Tests mit Last keine Eingabemasken vermisst. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- 1 – stimme ich definitiv nicht zu
 2
 3
 4
 5 – stimme ich definitiv zu

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1L8FH86iSzOEK00QpNj6Ourj2tiQ_ug52brqpeu1zNc/edit#settings

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Figure B.14: Evaluation Questionnaire 5 of 14

B Evaluation Material

11.11.22, 02:16

Prototyp Evaluation im Kontext der Masterthesis von Dominik Kesim

14. Falls deiner Einsicht nach für die Modellierung eines Resilienz Tests mit Last Eingabemasken gefehlt haben, welche waren das?

15. Ich wusste bei allen Eingabemasken zur Modellierung von Resilienz Tests mit Last welche Informationen von mir verlangt werden. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- 1 – stimme ich definitiv nicht zu
 2
 3
 4
 5 – stimme ich definitiv zu

16. Die Informationstexte für die Modellierung von Resilienz Tests mit Last waren zum Verständnis der Eingabemasken hilfreich für mich. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- 1 – stimme ich definitiv nicht zu
 2
 3
 4
 5 – stimme ich definitiv zu

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1L8FH86iSzOEK00QpNj6Ourj2tiQ_ug52brqpeu1zNc/edit#settings

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Figure B.15: Evaluation Questionnaire 6 of 14

11.11.22, 02:16

Prototyp Evaluation im Kontext der Masterthesis von Dominik Kesim

17. Falls du nicht bei allen Eingabemasken für die Modellierung eines Resilienz Test mit Last wusstest, welche Informationen verlangt wurden, welche Eingabemasken waren das?

18. Die Präsentation der Eingabemasken für Resilienz Tests mit Last war verständlich und übersichtlich für mich. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- 1 – stimme ich definitiv nicht zu
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5 – stimme ich definitiv zu

Aufgabe 4 – "Freie Modellierung"

Modellierung einer gewählten Fragestellung zur Domain Story "Einlasskontrolle"

19. Ich habe bei der Modellierung einer selbstgewählten Fragestellung keine Features vermisst. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- 1 – stimme ich definitiv nicht zu
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5 – stimme ich definitiv zu

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1L8FH86iSzOEK00QpNj6Ourj2tiQ_ug52brqpeu1zNc/edit#settings

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Figure B.16: Evaluation Questionnaire 7 of 14

B Evaluation Material

11.11.22, 02:16

Prototyp Evaluation im Kontext der Masterthesis von Dominik Kesim

20. Falls du bei der Modellierung einer selbstgewählten Fragestellung bestimmte Features vermisst hast, welche waren das?

Prototypübergreifende Fragen

21. Die Darstellung Zusammenfassung der Modellierung in der "Summary" war verständlich für mich. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- 1 – stimme ich definitiv nicht zu
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5 – stimme ich definitiv zu

22. Die Darstellung der Analyse Ergebnisse war verständlich für mich. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- 1 – stimme ich definitiv nicht zu
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5 – stimme ich definitiv zu

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1L8FH86iSzOEK00QpNj6Ourj2tiQ_ug52brqpeu1zNc/edit#settings

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Figure B.17: Evaluation Questionnaire 8 of 14

11.11.22, 02:16

Prototyp Evaluation im Kontext der Masterthesis von Dominik Kesim

23. Ich konnte den Zusammenhang zwischen den modellierten Informationen und den Analyse Ergebnissen verstehen. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- 1 – stimme ich definitiv nicht zu
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5 – stimme ich definitiv zu

24. Ich hatte den Eindruck, dass die Analyse Ergebnisse alle Informationen bereitstellen, die ich benötige um eine angemessene Interpretation der Ergebnisse vorzunehmen. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- 1 – stimme ich definitiv nicht zu
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5 – stimme ich definitiv zu

25. Falls Informationen in den Analyse Ergebnissen gefehlt haben, welche waren das?

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1L8FH86iSzOEK00QpNj6Ourj2tiQ_ug52brqpeu1zNc/edit#settings

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Figure B.18: Evaluation Questionnaire 9 of 14

B Evaluation Material

11.11.22, 02:16

Prototyp Evaluation im Kontext der Masterthesis von Dominik Kesim

26. Ich hatte den Eindruck, dass der Prototyp einfach zu benutzen war. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- 1 – stimme ich definitiv nicht zu
 2
 3
 4
 5 – stimme ich definitiv zu

27. Ich hatte den Eindruck, dass der Prototyp sehr kompliziert ist. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- 1 – stimme ich definitiv nicht zu
 2
 3
 4
 5 – stimme ich definitiv zu

28. Ich musste einige Dinge lernen bevor ich den Prototypen nutzen konnte um die Aufgaben zu erledigen *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- 1 – stimme ich definitiv nicht zu
 2
 3
 4
 5 – stimme ich definitiv zu

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1L8FH86iSzOEK0OQpNj6Ourj2tiQ_ug52brqpeu1zNc/edit#settings

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Figure B.19: Evaluation Questionnaire 10 of 14

11.11.22, 02:16

Prototyp Evaluation im Kontext der Masterthesis von Dominik Kesim

29. Ich war sehr irritiert als ich den Prototyp benutzt habe. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- 1 – stimme ich definitiv nicht zu
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5 – stimme ich definitiv zu

30. Ich habe mich sehr unsicher gefühlt als ich den Prototyp benutzt habe. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- 1 – stimme ich definitiv nicht zu
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5 – stimme ich definitiv zu

31. Ich habe keine Features vermisst während ich die Aufgaben bearbeitet habe. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- 1 – stimme ich definitiv nicht zu
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5 – stimme ich definitiv zu

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1L8FH86iSzOEK0OQpNj6Ourj2tiQ_ug52brqpeu1zNc/edit#settings

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Figure B.20: Evaluation Questionnaire 11 of 14

B Evaluation Material

11.11.22, 02:16

Prototyp Evaluation im Kontext der Masterthesis von Dominik Kesim

32. Ich fühle mich zuversichtlich den Prototyp für meine Arbeit zu verwenden. *

Markieren Sie nur ein Oval.

- 1 – stimme ich definitiv nicht zu
 2
 3
 4
 5 – stimme ich definitiv zu

Offenes Feedback

Hier kannst du gerne weiteres Feedback angeben.

33. Gab es weitere Features die du während der Bearbeitung der Aufgaben vermisst hast? Falls ja, welche kommen dir in den Sinn?

34. Welche Features müssten wir deiner Meinung nach verbessern und warum? *

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1L8FH86iSzOEK00QpNj6Ourj2tiQ_ug52brqpeu1zNc/edit#settings

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Figure B.21: Evaluation Questionnaire 12 of 14

11.11.22, 02:16

Prototyp Evaluation im Kontext der Masterthesis von Dominik Kesim

35. Wie (mit welchen Tools und/oder Methodik) wurden bislang Fragestellungen in deinem Team/Unternehmen modelliert? *

36. Was ist mit eurem aktuellen Vorgehen die größte Schwierigkeit und wieso? *

37. Stellt das in diesem Prototyp vorgeschlagene Konzept aus deiner Sicht eine Verbesserung zu eurem bislang verwendeten Prozess dar? Falls ja/nein, wieso? *

38. Welche Features waren deiner Meinung nach am effektivsten? *

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Figure B.22: Evaluation Questionnaire 13 of 14

11.11.22, 02:16

Prototyp Evaluation im Kontext der Masterthesis von Dominik Kesim

39. Welche Features waren deiner Meinung nach am wenigsten effektiv? *

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Figure B.23: Evaluation Questionnaire 14 of 14

B.5 Consent Form Evaluation (unsigned)

Datum

Einwilligung zur Teilnahme am Experten Interview im Kontext des Dqualizer Forschungsprojekts

Titel der Masterarbeit: Annotation-based Modeling of Non-functional Requirements and Analysis Results in Domain-driven Design

Moderator: Dominik Kesim

Teilnehmer:in:

Vielen Dank, dass Sie sich die Zeit nehmen an dieser Evaluation teilzunehmen. Das Ziel dieses Interviews ist die Evaluation eines Prototyps um Domänen- sowie Fachexperten bei der Modellierung von Fragestellungen zur Erhebung von Nicht-funktionalen Anforderungen auf der Domänenebene zu unterstützen. Die Studie umfasst vier Aufgaben die mit Hilfe des Prototypen absolviert werden müssen, sowie ein Questionnaire mit Fragen über die Benutzung des Prototypen und Ihre Erfahrungen.

Die Studie dauert ungefähr 60 Minuten und wird remote mit Microsoft Teams durchgeführt. Die Aufgabenstellung, das Questionnaire, sowie das Gespräch werden in Deutsch geführt. Wenn Sie sich gesundheitlich nicht in der Lage fühlen oder das Interview unter den unten aufgeführten Bedingungen nicht durchführen möchten, dann haben Sie die Möglichkeit jederzeit aus dem Interviewprozess auszutreten. Falls Sie weitere Fragen haben oder Informationen über den gesamten Prozess benötigen, können Sie gerne vor Beginn der Studie stellen.

Aufgrund der ethischen Richtlinien in der Forschung, benötigen wir Ihr Einverständnis zu dem oben genannten Thema befragt zu werden und alle Informationen, die im Laufe dieses Gesprächs aufgezeichnet werden, speichern und verwenden zu dürfen. Wir bitten Sie, die nachfolgenden Informationen mit großer Aufmerksamkeit zu lesen und dies bei Einverständnis mit einer Unterschrift zu bestätigen:

- Ich nehme freiwillig an dieser Studie teil.
- Ich verstehe, dass ich jederzeit aus dieser Studie austreten kann oder Antworten zu bestimmten Fragen verwehren kann ohne weitere Konsequenzen befürchten zu müssen.
- Ich stimme zu, dass ich meinen Bildschirm während des Interviews über Microsoft Teams teile um die Analyse meiner Interaktion mit dem Prototypen zu ermöglichen.
- Ich stimme zu, dass das Gespräch über Microsoft Teams aufgezeichnet wird (sowohl Audio als auch Video).
- Ich verstehe, dass ich keine Gegenleistung für die Teilnahme an dieser Studie erhalte.
- Ich verstehe, dass alle Informationen die ich in dieser Studie preis gebe, vertraulich behandelt werden.

1 von 3

Figure B.24: Consent form (unsigned) expert evaluation 1 of 3

Datum

- Ich verstehe, dass meine Identität und die Identität über meinen Arbeitsplatz, Kollegen oder andere sensiblen Kundeninformationen anonym gehalten werden und nicht in irgendeiner Form veröffentlicht werden. Jede Art von Hinweis auf die oben stehenden Informationen werden verschleiert, sodass keine Rückschlüsse auf diese Informationen möglich sind.
- Ich verstehe, dass anonymisierten Informationen in der Masterarbeit von Dominik Kesim (Universität Stuttgart), mit dem Titel: „Annotation-based Modeling of Non-functional Requirements and Analysis Results in Domain-driven Design“ direkt oder indirekt zitiert werden. Die Masterarbeit, wird in Zusammenarbeit mit der Novatec Consulting GmbH und der Universität Hamburg im Rahmen des Dqualizer Forschungsprojekts durchgeführt. Das offizielle Abgabedatum der Thesis ist der 01. Dezember 2022.
- Ich verstehe, dass die unterschriebene Einwilligungserklärung sowie alle erhobenen Informationen und erstellten Audio/Video-Aufnahmen gespeichert und nur dem Moderator sowie den Prüfern der Masterarbeit zur Verfügung gestellt werden bis die Masterarbeit abgeschlossen ist. Nach Abschluss und Einreichung der Masterarbeit werden alle Audio- sowie Videoaufnahmen vollständig gelöscht.
- Ich verstehe, dass ich nach aktueller Auffassung der DSGVO das Recht besitze die erhobenen Informationen und Aufnahmen einzusehen.
- Ich verstehe, dass ich das Recht habe, die in diesem Prozess involvierten Personen, jederzeit zu kontaktieren.
- Ich verstehe, dass ich die Möglichkeit erhalte, die Zusammenfassung dieses Interviews sowie dazugehörige Materialien auf Richtigkeit zu prüfen bevor diese weiterverwendet werden.
- Zugang zu allen Studienmaterialien erhalten ausschließlich folgende Personen sowie der Teilnehmer: Dominik Kesim, Dr.-Ing. André van Hoorn (Prüfer und Betreuer, Universität Hamburg), Sebastian Frank (Betreuer, Universität Hamburg) und Matthias Eschhold (Prüfer und Betreuer, Novatec Consulting GmbH).

Einwilligung für Zitate

Ich verstehe, dass meine Aussagen direkt oder indirekt zitiert werden können.
Markieren Sie bitte alle nachfolgenden Aussagen mit einem Kreuz, sofern Sie zustimmen.

<input type="checkbox"/>	Ich wünsche alle Materialien auf Korrektheit zu prüfen, die mit meinem Interview zusammenhängen.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Ich stimme zu direkt zitiert zu werden.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Ich stimme zu direkt zitiert zu werden, sofern mein Identität verschleiert und ein Pseudonym verwendet wird.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Ich verstehe, dass meine Zitate und Informationen in der Masterarbeit von Dominik Kesim publiziert werden könnten.

2 von 3

Figure B.25: Consent form (unsigned) expert evaluation 2 of 3

Datum

Kontaktinformationen:

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Zustimmung des Teilnehmers

Mit Ihrer Unterschrift stimmen Sie den oben genannten Bedingungen zu und bestätigen Ihre Teilname.

..... Datum

Zustimmung des Moderators

..... Datum

Figure B.26: Consent form (unsigned) expert evaluation 3 of 3

C Drafts

In the following we provide the drafts of our concept for the monitoring specification ui. This chapter is structured as follows.

Section C.1 – Monitoring Specification UI – Drafts: - Monitoring Specification UI Drafts

C.1 Monitoring Specification UI – Drafts

The image shows a hand-drawn UI mockup titled "Monitoring Spezifikation". It features two columns of controls. The left column has a "Target for observation" dropdown with "Target_1" selected, a "Triggers" dropdown with "Target_1" selected and a list of "Target_2", "Target_3", "Target_4", and "Target_5" visible below it, and "Save" and "Close" buttons at the bottom. The right column has a "Metric to look out for" section with two checkboxes: "Execution times" and "Count", both of which are unchecked. Information icons (i) are placed next to the labels for "Target for observation", "Triggers", and "Metric to look out for".

Figure C.1: Monitoring folded out dropdown of *Triggers*

The image shows a hand-drawn UI mockup titled "Monitoring Spezifikation". It features two columns of controls. The left column has a "Target for observation" dropdown with "Target_1" selected, a "Triggers" dropdown with "Target_1" selected, and a "Context" dropdown with "PRODUCTION" selected and "TESTING" visible below it. "Save" and "Close" buttons are at the bottom. The right column has a "Metric to look out for" section with two checkboxes: "Execution times" and "Count", both of which are unchecked. Information icons (i) are placed next to the labels for "Target for observation", "Triggers", and "Context".

Figure C.2: Monitoring folded out dropdown of *Context*

D Prototype UI Screenshots

In the following we provide screenshots of our prototype which we did not show in Chapter 4. This chapter is structured as follows.

Section D.1 – Domain Story Modeler Modified Context Menu: - Extended context menus of domain story elements

D.1 Domain Story Modeler Modified Context Menu

Figure D.1: Context Menu of the *Kino Application* that shows the resilience test icon

Figure D.2: Context Menu of the *Kino Application* that shows the load test icon

Declaration

I hereby declare that the work presented in this thesis is entirely my own and that I did not use any other sources and references than the listed ones. I have marked all direct or indirect statements from other sources contained therein as quotations. Neither this work nor significant parts of it were part of another examination procedure. I have not published this work in whole or in part before. The electronic copy is consistent with all submitted copies.

Haiterbach, der 29.11.2022

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'Klein', written over a horizontal line.

place, date, signature